
D3.1 / First report on digital biomarkers for PD

Editor

Christos Chatzichristos
(KUL)

Contractual delivery

October 2024

Actual delivery

December 2024

Deliverable type

R - Document, report

Dissemination level

PU – Public

Version - date

1.0 - 16/12/2024

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Deliverable ID

Project acronym	AI-PROGNOSIS
Project full title	Artificial intelligence-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis
Grant Agreement ID	101080581
Deliverable number	D3.1
Deliverable title	First report on digital biomarkers for PD
Work package	WP3 - Predicting PD risk, progression and medication response
Deliverable type	R - Document, report
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Version - date	1.0 - 16/12/2024
Contractual delivery	October 2024
Actual delivery	December 2024
Lead partner	KUL
Editor	Christos Chatzichristos (KUL)
Contributors	Sofia Balula Dias (FMH); Christos Chatzichristos, Maarten De Vos, Georgios Roussis (KUL); Ioannis Gerasimou, Apostolos Moustaklis, Harris Sotirakis, Stelios Hadjidimitriou (AUTH); Nikos Grammalidis, Theocharis Chatzis (CERTH); Tim Feige (TUD)
Reviewed by	Angeliki Zarifi (AING) Dhaval Trivedi (KCL)
Approved by	Leontios Hadjileontiadis (AUTH, Project Coordinator)
Keywords	Acceleration; Balance; bradykinesia; cognitive function; cognitive test; daytime somnolence; digital assessment; digital biomarker; dyskinesia; keystroke dynamics; motor assessment; Parkinson's disease; physical activity; posture; rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder; RBD; rest tremor; rigidity; typing; wearable

Document history

Version	Date	Contributors	Action / status
0.1	19/07/2024	KUL	Initial document structure (table of contents)
0.2	31/07/2024	KUL, AUTH	Final document structure (table of contents), updated after meeting with AUTH
0.3	01/10/2024	KUL, AUTH, CERTH, FMH, TUD	Pre-final version of the deliverable submitted for review to clinical partners
0.4	11/10/2024	KUL, AUTH	Ready for internal review
0.5	30/10/2024	AING	Reviewed by Angeliki Zarifi (AING)
0.6	31/10/2024	KCL	Reviewed by Dhaval Trivedi (KCL)
0.7	25/11/2024	KUL, CERTH, AUTH, FMH	Document revised
0.8	04/12/2024	AUTH, KUL, CERTH	Quality checked by Project Coordinator; Document revised
0.9	16/12/2024	KUL, TUD, CERTH	Update of section 11; Approved for submission by the Project Coordinator
1.0	16/12/2024	AUTH	Submitted version

Contents

List of figures	9
List of tables.....	11
List of abbreviations	13
Executive summary.....	15
1 Introduction	17
1.1 Document scope.....	17
1.2 Document structure	17
2 CTTI recommendations and Trustworthy AI	18
2.1 CTTI recommendations	18
2.2 Trustworthy AI Framework of AI-PROGNOSIS.....	19
2.3 Connection of CTTI recommendations and Trustworthy AI principles	20
2.3.1 Transparency and Accountability	20
2.3.2 Data Integrity and Security	20
2.3.3 Fairness and Inclusivity	20
2.3.4 Human-Centric Design	21
2.3.5 Explainability	21
2.4 Summary and key concepts.....	21
3 Rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder tracking	21
3.1 Background and objectives.....	21
3.2 Methods	22
3.2.1 Datasets.....	22
3.2.2 Digital biomarkers	27
3.3 Results	28
3.3.1 Descriptive statistics of potential digital biomarkers.....	28
3.3.2 Machine learning-based classification of RBD.....	31
3.4 Discussion	34
3.4.1 Interpretation.....	34
3.4.2 Limitations.....	34
3.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care	35
3.5 Summary	35
4 Daytime somnolence tracking	35
4.1 Background and objectives.....	35
4.2 Methods	36
4.2.1 Datasets.....	36
4.2.2 Digital biomarkers	36

4.3 Results	38
4.4 Discussion	39
4.4.1 Interpretation	39
4.4.2 Limitations	39
4.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care	40
4.5 Summary	40
5 Rest tremor tracking	41
5.1.1 Background and objectives	41
5.2 Methods	41
5.2.1 Datasets	41
5.2.2 Data pre-processing	45
5.2.3 Digital biomarkers	45
5.3 Results	49
5.3.1 Selection of digital biomarkers	49
5.4 Discussion	52
5.4.1 Interpretation	52
5.4.2 Limitations	52
5.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care	52
5.5 Summary	52
6 Dyskinesia tracking	53
6.1 Background and objectives	53
6.2 Methods	54
6.2.1 Datasets	54
6.2.2 Digital biomarkers	54
6.3 Discussion	54
6.3.1 Limitations	54
6.3.2 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care	54
6.4 Summary	55
7 Human activity recognition and physical activity tracking	55
7.1 Background and objectives	55
7.2 Methods	56
7.2.1 Datasets	56
7.2.2 Data pre-processing	57
7.2.3 Digital biomarkers	58
7.3 Results	59
7.3.1 Selection of digital biomarkers	59
7.4 Discussion	62

7.4.1 Interpretation.....	62
7.4.2 Limitations.....	62
7.4.3 Usability of digital biomarkers in the context of current care	62
7.5 Summary.....	62
8 Slowness of movement tracking with keystroke dynamics.....	63
8.1 Background and objectives.....	63
8.2 Methods	63
8.2.1 Datasets.....	63
8.2.2 Data pre-processing.....	65
8.2.3 Digital biomarkers	66
8.2.4 Sample characteristics	67
8.2.5 Selection of digital biomarkers.....	69
8.3 Discussion.....	71
8.3.1 Interpretation.....	71
8.3.2 Limitations.....	71
8.3.3 Usability of digital biomarkers in the context of current care	71
8.4 Summary.....	72
9 Slowness of movement tracking with wrist accelerometry	72
9.1 Background and objectives.....	72
9.2 Methods	73
9.2.1 Datasets.....	73
9.2.2 Data pre-processing.....	73
9.2.3 Digital biomarkers	74
9.3 Results	76
9.3.1 Sample characteristics	76
9.3.2 Validation of slowness of movement estimator.....	76
9.3.3 Selection of digital biomarkers.....	77
9.4 Discussion.....	78
9.4.1 Interpretation.....	78
9.4.2 Limitations.....	78
9.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care	78
9.5 Summary.....	79
10 Comprehensive motor function active assessment.....	79
10.1 Background and objectives.....	79
10.2 Methods.....	80
10.2.1 Datasets.....	81
10.2.2 Data pre-processing	83

10.2.3 Digital biomarkers	84
10.3 Results	87
10.3.1 Selection of digital biomarkers.....	87
10.3.2 Patient and public involvement.....	89
10.4 Discussion	94
10.4.1 Interpretation.....	94
10.4.2 Limitations.....	95
10.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care	95
10.5 Summary.....	96
11 Cognitive function active assessment.....	97
11.1 Background and objectives.....	97
11.2 Methods.....	97
11.2.1 Datasets.....	97
11.2.2 Digital biomarkers	98
11.2.3 Selection of digital biomarkers.....	101
11.3 Results	102
11.4 Discussion	102
11.4.1 Interpretation.....	102
11.4.2 Usability of digital biomarkers in the context of current care	103
11.5 Summary.....	103
12 Open science	104
12.1 Data sharing and accessibility	104
12.2 Collaborative Research and Multi-Stakeholder Engagement	104
12.3 Publication and reporting standards.....	104
13 Conclusions	104
References	108
Appendix I – Interview guide script for the CMFT co-creation session.....	114
Appendix II – Supplementary documents.....	115
S.1 Approval of the small-scale data collection in Papanikolaou General Hospital of Thessaloniki for the CMFT development (in Greek).....	115
S.2 Consent form for the small-scale data collection in Papanikolaou General Hospital of Thessaloniki for the CMFT development (in Greek).....	115

List of figures

Figure 1 Actigraphy data from specific subjects (healthy, apneic, with RBD) of RBD-Czech	23
Figure 2 Visualization of an unprocessed data sample of iRBDSG explaining processed values.	24
Figure 3 Representative data samples from two participants of iRBDSG. ZCM: zero-crossing, PIM: Signal's integral (as seen in Figure 2). Data pre-processing	24
Figure 4 Limits of the sleep period based on first algorithm. The blue signal represents the raw actigraphy data, i.e., acceleration vs. time, and the red vertical lines depict the start and end boundaries of sleep as detected by each algorithm.....	25
Figure 5 Limits of the sleep period based on the second algorithm. The blue signal represents the raw actigraphy data, i.e., acceleration vs. time, and the red vertical lines depict the start and end boundaries of sleep as detected by each algorithm.....	25
Figure 6 Boxplots of activity rate for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.....	29
Figure 7 Boxplots of the number of movement episodes for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.....	29
Figure 8 Boxplots of the mean duration of movement episodes for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.	30
Figure 9 Boxplots of mean distance between movement episodes for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.	30
Figure 10 Boxplots of episodes per minute for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.	30
Figure 11 Distribution of activity rate per group, RBD (blue) and non-RBD (pink).....	33
Figure 12 The Philips Actiware weights for the calculation of total activity for 30 s sampling epochs (x represents the multiplication of each segment with a weight). The current epoch is the one in the middle which is multiplied by 2. The x-axis is the different segments before and after the current one.....	36
Figure 13 Pipeline of the clustering method for detecting naps.....	37
Figure 14 Examples of sleep segments in two distinct subjects detected during the day for each method.	39
Figure 15 Overview of the hand movement classifier.	46
Figure 16 Overview of the rest tremor detection and assessment pipeline.	46
Figure 17 Overview of the human activity recognition (HAR) pipeline.....	58
Figure 18 Confusion Matrix on the MJFF-LRS dataset.	60
Figure 19 Confusion matrix on the Capture-24 dataset.	61
Figure 20 Feature vector estimation pipeline from keystroke timing data of a single typing session. HT: hold time; FT: flight time; NFT: normalised flight time; std: standard deviation; skew: skewness.	66
Figure 21 Representation of keystroke events and keystroke dynamics variables.....	66
Figure 22 Distribution of scores of UPDRS Part III items of interest (22, 23, 31) for PwPD and controls, as well as for each group separately, in the in-clinic dataset.....	68
Figure 23 Distribution of scores of UPDRS Part III items of interest (22, 23, 31) for PwPD and controls, as well as for each group separately, in the in-the-wild dataset.....	68
Figure 24 Digital scores (Prediction) with respect to the clinical score of each UPDRS Part III item of interest (ground truth) for a single, complete run of the LOSO cross-validation scheme on the in-clinic dataset.	69
Figure 25 Digital scores (Prediction) of the in-the-wild sample with respect to the clinical score of each UPDRS Part III item of interest (ground truth) for a sample run.	70

Figure 26 Slowness of movement assessment pipeline from keystroke dynamics.	71
Figure 27 Pipeline for slowness of movement assessment from wrist accelerometry.	74
Figure 28 ROC curves and AUCs of the two types of models developed for gait classification.	75
Figure 29 Time-wise classification of hand movement and gait presence over a 10-min period of slowness of movement estimation. Slowness of movement features are extracted only for 5-s windows classified as having hand movement and absence of gait in 30-s valid intervals (with hand movement and absence of gait based on majority voting on classifications of constituent 5-s windows).	76
Figure 30 Distributions of the estimated digital scores grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement score. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$, ** $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$	77
Figure 31 Distributions of the estimated digital scores grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the MDS-UPDRS Item 3.14 (Global spontaneity of movement) score. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$, ** $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$, ns not significant.	78
Figure 32 Camera recordings from CMFT corresponding to four MDS-UPDRS items for assessing motor skills: (a) item 3.8 (Leg agility), (b) item 3.9 (Arising from chair), (c) item 3.13 (Posture), (d) item 3.10 (Gait).	81
Figure 33 Video capture set-up for collecting CMF development data.	82
Figure 34 Overview of the data processing pipeline of the CMFT.	83
Figure 35 Mediapipe body landmark locations.	83
Figure 36 Time series of x and y coordinates of the detected landmarks of a user (with ID=11 and clinical UPDRS scores of the performed items 1,0,0,1,2,2, respectively) that performed the CMFT movement sequence; ($center_x$, $center_y$) are the coordinates of the midpoint between hips (landmarks 23 and 24).	85
Figure 37 Mock-ups of the Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) prototype presented during the co-creation session, including: 1) Main menu screen, 2) Set-up instructions screen, 3) Motor test instructions screen, 4) Countdown screen, and 5) Motor test recording.	90
Figure 38 Overview of the main findings derived from the thematic analysis.	92
Figure 39 Indicative screenshot of the stop-signal test. Depicted is the 4:3 aspect ratio from the iPad Version used in Feige et al. (2024).	99
Figure 40 Indicative screenshot of the Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART). Depicted is the 4:3 aspect ratio from the iPad Version used in Feige et al. (2024).	100
Figure 41 Indicative screenshot of the N-Back Task. Depicted is the 4:3 aspect ratio from the iPad Version used in Feige et al. (2024).	101

List of tables

Table 1 RBD datasets.....	22
Table 2 Potential RBD Biomarkers	27
Table 3 Values test for the hyperparameters of each method using grid-search	31
Table 4 Results of different models with different number of features for RBD-Czech dataset	32
Table 5 Results of different models with SMOTE for RBD-Czech dataset.....	33
Table 6 Results of different models with and without augmentation for iRBDSG dataset with the 8-best features	33
Table 7 Results of different models with SMOTE for RBD-Czech dataset with artifact removal.	34
Table 8 Overall percentage of the clustering-based detected naps that can be validated from a) the participants' diaries and/or b) visual inspection.	39
Table 9 Demographic and clinical characteristics for MJFF-LRS dataset.....	43
Table 10 Demographic and clinical characteristics of Verily Study Watch subset used for the validation of the rest tremor digital biomarker.	44
Table 11 Features extracted for training the tremor detector of the ML-based method. Asterisks (*) indicate the features that survived after the feature selection step.	49
Table 12 Rest tremor detection performance on the MJFF-LRS dataset.....	50
Table 13 Rest tremor amplitude classification results on the MJFF-LRS dataset, using various metrics.	51
Table 14 Rest tremor detection results on the Verily Study Watch dataset using the ML-based method.....	51
Table 15 Rest tremor amplitude classification results on the Verily Study Watch dataset, using various metrics.....	51
Table 16 Demographic information of Capture-24 participants.	56
Table 17 Performance of the HAR model fine-tuned on the MJFF-LRS dataset.	59
Table 18 Performance of the HAR model fine-tuned on the Capture-24 dataset.....	61
Table 19 Clinico-demographic characteristics of the subjects that generated the in-clinic typing dataset. N.A.: not applicable.	64
Table 20 Clinico-demographic characteristics of the subjects that generated the in-the-wild typing dataset. N.A.: not applicable.	65
Table 21 Clinico-demographic characteristics of the participants in the in-the-wild dataset after applying the conditions for typing session length (>40 key taps) and number of available typing sessions (>10).	67
Table 22 Performance of the model trained and tested on the in-clinic dataset; CI: confidence interval.	69
Table 23 Performance of the model trained on the in-clinic dataset and tested on the in-the-wild dataset; CI: confidence interval.	70
Table 24 Performance of the model trained on the in-clinic dataset and tested on the in-the-wild dataset, with data only from PwPD in both cases; CI: confidence interval.	70
Table 25 Demographic and clinical characteristics of Verily Study Watch subset used for the development of the wrist accelerometry-based dBMs of slowness of movement. N.A.: not applicable.....	73
Table 26 Features extracted in each 5-s window for gait classifier.....	75
Table 27 Results for the two models train to estimate bradykinesia	77
Table 28 Demographics of the participants in the CMFT development study.....	82
Table 29 Joint angles of interest for each movement of the CMFT (and associated MDS-UPDRS item).	85

Table 30 Features (31 in total) that are computed from each angle time series 86

Table 31 Features with maximum correlation kept for each motion item 87

Table 32 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for each MDS-UPDRS item of interest and all classifiers derived from LOSO validation. Best F1 scores for each item are shown in bold..... 88

Table 33 Demographic characteristics of the involved participants; PwPD: People with Parkinson’s disease. 91

Table 34 Demographics of the subjects included in the active cognitive tests dataset 98

Table 35 Features extracted from the Stop-Signal task. 99

Table 36 Features extracted from the Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART). 100

Table 37 Features extracted from the N-Back task; n-back level $\equiv n$ 101

Table 38 Features with maximum correlation with MoCA scores 101

Table 39 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall, and F1 scores for ML classifiers after hypertuning (with or without using feature selection) using Leave One Out cross-validation. Best performing ML classifiers are shown in bold..... 102

Table 40 Summary table with Objectives, Key Features, Results and Challenges for all dBMs 105

List of abbreviations

ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AoT	Arrow of Time
BART	BART
CMFT	Comprehensive Motor Function Test
CoV	Coefficient of Variation
CTTI	Clinical Trials Transformation Initiative
dBM	Digital Biomarker
DBS	Deep Brain Stimulation
DC	Direct Current (for time series normalization)
DHT	Digital Health Technologies
ECG	Electrocardiography
EDA	Electrodermal Activity
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FT	Flight Time
HAR	Human Activity Recognition
HT	Hold Time
IIR	Infinite Impulse Response
IMUs	Inertial Measurement Units
LOSO	Leave-One-Subject-Out (cross-validation)
LR	Linear Regression
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
MDS	Movement Disorder Society
MJFF-LRS	Michael J. Fox Foundation Levodopa Response Study
MIL	Multiple Instance Learning
ML	Machine Learning
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment

NFT	Normalized Flight Time
NIH	National Institutes of Health
NINDS	National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PD	Parkinson's Disease
PIM	Signal's integral
PPG	Photoplethysmography
PPMI	Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative
RBD	REM Behaviour Disorder
RBDSG	RBD Study Group
REM	Rapid Eye Movement ...
Rf	Random Forest
RLS	Restless Legs Syndrome
RMS	Root Mean Square
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
SBAS	Sleep-Related Breathing Disorders
SD	Standard Deviation
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SSRT	Stop-Signal Reaction Time
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TW	Time Warping
UPDRS	Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale

Executive summary

AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop a system of digital biomarkers for Parkinson's disease (PD) monitoring and for informing predictive models of disease risk and prognosis. Deliverable D3.1 reports on the development of the first version of digital biomarkers (dBM) for tracking PD symptoms and risk factors. The focus is placed on motor and non-motor symptoms, including rest tremor, slowness of movement (bradykinesia), dyskinesias, REM Behaviour Disorder (RBD), daytime somnolence, overall physical activity, gross motor function, and cognitive function, using data from wearables, smartphone interaction, and digital active tests. Symptom tracking approaches and findings are epitomised below.

Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD)

Objective: Early detection of RBD using actigraphy data; focus on distinguishing RBD from other conditions. *Key Features:* Activity rate, movement episodes, episode duration, skewness metrics, and sleep period boundaries were evaluated as key differentiators. *Key Results:* Machine learning models like Random Forest achieved balanced accuracy up to 89.2% with SMOTE augmentation. Statistical features demonstrated clear separation between RBD and non-RBD groups.

Daytime Somnolence

Objective: Detect and quantify daytime sleep episodes using actigraphy and clustering-based methods. *Key features:* Gaussian mixture models utilized features from sliding time windows of actigraphy data; segment-based clustering identified nap episodes. *Key Results:* 90% overlap between clustering results and Philips Actiware algorithm; detected naps were validated manually or via diaries with 99% accuracy.

Rest Tremor

Objective: Detect and classify tremor severity using wrist accelerometer data. *Key Features:* Frequency, amplitude, and tremor pattern metrics formed the basis of tremor classification. *Key Results:* High accuracy was achieved in tremor classification using a machine learning model (e.g., Random Forest) in the Michael J. Fox Foundation Levodopa Response Study (MJFF-LRS) dataset (85.5%), but the accuracy was lower (72.2%) on an external dataset (PPMI Verily Study Watch dataset).

Dyskinesias

Objective: Track dyskinesias severity using accelerometer data for real-time monitoring. *Key Features:* Features related to movement frequency and amplitude variations were explored for dyskinesia assessment. *Key Results:* Preliminary models showed promise in distinguishing dyskinesia from normal movements. Limited data collection for validation.

Human Activity Recognition and Physical Activity

Objective: Recognise human activities and evaluate mobility and physical activity levels using wearable devices for facilitating symptom assessment and providing insights into disease progression. *Key Features:* Activity counts, gait transitions, and state-switching metrics were used to quantify activity levels. *Key Results:* Models demonstrated reliability in classifying activity levels and transitions.

Slowness of Movement (Keystroke Dynamics)

Objective: Assess finger and hand bradykinesia and rigidity through typing patterns on touchscreens. *Key Features:* Statistical features of key hold time and between-keys flight time sequences during natural typing. *Key Results:* A regression model was trained on in-clinic-collected typing data to predict the finger tapping item (Item 23) of UPDRS Part III. The model was tested on a separate dataset including typing data collected in the wild and the digital score exhibited high correlation with the associated clinical score (UPDRS Item 23) ($r = 0.84$, $p < 0.05$).

Slowness of Movement (Wrist Accelerometry)

Objective: Assess slowness of gross upper limb movement through a wrist-worn accelerometer. *Key Features:* Features extracted from time-windowed 3-axis accelerometer signals during hand movement and no gait periods. *Key Results:* A pipeline including a hand movement detector, a gait detector and a slowness of movement estimator was implemented. For the slowness of movement estimator, a regressor was trained with acceleration features derived from the Verily Study Watch dataset to predict a composite clinical score of MDS-UPDRS Part III items related to bradykinesia and rigidity. The digital score exhibited a correlation of $r = 0.66$ ($p < 0.05$) with the clinical composite score and differed significantly between severity categories.

Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT)

Objective: Evaluate posture, balance, and motor coordination through active camera-based motion tracking assessments. *Key Features:* Joint angles, posture symmetry, and movement time series were captured and analysed with motion-tracking pipelines. *Key Results:* Models effectively correlated movement features with clinical scores for motor impairment (e.g., UPDRS Part III). High precision in detecting abnormalities in gait, posture, and transitions.

Cognitive Function Active Assessment

Objective: Assess cognitive decline in PD patients through digital cognitive tasks like Stop-Signal, Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART), and N-Back tests. *Key Features:* Task completion times, accuracy rates, and derived metrics such as reaction time variability and task-specific scores. *Key Results:* Machine learning models trained on extracted features demonstrated good prediction accuracy of cognitive status. Correlations between digital task scores and MoCA scores validated dBM effectiveness.

Overall challenges faced include dataset imbalances and the need for better annotation, especially for dyskinesias. dBMs implemented will be further refined and validated with data from the dBM-DEV study of the project (NCT06444789). The refined and validated dBMs will be reported in D3.2 “Final report on digital biomarkers for PD”. The report also includes an epitome of the Clinical Trials Transformation Initiative (CTTI) guidelines and their link to the trustworthy artificial intelligence (AI) development framework. The CTTI guidelines and concepts serve as the basis for developing and reporting on the dBMs in AI-PROGNOSIS.

1 Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder that affects millions of people globally and it is characterized by motor symptoms, such as tremor, bradykinesia, rigidity, and postural instability, alongside non-motor symptoms such as sleep disturbances, cognitive decline, and mood disorders (Jin et al., 2023). Traditionally, diagnosing and managing PD has relied heavily on clinical assessments and patient-reported outcomes, which are often subjective and unable to capture the full extent of symptom fluctuations that occur throughout the day (Abdo et al., 2010).

In recent years, digital biomarkers (dBMs) have emerged as a promising tool in the diagnosis and management of neurodegenerative conditions like PD. DBMs refer to quantifiable, objective physiological and behavioural data collected through digital devices, such as wearables and smartphones (Motahari-Nezhad et al., 2022). These technologies allow for the continuous and remote monitoring of patients, providing real-time insights into disease progression and treatment responses (Rovini et al., 2019). Unlike traditional methods, which may miss early signs of motor impairment or symptom fluctuations, dBMs can offer a more detailed and dynamic picture of a patient's condition. This ability to capture real-world data is crucial for tailoring treatment plans, adjusting medication dosages, and even tracking responses to clinical interventions, ultimately leading to more personalized care (Urso et al., 2023).

In AI-PROGNOSIS, an assortment of novel and existing dBMs of key PD symptoms and risk factors is being implemented that will serve both as a disease monitoring system, as well as input to the predictive models the project aims to develop for assessing PD risk and predicting progression and response of patients to medication. Based on smartwatch and user-smartphone interaction data, the focus has been placed on developing novel dBMs of rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) and of daytime somnolence and on implementing and extending existing digital assessments of rest tremor, bradykinesia, rigidity, dyskinesia, overall physical activity, posture/balance, and cognitive function.

1.1 Document scope

D3.1 is the outcome of tasks T3.1 "RBD and daytime somnolence tracking" and T3.2 "Motor and cognitive function tracking". It is important to note that D3.1 reports on the initial versions of dBMs of interest, with D3.3 to follow as the updated and final version of the dBMs system, which will also make use of the complete datasets collected in the Digital biomarkers development, validation, and verification study (dBM-DEV study) of the project.

1.2 Document structure

The present report is structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides a brief introduction including a concise background.
- Section 2 gives a brief introduction to the Clinical Trials Transformation Initiative (CTTI) recommendations for digital assessments, the concept of trustworthy artificial intelligence (AI), their interconnection, and the way they will influence the development and validation of the dBMs of interest.
- Section 3 explores methods to monitor and assess RBD, a key prodromal symptom of PD, using AI-powered dBMs for early detection and intervention.
- Section 4 focuses on tracking daytime sleepiness, also a prodromal PD sign, through dBMs to improve diagnostic accuracy of daytime sleepiness and patient management.

- Section 5 describes the implementation of dBMs to monitor rest tremor, one of the cardinal symptoms of PD.
- Section 6 investigates the use of dBMs to detect and assess dyskinesia, a common dopaminergic medication side effect, focusing on real-time tracking for improved treatment.
- Section 7 outlines the development of digital measures of overall physical activity levels, known to affect disease progression, allowing for insights into patients' mobility and overall health status.
- Section 8 presents the implementation of digital scores/indicators for assessing finger/hand bradykinesia and rigidity from keystroke dynamics captured during routine touchscreen typing. Bradykinesia and rigidity are also cardinal symptoms of PD.
- Section 9 presents the implementation of digital scores for assessing upper limb bradykinesia and rigidity from wrist accelerometry.
- Section 10 focuses on the design and preliminary performance of an active comprehensive motor function test to assess posture and balance that are gradually affected leading to adverse events, such as falls, the appearance of which constitutes a milestone in disease progression.
- Section 11 describes the development of active cognitive tests to assess cognitive function that is progressively affected by PD, with cognitive dysfunction (from mild to dementia) constituting also a disease milestone.
- Section 12 is an umbrella section, emphasizing the importance of open science principles in the development and validation of dBMs, ensuring transparency and reproducibility.
- Finally, Section 13 concludes the D3.1, summarising the key findings and outlining the next steps.

The D3.1 also includes two appendices relevant to development of the motor function assessment test (Section 10). Appendix I provides the interview guide for a co-creation session of the test persons with PD (PwPD), while Appendix II (S.1 and S.2) includes the approval and informed consent of a small-scale data collection for creating the proof-of-concept for the test.

2 CTTI recommendations and Trustworthy AI

2.1 CTTI recommendations

The Clinical Trials Transformation Initiative (CTTI) has developed comprehensive recommendations for the use of dBMs in clinical trials (CTTI, 2021). dBMs — measurable physiological, behavioural, or biological data collected through digital devices like wearables or sensors — can offer real-time insights into patient health, enabling more efficient and patient-centric research. The CTTI recommendations aim to ensure that dBMs are effectively integrated into clinical trials while maintaining scientific rigor and regulatory compliance.

One of CTTI's core recommendations is the importance of early and continuous collaboration. This involves bringing together various stakeholders, such as clinicians, patients, technology developers, and regulatory authorities. Engaging these diverse groups ensures that the dBMs being developed are not only scientifically valid but also meaningful in a clinical context. Moreover, such collaboration helps streamline the process by addressing potential concerns from regulators early on, which can prevent delays later in the trial.

Another key aspect is ensuring that the selection of dBMs is fit-for-purpose. This means that any dBM used in a clinical trial must be carefully validated to ensure it is relevant to the disease or condition under study. The tools and devices used to measure these biomarkers must also be scientifically sound, sensitive enough to detect meaningful changes, and capable of generating data that can impact clinical decision-making (Inan et al., 2020). This validation is crucial for ensuring that dBMs contribute real value to the trial, rather than simply adding unnecessary complexity.

CTTI also emphasizes the importance of considering regulatory and ethical requirements. When incorporating dBMs into trials, it is essential to comply with data privacy and security regulations. Informed consent procedures should ensure that participants understand how their data will be used, stored, and protected. Regular communication with regulatory authorities like the FDA is also crucial to ensure that the biomarkers and the technologies used to collect them meet the required legal and ethical standards.

Transparency and data integrity are fundamental to the successful use of dBMs. CTTI advocates for clear, pre-specified protocols on how dBMs data will be collected, analysed, and interpreted. This level of transparency ensures that the data are reliable and reduce the risk of bias in the analysis. Data storage and security must also be managed in such a way that the integrity of the data is maintained throughout the trial, from collection to reporting. A patient-centric approach is also crucial when developing and deploying dBMs. CTTI highlights the importance of designing devices and technologies that are easy for patients to use and that minimally disrupt their daily lives. Including patient feedback in the design phase can improve device usability and ensure that patients are more likely to adhere to trial protocols. Furthermore, patients should have a clear understanding of how these dBMs will contribute to their treatment or condition, reinforcing their engagement with the trial.

Lastly, standardisation and interoperability are essential for the broader adoption of dBMs in clinical trials. CTTI recommends establishing standardised data formats and ensuring that digital tools are interoperable with existing healthcare systems. This would allow for smoother integration of dBMs into clinical workflows and facilitate the sharing of data across different platforms, ultimately enhancing the utility and scalability of dBMs research. By following these recommendations, CTTI believes that dBMs can play a transformative role in clinical research, improving the efficiency, precision, and patient-centricity of trials while maintaining the highest standards of scientific and regulatory rigor.

2.2 Trustworthy AI Framework of AI-PROGNOSIS

The AI-PROGNOSIS Trustworthy AI Framework is grounded in the high-level expert working group's recommendations for trustworthy AI as defined in the European Commission's ALTAI (Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence) (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2020). Based on the ALTAI, the AI-PROGNOSIS framework defines a practical approach for developing AI systems that are lawful, ethical, and robust, addressing the challenges and responsibilities associated with the use of AI in high-stakes healthcare applications such as those aimed to be developed in the project. The core dimensions of trustworthiness covered include robustness, explainability, transparency, privacy, fairness, and accountability, with the framework emphasizing the need for human oversight, mitigating bias, and ensuring privacy-preserving techniques.

The framework follows a lifecycle approach, integrating these principles at various stages from design to deployment and external validation. Specifically, it employs a flexible application of ALTAI's seven trustworthiness requirements—human agency and oversight, technical

robustness, privacy and data governance, transparency, diversity and fairness, societal well-being, and accountability. The AI-PROGNOSIS project tailors these guidelines to the healthcare domain, ensuring alignment with the European Union Medical Device Regulation (MDR) and the recently voted AI Act (August 2024). The objective is to ensure that AI systems developed within this framework are both ethically aligned and legally compliant, ultimately fostering user trust and societal acceptance.

2.3 Connection of CTTI recommendations and Trustworthy AI principles

The connection between CTTI's recommendations for digital health technologies (DHTs) and the Trustworthy AI framework is profound, as both focus on ensuring that advanced technologies, including AI and dBMs, meet stringent standards of ethics, safety, transparency, and patient-centricity. Below, we elaborate on key parallels between the two frameworks.

2.3.1 Transparency and Accountability

CTTI emphasizes transparency across the entire clinical trial process, particularly when selecting and testing digital health technologies. It encourages early engagement with stakeholders—including regulators and patients—to ensure everyone understands how the technology works, the data it captures, and its potential outcomes. This aligns closely with the transparency and accountability requirements in the AI-PROGNOSIS Trustworthy AI framework, which stresses the importance of explainability and ensuring that AI systems are transparent throughout their lifecycle. This is particularly crucial in healthcare, where trust in AI decisions must be earned by making models' decision-making processes clear and traceable, not only to developers but also to clinicians, patients, and regulatory bodies. The accountability aspect in both frameworks ensures that any party responsible for a system—whether a digital health device or an AI model—can be held accountable for its outputs and their impacts on patient safety and outcomes. Both emphasize the need for auditability, where actions taken by AI or digital tools can be traced and reviewed by third parties, ensuring compliance with ethical standards and regulatory requirements.

2.3.2 Data Integrity and Security

Both frameworks stress the critical nature of data integrity. CTTI's recommendations outline the need for stringent data management practices, ensuring that the data collected through digital health technologies are accurate, reliable, and free from errors that could compromise clinical trial outcomes. This is mirrored in the technical robustness and privacy and data governance components of the AI-PROGNOSIS Trustworthy AI framework. These principles ensure that AI models handling sensitive healthcare data are secure, that privacy is maintained through the proper anonymization and protection protocols, and that the systems can withstand adversarial or unexpected inputs while maintaining performance.

2.3.3 Fairness and Inclusivity

A key focus of CTTI's recommendations is the inclusion of diverse patient populations to ensure that digital health technologies are not only effective but also equitable. For instance, CTTI advocates for selecting technologies that cater to a broad range of patient demographics and clinical needs. This commitment to inclusivity aligns with the fairness principle within the AI-PROGNOSIS framework, which seeks to eliminate bias from AI models by ensuring that training data are representative of diverse populations. Fairness also extends to ensuring that AI models provide equitable outcomes for all users, regardless of socioeconomic background, gender, age, or ethnicity.

2.3.4 Human-Centric Design

CTTI emphasizes the need for patient-centric digital technologies that are easy to use, reliable, and capable of collecting meaningful data that reflect the patient's real-world experience. This patient-centric approach is complemented by the human agency and oversight principle in the Trustworthy AI framework, which calls for AI systems to support human decision-making and to allow for human intervention in critical situations. Ensuring that digital tools and AI models remain understandable and actionable for both healthcare providers and patients is essential for fostering trust. However, there are also some key differences between the two concepts. Human-centric design of dBMs represents a broader quality focused on user-centered development, whereas human agency and oversight in AI specifically pertains to the role of AI in influencing human decisions and the extent to which humans can control or intervene in AI-driven processes.

2.3.5 Explainability

Finally, explainability is a key component in both CTTI's recommendations and the Trustworthy AI framework. CTTI underscores the importance of ensuring that data from digital health technologies are presented in a way that is understandable to various stakeholders, including patients, clinicians, and regulators. Similarly, AI systems under the Trustworthy AI framework must provide explanations of their outputs, ensuring that all stakeholders can understand the reasoning behind AI-driven decisions. This is particularly important in healthcare settings, where clinical decisions based on AI must be explainable to patients for ethical and practical reasons.

2.4 Summary and key concepts

In summary, CTTI's recommendations and the AI-PROGNOSIS Trustworthy AI framework both prioritize transparency, data integrity, patient-centricity, and fairness to ensure that digital health technologies and AI systems meet the highest standards of trustworthiness in clinical and healthcare settings. Both frameworks strive to ensure that new technologies are safe, reliable, and inclusive, ultimately enhancing patient outcomes while minimizing risks.

In the end of each of the sections detailing the dBMs developed, we introduce a table summarising each of the components according to the CTTI guidelines (Digital assessment ID). We include information about the "*Meaningful health aspect*" (part of life/health affected) related to each component, the "*Concept(s) of interest*" (the symptom impacting life/health), the "*Measurement technology*" (sensor and/or device), the "*Proposed digital biomarker(s)*" (the digital features/scores derived from raw sensed data), the "*Validation*" followed (measures, comparison against clinical standards, and type of validation), any "*Assumptions*" made (mainly regarding the technology and/or its acceptance), and "*Context of use considerations*" (user characteristics, technology configuration, and setting).

3 Rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder tracking

3.1 Background and objectives

The tracking and diagnosis of Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD) have significant implications for both diagnostic and prognostic purposes, particularly within the context of neurodegenerative diseases like PD (Fernandez, 2008). RBD is a prodromal

symptom of PD, often appearing years before motor symptoms (10-15 years in average before). Therefore, early detection of RBD through dBMs, such as those derived from actigraphy, provides a non-invasive, cost-effective method for identifying at-risk populations. Traditional methods, like polysomnography, while reliable, are expensive, impractical, and time-consuming. Recent studies focus on the potential of wearable devices to detect early signs of RBD, providing a more accessible option for patients (Rachellà,2023) (for more information check D2.3).

The target population for RBD prediction models includes individuals exhibiting early symptoms of RBD, such as disordered sleep or excessive movements during sleep, with a particular focus on PD patients. These tools are designed for use by healthcare professionals, such as neurologists, as well as by patients and caregivers monitoring disease progression from home. Notably, health disparities exist across sociodemographic groups, particularly in access to sleep disorder diagnostics. Studies suggest that certain populations, such as lower-income or rural groups, face increased barriers to early diagnosis due to the cost and availability of specialized equipment.

In AI-PROGNOSIS, we will attempt to develop and validate dBMs of RBD from wrist wearable motion data by leveraging existing datasets and data that will be collected in the dBM-DEV study (NCT06444789) of the project (see also D5.1 “Study initiation package (dBM-DEV study)”). The primary objective will be to arrive at dBMs that will increase the specificity of RBD detection compared to the RBD screening questionnaire (RBDSQ) (Stiasny-Kolster et al., 2007), a standardised patient self-rating questionnaire that is currently the most accessible instrument for RBD detection.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Datasets

So far, two existing datasets have been explored for the discovery of potential digital biomarkers of RBD, i.e., RBD-Czech and iRBDSG.

Table 1 RBD datasets

RBD	Population	Data form and comments
RBDCzech	91 subjects (45 RBD patients)	csv
IRBDsg	89 subjects (20 RBD)	Data form compatible only with software of company AMI. Transformation to .txt performed

RBD-Czech dataset

The first dataset explored, RBD-Czech (Kristian, 2019), contains raw actigraphy signals in .csv format from 91 participants (45 RBD patients). Each participant has data available for one night. Of the available signals, 90 were usable, as one was invalid (zero value for whole overnight recording). The actigraphy signals were sampled at a frequency of 1 Hz. The recordings were made during the night without annotation of the exact sleep period. The duration of the recordings varied for each participant. Each point in the time series is labeled either as part of a kicking episode or an awakening episode.

The participants belong to one of three groups, i.e., RBD, sleep apnoea, or controls. In total, there are 20 healthy participants, 28 with apnoea, and 42 with RBD. We need to note that since the data were captured within the context of a sleeping lab, we are not certain if the healthy label are people with some other disorder other than RBD or apnoea or with no

sleeping disorder. All patients participated in the study at the Center for Sleep Disorders at the University Hospital in Prague. The diagnosis of RBD was made using polysomnography and the maximum interval between data collection and diagnosis was three years. Figure 1 shows representative acceleration-time raw signals for three participants.

Figure 1 Actigraphy data from specific subjects (healthy, apneic, with RBD) of RBD-Czech

iRBDSG dataset

The second dataset, iRBDSG, consists of 89 participants (20 RBD patients) and was acquired via an ongoing collaboration with the RBD Study Group (RBDSG)¹. Currently, no work has been published involving this dataset. The data were collected using the AMI Motionlogger sensor (Ambulatory Monitoring Inc., Ardsley, NY) (Motionlogger, 2024). This device detects wrist movements through a piezoelectric accelerometer. Movement causes the piezoelectric beam to twist, which generates a voltage signal. The sampling rate is 10 Hz. This voltage is amplified, passed through an analog-to-digital converter, and filtered with a band-pass filter. The resulting signal is compared to a reference signal to determine if it exceeds a movement threshold.

The signal that is ultimately available is not the raw signal obtained from the process described above, but rather a pre-processed signal in each 30-second epoch. For each 30-second

¹ <https://www.irbdsg.com/>

period, the number of zero crossings (when the signal passes the threshold) and the signal's integral (PIM) are available, as shown in **Figure 2**. Additionally, for each period, information about the lighting conditions and temperature is included.

Figure 2 Visualization of an unprocessed data sample of iRBDSG explaining processed values.

The measurements were taken throughout the day, and there is no annotation of the sleep periods. Furthermore, multiple nights are available for each participant, but the RBD label (yes or not) is assigned per participant, not per night. In this dataset, the labels overlap, and there is a total of 20 participants with RBD, 19 without any syndrome, 36 with Restless Legs Syndrome (RLS), and 44 with Sleep-Related Breathing Disorders (SBAS). The diagnoses were made through two sessions of polysomnography. **Figure 3** shows two representative signals from the second dataset. The signal during the night hours for a randomly selected day has been isolated. The top images display the number of zero crossings for each 30-second period, while the bottom images show the signal's integral.

Figure 3 Representative data samples from two participants of iRBDSG. ZCM: zero-crossing, PIM: Signal's integral (as seen in Figure 2). Data pre-processing

Sleep period detection

In both datasets, there was no labelling of the sleep period. In the RBD-Czech dataset, where the data are raw, it was observed that movement was more intense at the beginning and end of the recording, which only concerned night-time hours. This leads to the hypothesis that this movement might not be part of sleep. Therefore, two algorithms were created for detecting the sleep period, and the discriminative ability of the features was re-evaluated.

The first algorithm detects the first and last periods without movement for more than two minutes. Then, it removes the time points before the first and after the last such period. The second algorithm detects the first and last 11 movement episodes. This number was chosen to cover the part of the signal where significantly greater movement is observed in most participants. The verification was done by visualizing the signal and the threshold of 11 episodes. If any of these episodes have a significant distance from a neighbouring one or if its amplitude is greater than one-quarter of the maximum amplitude observed in the signal, then this episode and the part of the signal before or after it (depending on whether the episode is among the first or last 11) is discarded.

Finally, the detection of the sleep period was also done manually for each participant. In the diagrams below, the boundaries of the sleep period are shown for some signals from participants using the two methods, **Figure 4** and **Figure 5**, respectively.

Figure 4 Limits of the sleep period based on first algorithm. The blue signal represents the raw actigraphy data, i.e., acceleration vs. time, and the red vertical lines depict the start and end boundaries of sleep as detected by each algorithm.

Figure 5 Limits of the sleep period based on the second algorithm. The blue signal represents the raw actigraphy data, i.e., acceleration vs. time, and the red vertical lines depict the start and end boundaries of sleep as detected by each algorithm.

Class imbalance

Both datasets are imbalanced in terms of RBD cases. The RBD-Czech dataset consists of 90 participants, of which 42 have RBD, while the iRBDSG dataset contains 89 participants, 20 of whom have RBD. Machine learning techniques tend to focus on minimizing error for the majority class when the data is imbalanced, often ignoring the minority class. Therefore, the final step in data pre-processing involved using data augmentation to augment the RBD class and balance the datasets. Two methods were applied, Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) (Chawla, 2002) and random sampling of RBD nights.

SMOTE focuses on generating synthetic samples for the minority class. For each sample in this class, one or more of its k -nearest neighbours is selected. A new synthetic sample is created by interpolating between the selected sample and its neighbours. In this study, SMOTE was applied in the feature space, meaning that new feature values were generated, but no new signals were created.

Random sampling of RBD nights was applied only to the iRBDSG dataset, where multiple nights were available for each participant. First, the nights of participants with RBD were isolated. Then, to create a new synthetic participant, certain of those nights were randomly selected and the mean value for each feature across those nights was calculated. The number of nights for each new participant was drawn as a random sample from a normal distribution, with the mean and standard deviation equal to those of the original dataset's distribution of nights per participant.

The SMOTE technique was applied to both datasets, separately and after their combination. In the case of iRBDSG, the random sampling of RBD nights method was also tested.

Artifact removal

Physiological signals, especially those captured by wearables, often contain erroneous values (artifacts). Hence, we explored whether it is possible to detect errors in the signals from the RBD-Czech dataset, which contains raw data, and how their removal impacts classification performance. The detection method is based on the work of Supramanian (2022) and uses unsupervised learning techniques to detect artifacts in electrodermal activity signals. This method was chosen due to insufficient artifact annotations, making unsupervised methods more suitable. Furthermore, most of the features used are extracted in the time domain rather than the frequency domain, as the sampling rate does not favour frequency analysis. We implemented the following algorithm:

1. The first step is to divide the signal into non-overlapping windows of 10 s each. Then, the following features are extracted for each window:
 - a. Standard deviation of the signal
 - b. Difference between the maximum and minimum value
 - c. Mean of the first derivative
 - d. Median of the first derivative
 - e. Standard deviation of the first derivative
 - f. Minimum value of the first derivative
 - g. Maximum value of the first derivative
 - h. Mean of the Haar wavelet coefficients at the 4th level
 - i. Median of the Haar wavelet coefficients at the 4th level
 - j. Standard deviation of the Haar wavelet coefficients at the 4th level
 - k. Maximum Haar wavelet coefficient at the 4th level

- I. Minimum Haar wavelet coefficient at the 4th level
2. Apply various unsupervised learning methods to assign a score to each window, ranging from 0 to 1. The unsupervised methods tested were:
 - *k*-nearest neighbours
 - Random Forest classification
 - Support Vector Machine

The higher the score, the more likely the window contains erroneous measurements.
3. Find the optimal threshold for classifying the windows as containing errors, for each method. First, potential optimal thresholds are calculated. As the threshold increases, the number of windows exceeding the threshold decreases. Furthermore, the signal corresponding to errors is expected to differ significantly from the "normal" values, so there should be a large difference between the number of windows exceeding a "good" threshold and those exceeding neighbouring thresholds. A larger difference, along with fewer windows exceeding the threshold, means greater spacing between the erroneous windows at a good threshold. Since errors occur randomly, their spacing should also be irregular. To quantify this, the skewness of the distribution of distances between erroneous windows is calculated for each threshold value. The thresholds with local maxima in skewness are selected as candidates. A greater skewness implies a more irregular distribution of erroneous windows, which aligns with the expectation that errors occur randomly within the signal. This method resembles the L-curve method (Castellanos, 2002), but here, we are looking for the maxima of the graph. Essentially, a point with a sharp rise represents a threshold that differs from the previous one in that the skewness of the distribution of erroneous windows is higher.

Once the optimal threshold is selected for each method, the final step is to choose the best method. The method that results in the lowest percentage of windows classified as errors is considered the best. The results of the different preprocessing methods are shown in Section 3.3.

3.2.2 Digital biomarkers

In both datasets we explored various possible biomarkers from the relevant literature (**Table 2**), with the main focus placed on the study of Rachellà et al. (2023).

Table 2 Potential RBD Biomarkers

	Potential biomarker	Explanation
1	Activity Rate	The ratio of the time points corresponding to movement
2	Global Activity	Percentage of activity windows, calculated from sliding windows of 30 seconds
3	Number of Movement Episodes	Number of defined movement episodes
4	Mean Duration of Movement Episodes	Mean duration of the movement episodes
5	Mean Distance Between Episodes	Mean distance between movement episodes
6	Mean Amplitude	Mean amplitude of time points that contain movement
7	Episodes Per Minute	Number of movement episodes per minute
8	Skewness of Amplitude	Skewness of the amplitude distribution
9	General Mean	Overall mean of the amplitude distribution

10	95 th Percentile	95th percentile of the amplitude distribution
11	Number of Kicks	Number of kick episodes in the signal
12	Number of Bouts	Number of awakening episodes in the signal
13	Kicks Per Minute	Number of kick episodes per minute
14	Bouts Per Minute	Number of awakening episodes per
15	Activity Mean	Mean of the distribution of movement time points
16	Activity Median	Median of the distribution of movement time points
17	Activity SD	Standard deviation of the distribution of movement time points
18	Activity Skew	Skewness of the distribution of movement time points
19	Activity Kurtosis	Kurtosis of the distribution of movement time points
20	Duration Mean	Mean of the distribution of episode durations
21	Duration Median	Median of the distribution of episode durations
22	Duration SD	Standard deviation of the distribution of episode durations
23	Duration Skew	Skewness of the distribution of episode durations
24	Duration Kurtosis	Kurtosis of the distribution of episode durations
25	Percentage Of Close Distances	Percentage of episodes with a distance from neighbours less than 10 seconds
26	Percentage of Medium Distances	Percentage of episodes with a distance from neighbours greater than 10 seconds and less than 60
27	Percentage of Far Distances	Percentage of episodes with a distance from neighbours greater than 60 seconds
28	Percentage of Short durations	Percentage of episodes lasting less than 2 seconds
29	Percentage of Medium durations	Percentage of episodes lasting more than 2 seconds and less than 10 seconds
30	Percentage of Long durations	Percentage of episodes lasting more than 10 seconds
31	Movement High Magnitude Percentage	Percentage of episodes with high mean amplitude (> 3 times threshold)
32	Movement High Magnitude Low Duration Percentage	Percentage of episodes with high amplitude and low duration
33	Movement High Magnitude Low Distance Percentage	Percentage of episodes with high amplitude and short distance from neighbouring episodes

For the above definition of the dBMs, the following should be noted:

- A timestamp is classified as a movement when the acceleration magnitude exceeds the mean acceleration magnitude by at least one standard deviation, provided the standard deviation is greater than 0.1.
- Movement episode: consecutive timestamps where acceleration magnitude is above a threshold.
- Kick/bout episode: consecutive timestamps labeled as kick / bout - kick/bout labels are provided by the RBD-Czech dataset, hence those dBMs were only explored in the first dataset.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Descriptive statistics of potential digital biomarkers

Initially we explored our data and tried to understand the different statistical properties of the potential dBMs among RBD patients and persons without RBD, in both datasets. In the boxplots of **Figure 6-Figure 9**, the distributions of the features with the highest discriminative power for the different classes and both datasets are shown. Each boxplot depicts the group

median, the first (Q1) and the third (Q3) quartile, with the whiskers showing the Q1-1.5 interquartile range (IQR) and Q3+1.5 IQR and circles depicting outlier values. Specifically, these are the features for which the distributions between healthy individuals and those suffering from RBD showed the greatest differentiation. This means that either they covered distinct value ranges or the values in the second and third quartiles, i.e., around the median of the boxplot, exhibited less overlap in their value ranges.

Figure 6 Boxplots of activity rate for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.

Figure 7 Boxplots of the number of movement episodes for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.

Figure 8 Boxplots of the mean duration of movement episodes for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.

Figure 9 Boxplots of mean distance between movement episodes for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.

Figure 10 Boxplots of episodes per minute for the RBD and non-RBD groups in the RBD-Czech and iRBDSG datasets.

The relationship between most features across the two classes suggests the presence of idiopathic conditions. Specifically, participants with RBD exhibit a higher activity rate compared to healthy individuals or those with sleep apnoea. These participants also experience more movement episodes at night, which tend to last longer and occur more frequently in close succession. Moreover, the distributions of the skewness of activity times (activity skewness) and episode durations (duration skewness) are more positively skewed for the RBD participants. Positive skewness means that the distribution is asymmetric, with most values falling below the mean.

3.3.2 Machine learning-based classification of RBD

We have investigated the ability of machine learning (ML) models to detect RBD, with the available potential dBMs as input features. Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RFs) and Logistic Regression (LR) models were explored to classify the participants into RBD and non-RBD groups based on actigraphy data, taking into account both the Czech-RBD and iRBD SG datasets. The datasets were initially processed independently and then combined for further evaluation.

Model training and testing

Hyperparameters are model characteristics independent of the data that must be set at training and directly influence performance. Grid-search was employed in order to estimate the hyperparameters of the models. The dimensionality of the grid equals the number of parameters to tune. The values for each parameter are predefined, and then every possible combination is tested. The grid is theoretically formed if every possible combination is considered a node. Although this method always converges to the best result from the examined options, it has the drawback of requiring significant computational power, which increases proportionally with the number of cases being evaluated.

The parameters to be tuned for each model were selected based on their ability to cause significant changes in performance when altered. A wide range of values was tested for all parameters. For each point on the grid, k-fold validation is performed. The dataset is split into five (5) folds, and the model was trained and evaluated 5 times, each time leaving out a different fold for validation. This process produced a balanced accuracy score for each grid node. The chosen performance metric was balanced accuracy to compensate for the class imbalance in the datasets. This was done for every model type (SVM, RF and LR) and for both datasets. High-discriminatory features common to both datasets were used, such as the number of episodes per minute, the average distance between episodes, activity percentage, 95th percentile, activity skewness, kurtosis of episode duration, and the average signal value (see **Table 2**). In the end, the best-performing parameters were selected for each model and for both datasets to be used in all subsequent experiments. The values and parameters tested are shown in **Table 3**.

Table 3 Values test for the hyperparameters of each method using grid-search

Method	Parameter	Value
SVM	C	0.1, 1, 5, 10, 20, 30
	Kernel	Linear, rbf, sigmoid
	Gamma	Scale, auto
LR	Penalty	none, l_2
	C	1, 10, 100
RF	Number of trees	10, 50, 100, 200, 300
	Max depth	None*, 10, 20, 30, 40

	Min number of separations	2, 5, 10, 15, 20
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* If None, then nodes are expanded until all leaves are pure or until all leaves contain less than `min_samples_split` samples.

The final parameters selected were [`'C'`: 20, `'gamma'`: 'auto', `'kernel'`: 'linear'] for the SVM, [`'max_depth'`: None, `'min_samples_split'`: 2, `'n_estimators'`: 50] for the RF, and [`'C'`: 100, `'penalty'`: 'l2'] for LR. These parameters were chosen because they ranked among the best for each dataset. While they may not be the absolute best across both datasets simultaneously, they represent a strong balance for each dataset individually. In other words, the optimal parameters for each model did not coincide perfectly across both datasets, but the chosen ones were among the top-performing for each. In **Table 4**, the average balanced accuracy for each model is shown in the RBD-Czech dataset.

Table 4 Results of different models with different number of features for RBD-Czech dataset

Method	8 Best features	16 best features	All features
SVM	73.0 ± 8.0%	69.0 ± 9.0%	70.0 ± 8.0%
RF	72.0 ± 9.0%	74.0 ± 8.0%	73.0 ± 8.0%
LR	72.0 ± 9.0%	69.0 ± 8.0%	70.0 ± 9.0%

The features were selected based on a statistical test that assessed discriminatory power between the two groups. Specifically, the 8 best features with the greatest discriminatory ability were:

- average distance between episodes,
- episodes per minute,
- activity rate,
- 95th percentile,
- mean value,
- activity skewness,
- duration kurtosis, and
- average episode duration.

Initially, we observe that the models do not differ significantly from one another. Moreover, the standard deviation in all cases is relatively high. This suggests that there is considerable variability in the results between different folds. There are two possible reasons for this, either the models are too generalized and cannot effectively distinguish between cases that lie near the boundary of the two classes, or the data itself varies significantly, meaning that training with certain subsets yields substantially better results than others.

In that case, since the high deviation occurs across all models and an analysis has already been conducted to identify the best parameters, we conclude that the variation is due to the nature of the data. Given that not all RBD participants exhibit episodes every night, it is likely that this variation is related to whether the training set happens to include participants who did not exhibit the disorder. We must note again that we have the label for each patient as RBD patient, but is not necessary that the patient had RBD in the single night we have data, he/she might have experienced an RBD episode in a different night.

Using SMOTE to augment the under-represented class of RBD cases leads to an improvement of the balanced accuracy (**Table 5**), mainly for RF, but the change is not considerable since the dataset is quite balanced.

Table 5 Results of different models with SMOTE for RBD-Czech dataset

Method	8 best features
SVM	74.2 ± 8.0%
RF	76.4 ± 9.0%
LR	72.3 ± 7.0%

In the iRBDSG dataset, there are multiple nights per patient. Similar to RBD-Czech, we do not know for which nights an RBD patient experienced episodes. For the features of activity rate and the number of episodes per night, the distribution of the both the RBD and non-RBD subjects show two peaks, one at zero and another at a higher value (red plot of **Figure 11**). This behaviour has been also noted for nights of the same subject. In other words, many participants exhibit very low activity on some nights and high in others. This indicates that the disorder does not manifest on every night for RBD participants, as if it did, the activity rate would always have value above zero. **Figure 11** better illustrates the distribution of activity percentage for RBD and non-RBD nights.

Figure 11 Distribution of activity rate per group, RBD (blue) and non-RBD (pink).

This sporadic nature of RBD combined with the distributions shown in **Figure 11**, where there is no apparent difference between the two groups, suggests that ground truth (occurrence of RBD episode(s)) per night would be useful for analysis. Hence, we tried two approaches: 1) to try to identify whether each night belongs to an RBD patient or not by having different nights as training and test set, and 2) to try to identify whether a subject has RBD or not, by combining decisions across their nights. The results based on five-fold cross-validation (avoiding subjects being part of training and testing datasets) can be viewed in **Table 6**.

Table 6 Results of different models with and without augmentation for iRBDSG dataset with the 8-best features

Method	Night classification		Subject classification	
	Without SMOTE	With SMOTE	Without SMOTE	With SMOTE
SVM	55.4±11.0%	70.6±6.0%	65.0±11.0%	83.5±6.0%
RF	56.2±10.0%	78.4±6.0%	63.0±13.0%	89.2±5.0%
LR	52.6±7.0%	68.3±8.0%	71.0±10.0%	80.1±7.0%

As expected, it can be observed that performance is very low (almost random) without using augmentation, since the classes are unbalanced. Furthermore, it seems more effective to identify RBD patients rather than a night with RBD episode(s), due to the lack of ground truth per night. It must be noted that in the training phase for night classification, we assumed that every night that belongs to an RBD patient is a night with RBD episode(s) and therefore, we might have provided inaccurate labels to the model, since the disorder is not exhibited every night. The noisy night labels may be the reason why the performance is low. On the contrary, when we consider subject classification along with augmentation, the classification performance improves considerably, with balanced accuracy reaching 89.2%.

Sleep period detection

The use of sleep period detection (trimming of start and end period of the signal) had a minimal effect on the performance of the classification of subjects. Hence, no results are presented.

Artifact removal

After performing artifact removal (as described in Section 0), we obtained slightly better performance (**Table 7**), compared to the results of **Table 5**. The improvement could have been more, if we had artifact annotations. Hence, artifact removal will be part of our final pipeline for RBD detection.

Table 7 Results of different models with SMOTE for RBD-Czech dataset with artifact removal.

Method	8 best features
SVM	75.6±8.0%
RF	76.6 ±9.0%
LR	74.8±9.0%

3.4 Discussion

3.4.1 Interpretation

The analysis conducted shows a clear difference in actigraphy metrics between RBD patients and non-RBD subjects, particularly regarding activity rate, movement episode count, and episode duration. These findings are consistent with the known characteristics of RBD, such as increased motor activity during REM sleep. The positive skewness in the distributions of activity and episode duration suggests that a small number of nights feature extreme movement activity, which might reflect the episodic nature of RBD. Importantly, the ML-based classification models performed reasonably well, with RF classifiers showing a slight edge over SVM and LR ones.

The balanced accuracy scores demonstrate that with appropriate feature selection and data preprocessing, actigraphy data can be used to differentiate between RBD and non-RBD subjects with significant accuracy, especially when augmentation techniques are applied. These results, however, should be considered with caution due to the inherent variability in night-to-night activity within RBD patients, which is a key characteristic of the disorder.

3.4.2 Limitations

Several limitations must be acknowledged. One of the main issues is the quality and availability of input data, particularly the lack of ground truth for each night. In both datasets, the labels concern the subject's diagnosis with regard to RBD rather than each night, which could confuse the model, since the disorder does not manifest every night. This was evident in the iRBD SG dataset, where the assumption (due to lack of labels) that we had the presence of RBD episodes during all nights of RBD patients misled the models. This issue may be even

more pronounced in the RBD-Czech dataset, where only one night per patient is available, yet the labels are based on the overall diagnosis.

Moreover, the datasets had small sample sizes, with 90 and 89 participants, respectively, and included individuals with secondary sleep disorders, such as sleep apnoea. The relatively low sampling rate and the absence of detailed night-level labels also hinder the model's ability to generalize across different scenarios. Another limitation is the performance variability across different models and the minimal effect of sleep detection on classification accuracy, indicating that more research is needed to understand its impact fully.

3.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

Despite these limitations, the dBMs identified above have potential applicability in clinical practice. These biomarkers could assist in the screening and monitoring of RBD in populations where polysomnography is not feasible due to cost or accessibility. For example, the ability to classify RBD patients with a relatively high degree of accuracy based on actigraphy could be used in home-monitoring systems.

A concrete limitation of the current dataset was the lack of ground truth and labels. In the DBM-Dev study of AI-PROGNOSIS we will collect a single night with PSG. Furthermore, on the nights that the data will not be collected within sleep labs, we will request caregivers and patients to note the RBD nights the following day and (if possible) also an approximation of the time of RBD events. The extra clinical observations that will be collected during dBM DEV study will be helpful towards diagnosis and clinical care and improving the current dBMs.

3.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Early detection and monitoring of REM sleep behaviour disorder, a significant prodromal marker of Parkinson's Disease.
Concept(s) of interest	Abnormal motor activity during REM sleep, such as kicking, punching, or other movement episodes.
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn accelerometer (actigraphy).
Type of measurement	Passive measurement during overnight sleep periods.
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	Activity rate, number and duration of movement episodes, mean distance between episodes, and skewness of activity.
Validation	Machine learning models (e.g., Random Forest, SVM) validated on datasets like RBD-Czech and iRBD SG with augmentation techniques
Assumptions	Cross-validation using datasets like RBD-Czech and iRBD SG with machine learning classifiers.
Context of use considerations	Screening for individuals with suspected RBD and long-term home monitoring for progression tracking.

4 Daytime somnolence tracking

4.1 Background and objectives

Daytime somnolence, or excessive daytime sleepiness, is a condition characterised by an overwhelming need to sleep during the day. It is often associated with various sleep disorders, neurodegenerative diseases, and general sleep deprivation. Monitoring daytime somnolence

is critical for understanding sleep patterns and evaluating the effectiveness of interventions to improve sleep quality, particularly in populations such as PwPD or other neurodegenerative conditions. Moreover, daytime somnolence is considered a prodromal sign of PD.

AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop dBMs that detect and quantify daytime somnolence using data from a wrist wearable, by leveraging existing datasets and data that will be collected in the dBM-DEV study of the project. At this phase, the main objective is to explore the feasibility of using actigraphy data to identify daytime sleep and nap episodes. By employing advanced clustering methods and comparing results with established algorithms like those of Philips Actiware (Koninklijke Philips N.V., Amsterdam, the Netherlands), the project seeks to provide a robust solution for daily somnolence tracking. Additionally, validating these findings against participant-reported sleep diaries allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between detected sleep events and subjective reports. For more information on the current state-of-the-art and previous research in the detection of daytime somnolence, the reader is referred to D2.3, “Initial report on domain review and datasets”, Section 2.2.5.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Datasets

The dataset was collected at KU Leuven University Hospital (UZ Leuven) in a study on understanding sleep in PD. It contains actigraphy data from 88 subjects recorded with a wrist wearable device (Philips Respironics Actiwatch-II) over seven days. For the present analysis, data from 24 subjects were excluded due to poor data quality (high frequency noise) or missing data. The subjects were instructed to report time and duration of night sleep as well as daily naps, if any, using a diary. They also indicated going to sleep and waking up events by depressing a marker button on the device. Actiwatch data were recorded with a 32 Hz sampling frequency and the sampling epochs were chosen to have 30 s duration. The dataset also contains white light measurements which were not used here. Philips Actiware-detected sleep and wake epochs were available. Philips-Actiware algorithm calculates the total activity of each epoch as a weighted sum of the activity in question and its immediate surroundings, as shown in Figure 12. The result is then compared to the wake threshold such that if the sum exceeds the threshold, the epoch is scored as wake. The threshold can take one of the software’s predefined values or be set manually.

Figure 12 The Philips Actiware weights for the calculation of total activity for 30 s sampling epochs (x represents the multiplication of each segment with a weight). The current epoch is the one in the middle which is multiplied by 2. The x-axis is the different segments before and after the current one.

4.2.2 Digital biomarkers

Given the available dataset, a clustering method was implemented for daytime somnolence detection, leveraging features directly derived from raw actigraphy signals. For this purpose, Gaussian mixture clustering models are employed to characterize each epoch as sleep or awake in a subject-specific fashion. The feature vectors chosen as inputs for the models are sliding windows of the raw signals aligned such that each feature vector essentially represents

an epoch's neighbourhood in the time domain (**Figure 13**). For the edge epochs, zero padding is implemented. Segments of consecutive epochs labelled as sleep are considered a nap. Nearby nap segments are concatenated forming a single nap. Only daytime segments (07.00-21.00) are considered, excluding the night sleep periods. The pipeline of the method is outlined below:

- The raw accelerometer signals are segmented into 5 min sliding windows (10 epochs of 30 seconds).
- A Gaussian mixture model with two (2) clusters is fitted for each participant.
- The 'sleep' segments with at least 5 min duration are considered nap segments. Nap segments being less than 10 min apart are considered a single awake. The above parameters are tuned via trial and error using data from a small subset of the participants.

Figure 13 Pipeline of the clustering method for detecting naps.

Due to the lack of ground truth, we could only compare the results with obtained labels from the Actiware algorithm, which is implemented within the actigraphy device that was used to capture the data.

The Actiware algorithm is epitomised below:

1. **Total Activity Calculation:** The algorithm calculates total activity for each window of time (typically 1-minute or 30-second epochs) by computing the weighted sum of activity data points collected by the wearable device. This total activity serves as the primary metric to distinguish between sleep and wake states.

The algorithm uses different weight factors for each data point within a window to emphasize the impact of recent activity and de-emphasize older movements. The weights can vary based on the configuration, but default settings are (as can be seen in **Figure 12** The Philips Actiware weights for the calculation of total activity for 30 s sampling epochs (x represents the multiplication of each segment with a weight). The current epoch is the one in the middle which is multiplied by 2. The x-axis is the different segments before and after the current one.

- **x1/25** for less important, distant data points,
- **x1/5** for more important, recent data points,
- **x2** for the current or most recent activity point, reflecting that more weight is given to activity close to the moment of measurement (x is a multiplication)

Additionally, the user can manually set the threshold if customisation is needed for specific research or clinical conditions.

2. Thresholding for Sleep and Wake Detection:

- **Sleep Detection:** If the total activity falls *below a threshold* (referred to as the 'wake threshold'), the algorithm classifies the subject as being in a sleep state.
- **Wake Detection:** If the total activity *exceeds the wake threshold*, the subject is classified as awake.

3. Wake Threshold Values:

The wake threshold can be set at different levels depending on the desired sensitivity of the algorithm:

- **Low:** Threshold value of 20
- **Medium:** Threshold value of 40
- **High:** Threshold value of 80
- **Automatic:** The threshold can be also automatically computed based on the collected activity data, allowing for dynamic adjustments to individual patterns.

4.3 Results

The proposed Gaussian mixture clustering method is compared to the Actiware algorithm. In **Figure 14**, sleep epochs detected during the day by both the clustering and the Actiware methods are presented for two subjects, along with the percentage that both approaches match. The two methods show very similar results, as the detected sleep/wake periods exhibit over 90% overlap. Overall, results showed that the Actiware algorithm seems to be more sensitive when it comes to detecting sleep segments during the day. In particular, the clustering method-detected sleep epochs are a subset of the respective epochs detected by Actiware, for all subjects.

Next, the results of the proposed clustering-based method are compared with the naps reported by the participants in the sleep diary and evaluated visually by KUL engineers. The percentage of the detected nap segments that can be validated either visually or via the sleep diary logs across all participants is shown in **Table 8**. Naps are significantly underreported in the diaries (3 naps reported per participant on average), compared to the results of both the clustering method (9 naps detected per participant on average) and visual inspection. Almost all naps (99%) detected by our method can be validated manually and conversely, there are few naps detectable via visual inspection that were missed by the clustering method (on average 0.8 naps per participant).

Figure 14 Examples of sleep segments in two distinct subjects detected during the day for each method.

Table 8 Overall percentage of the clustering-based detected naps that can be validated from a) the participants' diaries and/or b) visual inspection.

Diaries	Manual inspection	Percentage of detected naps (% of total detections)
Yes	Yes	18.52
Yes	No	0.33
No	Yes	80.47
No	No	0.68

4.4 Discussion

4.4.1 Interpretation

The results show a high degree of similarity between the sleep/wake patterns detected by the proposed clustering method and the Philips Actiware algorithm, with over 90% overlap. This alignment underscores the efficacy of the proposed clustering method in identifying sleep episodes during the day. The clustering method's ability to detect sleep segments that were not reported by participants in their diaries also highlights the advantage of continuous, objective monitoring through actigraphy over subjective self-reporting.

The Gaussian mixture model applied here proved to be effective in discriminating between sleep and wake periods based on raw actigraphy data, despite the absence of ground truth labels. These findings suggest that even unsupervised approaches can yield useful insights into sleep behaviour when trained on sufficiently granular datasets. The consistency in nap detection, particularly the ability to capture unreported naps, emphasises the model's potential with regard to more accurate and reliable tracking of daytime sleepiness.

4.4.2 Limitations

Despite the promising results, there are several limitations to consider. The primary challenge lies in the quality of input data. Out of 88 participants, data from 24 participants were excluded due to poor data quality or missing data, which represents a significant portion of the original dataset. This raises the question of how to handle incomplete or noisy data in future applications of the model. Furthermore, the absence of ground truth labels poses a challenge

for validating the accuracy of the predictions. The reliance on Actiware's output and manual inspection for validation limits the extent to which we can fully assess the accuracy of the clustering algorithm.

4.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

The usability of dBMs derived from actigraphy data in the context of current clinical care is promising. With wearables becoming more widespread, continuous monitoring of sleep patterns, including daytime somnolence, could be integrated into routine clinical practice. The non-invasive nature of these devices makes them suitable for long-term monitoring, allowing healthcare providers to track patient sleep behaviour over extended periods without requiring intrusive procedures.

Future research should focus on validating these dBMs across larger, more diverse populations to ensure their generalizability. Additionally, integrating these dBMs into clinical workflows will require careful consideration of how to present the data in an interpretable and actionable manner for clinicians. One important next step will be developing user-friendly interfaces for visualizing sleep/wake data in a clinical setting.

Another avenue for future work involves personalizing the wake thresholds for each individual, as different patients may exhibit different movement patterns that could affect the accuracy of sleep/wake detection. Developing adaptive models that can learn from individual behaviours and adjust their sensitivity in real time would significantly improve the utility of dBMs in personalized healthcare.

In conclusion, while dBMs for daytime somnolence detection show great potential for enhancing patient care, further work is needed to ensure their reliability, scalability, and ease of use in everyday clinical practice.

4.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Quantifying excessive daytime sleepiness, a prodromal symptom in Parkinson's Disease.
Concept(s) of interest	Daytime napping behaviour, sleep episodes, and overall somnolence patterns.
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn accelerometer (actigraphy).
Type of measurement	Passive detection of sleep episodes during daytime hours
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	Number, duration, and frequency of naps detected through clustering algorithms using raw Actigraphy data.
Validation	Compared against participant-reported sleep diaries and Philips Actiware algorithm.
Assumptions	Accurate differentiation between activity and rest; clustering reflects true nap events.
Context of use considerations	Enhanced monitoring of sleep disorders and potential integration into diagnostic workflows.

5 Rest tremor tracking

5.1.1 Background and objectives

Rest tremor, characterised by rhythmic, involuntary movements in relaxed limbs, primarily hands, chin, legs, lips, and jaw (Shahed and Jankovic, 2007), is one of the cardinal symptoms of PD, according to the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke)). Rest tremor occurs when the body is relaxed, particularly when the hands are still, such as when a person is sitting or lying down with their hands resting. It may also appear during activities like walking if the hands are inactive and not engaged in movement. Accurate assessment is critical for diagnosing and monitoring disease progression (Vescio et al., 2021). Traditional methods, such as clinical observation and self-reporting, are often subjective and infrequent (Al Mahadin et al., 2020).

Wearable sensors like accelerometers and gyroscopes are increasingly used for real-time tremor monitoring, capturing severity and frequency in everyday activities (Vescio et al., 2021). This enables passive and remote symptom tracking, overcoming the limitations of periodic clinical assessments. It also helps detect early motor impairment, such as subtle gait or posture changes, facilitating earlier diagnosis and intervention (Urso et al., 2023). Studies show PD rest tremors typically occur at frequencies of 3-7 Hz (Raethjen et al., 2009; Deuschl et al., 2000), which we refer to as the tremor's frequency range and can be identified using spectral analysis of sensor data. This improves disease monitoring and allows for precise treatment adjustments, like medication timing and dosage optimization (Tortelli et al., 2021).

In AI-PROGNOSIS, we focus on two methods for tracking rest tremors in PD patients: a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)-based method (Powers et al., 2021) and a Machine Learning (ML)-based method (Mahadevan et al., 2020). The FFT-based utilizes FFT to detect tremor events by analysing frequency components within the PD-specific tremor range (3–7 Hz) with a signal processing pipeline. The ML-based method employs a machine learning pipeline with feature selection techniques for tremor detection and amplitude classification based on accelerometer data.

The objectives of rest tremor tracking in this context are to detect the presence and consistency of rest tremors and assess tremor amplitude over time to gain insights into tremor severity. As part of this project, implementing this dBM facilitates continuous monitoring and enhances predictive models, particularly the PD progression model, by providing data that will be used as input for more accurate predictions. This system will be externally validated using data collected in the dBM-DEV study of the project.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Datasets

For the development and evaluation of our rest tremor tracking method, we utilized two datasets: the Michael J. Fox Foundation Levodopa Response Study dataset (Daneault et al., 2021), hereafter referred to as the MJFF-LRS dataset, and the Verily Study Watch dataset (Atri et al., 2022) from the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) study.

Dataset selection

The MJFF-LRS dataset was chosen for its detailed, time-stamped recordings of wrist activity from PD patients, including accelerometer data and annotations of motor tasks. This makes it ideal for accurately training our tremor-tracking model. The Verily Study Watch dataset, part of the PPMI study, provided longitudinal motion and physiological data from a diverse cohort,

including PD patients, at-risk individuals, and healthy controls. This dataset was used to validate our model, ensuring it performs well across different patient profiles and settings. These datasets offer a robust foundation for both developing and validating our tremor tracking approach, enhancing its accuracy and real-world applicability.

MJFF-LRS Dataset

The MJFF-LRS dataset contains data solely from PD patients. The study was designed to monitor and understand motor fluctuations and symptoms in both home and clinical settings. A total of 31 PwPD were recruited from two sites, the Spaulding Rehabilitation Hospital (Boston, MA) and the Mount Sinai Hospital (New York, NY). Each participant wore a GeneActiv (Activinsights Ltd, Cambridgeshire, United Kingdom) on the wrist of the most affected limb, a Pebble smartwatch (Foxlink Group, New Taipei City, Taiwan) on wrist of the least affected limb, and a Samsung Galaxy Mini smartphone (Samsung Electronics Co., Ltd, Suwon, South Korea) in a fanny pack worn in front at the waist, recording data over a period of four days. During the trial, participants were assessed on both the first and last days, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation in different states. On Day 1, participants arrived at the laboratory in the ON state (i.e., after taking their medication). They completed demographic and medical history questionnaires, followed by sections I, II, and IV of the MDS-UPDRS. After donning sensors, participants completed a series of motor tasks, including those from the MDS-UPDRS Part III, as well as additional activities such as standing, walking, finger-to-nose, alternating hand movements, drawing, typing, and other daily tasks. They performed these tasks 6-8 times at 30-minute intervals. For the subset of participants recruited from Boston, labels are available for all tasks corresponding to all items in section III of the MDS-UPDRS. For all participants, however, clinical labels indicating symptom severity and/or symptom presence are available for all motor tasks. Limb-specific tremor severity scores (ranging from 0-4) were recorded for each arm and leg, along with the presence or absence of dyskinesia and bradykinesia in both upper and lower limbs. Here, tremor severity refers to kinetic, postural, or rest tremors. Rest tremor is considered to occur in states where the hand is at rest or inactive. Therefore, we consider tremor labels to refer to rest tremor during tasks that do not involve direct hand engagement, including standing, sitting, walking straight, walking while counting backward, walking through a narrow passage, stairs down, stairs up, and sit-to-stand.

On Days 2 and 3, all participants wore sensors at home and were instructed to conduct their usual activities while recording medication intake times and doses, as well as sleep and wake times. In addition, the Boston subset was asked to perform a short battery of motor tasks corresponding to specific items of section III of the MDS-UPDRS—alternating hand movements, finger-to-nose, and sitting quietly—every 30 minutes, for a total of seven times on each of the two days at home. On Day 4, participants returned to the clinic in a practical OFF state and repeated the Day 1 procedures, following the same motor tasks and assessments. The inclusion criteria required participants to be community-dwelling individuals currently undergoing treatment with L-dopa and experiencing motor fluctuations, while exclusion criteria included any significant neurological disorder or prior deep brain stimulation (DBS). After excluding three participants due to missing or corrupt data, the dataset included data from 28 participants (66.5 ± 8.8 years; 19 males and 9 females) (

Table 9). All participants were in the early stages of the disease, with a Hoehn and Yahr (H&Y) stage of at least two. It should be noted that the MDS-UPDRS 3.17 Score Distribution in

Table 9 refers to the average rest tremor score of the wrist of the most affected upper limb across the eight related to rest states, as described above. Accordingly, the rest tremor field

was calculated for each subject using these average scores, and a positive value was considered if the score was greater than 0.

Table 9 Demographic and clinical characteristics for MJFF-LRS dataset

Gender	n (%)
Male	19 (67.9%)
Female	9 (32.1%)
Age group	n (%)
46-56	8 (28.6%)
57-64	11 (39.3%)
65-80	9 (32.1%)
Most Affected Side by PD	n (%)
Right	19 (67.9%)
Left	7 (25.0%)
Bilateral	2 (7.1%)
Rest Tremor	n (%)
Yes	20 (71.4%)
No	8 (28.6%)
H&Y stage	n (%)
0	0 (0.0%)
1	0 (0.0%)
2	22 (78.6%)
3	3 (10.7%)
4	2 (7.1%)
Missing/Unknown	1 (3.6%)
MDS-UPDRS 3.17 Score Distribution	n (%) (Day 1/ Day 2)
0	20 (71.4%) / 19 (67.9%)
1	6 (21.5%) / 7 (25.0%)
2	2 (7.1%) / 2 (7.1%)
3	0 (0.0%) / 0 (0.0%)
4	0 (0.0%) / 0 (0.0%)

Verily Study Watch Dataset (PPMI)

The Verily Study Watch dataset is part of the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative² (PPMI), a longitudinal, multi-centre study designed to assess the progression of PD across its different stages. PPMI launched a sub-study using the Verily Study Watch³ (Verily Life Sciences LLC, a subsidiary of Alphabet Inc, South San Francisco, California) at sites within the United States. In this sub-study, all US-based PPMI participants were invited to wear the Verily Study Watch, equipped with an accelerometer, gyroscope, as well as other sensors such as a three-channel photoplethysmogram (PPG), electrodermal activity (EDA), and environmental sensors for pressure, temperature, and humidity. The dataset includes raw

² Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative study - <https://www.ppmi-info.org/>

³ Verily Study Watch - <https://verily.com/perspectives/introducing-verily-study-watch>

motion and physiological data, as well as extracted features related to sleep, physical activity, and heart activity, collected during both free-living conditions and clinical visits.

Subjects wore the Verily Study Watch for up to 23 hours per day over several months to two years, with average and median wear times of 18 and 21 hours per day, respectively. The recording period spanned between 254 to 560 days. Data captured included triaxial inertial sensors (accelerometer and gyroscope) sampled at 100 Hz, along with PPG, electrodermal activity (EDA), and environmental data (pressure, temperature, humidity). The data were collected without contextual labels, e.g., sleeping or walking. The Verily dataset includes 353 participants in total, 148 with PD, 158 PwPD risk factors, and 35 healthy controls.

We validated our best-performing method, initially trained on the MJFF-LRS dataset, using the Verily data. For our analysis, we utilised a subset of the Verily Study Watch dataset that included detailed activity annotations recorded during clinical visits. These annotations provided start and end timestamps for specific activities performed by the participants, allowing us to establish a reliable ground truth. For instance, certain subjects had annotations for activities they completed as part of their clinical assessments, such as the precise periods in which they performed MDS-UPDRS item 3.17 (rest tremor). This activity-specific timestamp information enabled us to accurately align sensor data with clinical observations, making it possible to assess inactivity and rest tremor states with greater precision. We initially acquired data from 161 subjects; however, three subjects were excluded because they lacked accelerometer data during the specific periods when item 3.17 was assessed. This resulted in a final dataset of 158 patients (62.4 ± 8.3 years; 73 males and 85 females), as shown in **Table 10**, from whom we identified 201 activities related to item 3.17. This validation not only tested the model's accuracy but also helped detect inactivity periods, enabling the evaluation of rest tremor and dyskinesia. We calculated the MDS-UPDRS 3.17 score Distribution and rest tremor fields, based on the average 3.17 scores derived from the performed MDS-UPDRS item-related activities

Table 10 Demographic and clinical characteristics of Verily Study Watch subset used for the validation of the rest tremor digital biomarker.

Gender	n (%)
Male	73 (46.2%)
Female	85 (53.8%)
Cohort	n (%)
PD patient	81 (51.3%)
Prodromal	66 (41.7%)
Healthy control	11 (7.0%)
Enrolment Age	n (%)
44-56	37 (23.4%)
57-64	57 (36.1%)
65-85	64 (40.5%)
Rest Tremor	n (%)
Yes	49 (31.0%)
No	109 (69.0%)
H&Y stage	n (%)
0	73 (46.2%)
1	12 (7.6%)

2	67 (42.4%)
3	3 (1.9%)
4	3 (1.9%)
MDS-UPDRS 3.17 Score Distribution	n (%)
0	109 (69.0%)
1	11 (7.0%)
2	24 (15.2%)
3	14 (8.8%)
4	0 (0.0%)

Ethical approval

Each participant in these studies provided informed consent to participate. MJFF-LRS received approval from the Institutional Review Boards of both the Spaulding Rehabilitation Hospital and Mount Sinai Hospital (Spaulding IRB #2014P000847; NY IRB #14-1569). Participating PPMI sites all received approval from an ethical standards committee before study initiation and written informed consent was obtained for all individuals participating in the study. The Verily Study Watch dataset, being a subset of PPMI, adheres to the initiative's ethical standards and protocols.

5.2.2 Data pre-processing

In our analysis for rest tremor tracking, we utilised data from both the MJFF-LRS and Verily Study Watch datasets, employing specific criteria to ensure the quality and relevance of the data for our research objectives. This sub-section details the selection criteria of each dataset.

MJFF-LRS dataset

For our analysis, we focused on data collected from the GENEActiv smartwatch. We excluded data from the Pebble smartwatch, as it was worn on the least affected side and, therefore, may not accurately capture tremor and motor fluctuations. Additionally, data from the Samsung Galaxy Mini smartphone was excluded since it was positioned at the waist. Our analysis specifically targeted data from Day 1 and Day 4 of the study, as these days included corresponding clinical assessment and rating of motor symptoms, including rest tremor. During our analysis, we excluded one subject (4_BOS) who lacked GENEActiv accelerometer data for the upper limb. This adjustment led to a total of 27 subjects.

Verily Study Watch dataset

In the preprocessing phase, we utilized detailed activity annotations from clinical visits, which included precise start and end timestamps for activities performed by subjects. For example, the timestamps indicate when subjects engaged in MDS-UPDRS item 3.17. This approach provided a reliable ground truth for our analysis, enabling us to evaluate the performance of our algorithm against clinically validated data. From the dataset, we extracted information from 158 unique subjects, identifying 201 distinct activities related to item 3.17 of the MDS-UPDRS, identifying 201 annotated instances where these subjects performed item 3.17 of the MDS-UPDRS. Each instance included start and end timestamps, facilitating us to assess and categorize the severity levels of tremor observed during these activities.

5.2.3 Digital biomarkers

We have implemented and compared two proposed methods for tracking rest tremors in PD patients, focusing on tremor detection and amplitude classification. These methods apply specifically to periods of hand stillness, identified through a specialized hand movement

classifier (Mahadevan et al., 2020), as depicted in **Figure 15**. This classifier processes accelerometer data using a sequence of steps to differentiate between active and inactive states. Initially, the accelerometer data undergoes preprocessing, where the x, y, and z-axis signals from the 3-axis accelerometer are combined to calculate a single vector magnitude that reflects the overall intensity of motion. A low-pass filter is then applied to eliminate high-frequency noise, smoothing the signal to highlight significant movements related to hand activity. The filter used is an infinite impulse response (IIR) filter of 6th order, Butterworth type. The classifier subsequently calculates a set of statistical features, including the rolling mean and standard deviation over a one-second sliding window. By calculating the Coefficient of Variation (CoV), which gauges signal variability relative to its average and applying an empirically derived threshold of 0.01 (Mahadevan et al., 2020) the classifier determines whether a hand movement is detected in each sample. The final output is an array of binary labels indicating the presence or absence of hand movement in each 2.56-second window. The algorithm first labels each sample within the window based on the CoV; then, it assigns the most frequent label among these samples as the label for the entire 2.56-second window.

Figure 16 provides an overview of the rest tremor tracking pipeline.

Figure 15 Overview of the hand movement classifier.

Figure 16 Overview of the rest tremor detection and assessment pipeline.

FFT-based method The first method is based on the Motor Fluctuations Monitor for Parkinson's Disease (MM4PD) (Powers et al., 2021) and uses the FFT for tremor detection. After preprocessing and converting raw sensor data into the frequency domain, the system checks for tremor presence by analysing frequency components within the tremor frequency range (3-7 Hz). The steps of the algorithm are detailed below.

Data preparation

- Resampling: Data is resampled to 50 Hz to reduce computational load while retaining signal quality.
- Segmentation: Resampled data is segmented into 2.56-s windows for processing. This allows the method to isolate short bursts of motion, crucial for detecting intermittent tremors with sufficient signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

- **FFT Transformation:** Each resampled window is transformed into the frequency domain using FFT to analyse frequency-specific features of the tremor.

Feature Extraction

- **Magnitude Calculation:** Before applying FFT, accelerometer axes are combined to estimate the overall wrist movement strength.
- **Harmonic SNR:** To refine tremor detection, we compute the harmonic SNR on the FFT output of each window. Harmonic SNR is a measure used to evaluate the strength of specific frequencies (harmonics) associated with a target signal, such as tremor, relative to background noise. By isolating power at harmonics—multiples of a fundamental frequency—this metric emphasizes the presence of repetitive, oscillatory patterns that characterize the signal of interest. In tremor detection, a high Harmonic SNR indicates that frequencies linked to tremor activity stand out prominently against random noise, enhancing the ability to differentiate true tremor events from non-tremor movements.

Tremor Detection

- **Peak Frequency Detection:** The frequency with the highest power within the 3-7 Hz range is identified.
- **Spectral Power Estimation:** Spectral power within the tremor-related frequency range is calculated. This power is a key measure of tremor intensity, as higher power values within the tremor frequency range suggest stronger tremors.
- **Tremor Detection Criteria - Tremor detection is based on two three conditions:**
 - A peak exists within the 3-7Hz range, which corresponds to the typical frequency of Parkinsonian tremor.
 - **Peak Power Threshold:** Tremor is detected if the peak power (A_p) within the tremor frequency range exceeds a predefined threshold of $T_{min} = 3.6$ which is empirically determined from the data.
 - **Power Ratio:** To further confirm tremor and reduce false positives, the peak power must also exceed $k = 2.1$ times the average power (A_{mean}) outside the tremor frequency range.

Tremor amplitude classification

- **Wrist Displacement:** Tremor severity is determined, in windows where tremor was detected, by calculating wrist displacement from the peak power (A_p) and corresponding frequency (f_p), $displacement = \frac{A_p}{(2\pi f_p)^2}$

ML-based method: The second method leverages an ML pipeline for rest tremor detection and amplitude classification and is based on the work of Mahadevan et al. (2020). After identifying hand rest periods, it uses accelerometer data to classify tremor events and quantify their severity. The steps of the algorithm are detailed below.

Input data.

- Three-axis raw acceleration signal

Data Preparation

- **Resampling:** Input data is resampled to 50 Hz to reduce complexity.
- **Filtering:** A first-order Butterworth bandpass filter isolates relevant tremor signals (3.5–7.5 Hz) and non-tremor movement (0.25–3 Hz).

- Dimensionality Reduction: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is applied to reduce the data into key signal components, minimizing the impact of device orientation and reducing motion complexity.

Feature extraction and ML model development

The processed signals include:

1. Three-axis accelerometer signals filtered in the tremor frequency band Three-axis accelerometer signals filtered in the non-tremor frequency band.
2. One PCA projection, in the tremor movement band, specifically using the first principal component, which captures the highest variance in this frequency band.
3. One PCA projection in the non-tremor movement band, using the first principal component.

These four processed signals are segmented into 2.56-second non-overlapping windows, enabling detailed tracking of tremor constancy and amplitude over time. From each window, 8 time-domain and frequency-domain features are extracted as listed in **Table 11**.

- Feature Selection: We used recursive feature elimination with cross-validation using a decision tree estimator (Guyon et al., 2003) to identify the most relevant features from the extracted ones. This feature selection method iteratively removes less important features to improve classification performance and reduce computational complexity.
- Model Training: A Random Forest (RF) classifier was trained using the selected features to predict the presence or absence of tremor. Since we lacked per-window ground truth, each window was labelled according to its task. RF effectively handles high-dimensional data and provides robust performance. To assess the model's ability to generalise, we employed a leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) cross-validation approach. This ensures that the model is evaluated on participants not seen during training, providing a realistic estimate of its ability to detect tremor across different subjects.
- Model Evaluation: In testing, task-level tremor presence was determined by the majority vote of predicted window labels within each task, providing an overall tremor classification per task. This approach compensates for the lack of per-window ground truth labels.

Tremor detection.

For unseen data, such as the Verily Study Watch dataset, we use an ensemble approach with majority voting across all LOSO-trained models. Each model first predicts a task-level label following the evaluation scheme described above. Then, a majority voting is applied across all models to determine the overall task-level tremor classification. We perform per-subject evaluation, where for each subject, we first average the predictions across all tasks and then average across all subjects.

Tremor amplitude classification.

Once tremor events are detected, we further classify the tremor amplitude within each tremor window. The process is as follows:

- The vector magnitude of the band-pass filtered in the tremor frequency range signal is computed. This helps eliminate the dependence on device orientation and accounts for tremor movement in all directions.
- Tremor Amplitude is calculated using the root mean square (RMS) of the vector magnitude for each 2.56s window.
- The 85th percentile tremor amplitude is calculated to summarize each subject's tremor severity over each separate task.

Table 11 Features extracted for training the tremor detector of the ML-based method. Asterisks (*) indicate the features that survived after the feature selection step.

Feature	Description
Root mean square value*	Root mean square value of the sensor data in a given time window. The RMS value is a measure of signal energy. The value of signal energy of accelerometer data is correlated with the amount and intensity of motion
Signal range*	Range of signal values. Signal range provides a measure of the extremes of motion observed in a given time window of sensor data. Higher range would indicate occurrence of a large excursion in sensor values.
Signal entropy*	Signal entropy is calculated by estimating Shannon entropy of the probability mass function of a signal. Signal entropy values close to zero indicate that the signal is periodic and smooth, whereas large negative values indicate that the signal is irregular and non-periodic
Dominant frequency*	Value of the frequency with the highest magnitude in the normalized power spectrum of the accelerometer signal. The dominant frequency value captures the fundamental frequency of the underlying movement (e.g., tremor, walking) producing the acceleration signal.
Dominant frequency magnitude	Magnitude of the dominant frequency in the normalized power spectrum. This feature captures the percentage of total signal energy in the dominant frequency. Higher values indicate that most of the signal energy is concentrated in the dominant frequency and lower values indicate that the signal energy is spread across the different frequencies in the power spectrum.
Ratio of dominant frequency band to total energy in spectrum	Ratio of the energy in the dominant frequency component to the sum of the energy in the entire frequency spectrum of a signal. This feature captures periodicity of a signal by calculating the ratio of the energy in the dominant frequency component to the sum of energy in the entire frequency spectrum of a signal.
Spectral flatness*	Spectral flatness is calculated by dividing the geometric mean of the power spectrum with the arithmetic mean. Spectral flatness captures the amount of modulation or the level of consistency and ranges from 0 to 1.
Spectral entropy*	Spectral entropy is calculated by estimating Shannon entropy of the probability mass function of the power spectrum of a signal. Values closer to 1 indicate presence of white noise. Values closer to 0 indicate presence of periodicity in the signal.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Selection of digital biomarkers

Training for tremor detection and amplitude classification was conducted exclusively on the MJFF-LRS dataset. Data from 27 subjects (

Table 9) were used for training and testing, covering various stages of tremor severity.

Rest tremor detection (MJFF-LRS dataset)

Table 12 provides a summary of the rest tremor detection results for both the FFT-based and the ML-based methods. Detection performance was evaluated by comparing the predictions of each algorithm against ground-truth labels in the MJFF dataset. For each task period, we identified tremor presence based on the label provided: if the label for rest tremor is marked as "0," it indicates no tremor is present. This approach allowed us to assess the accuracy of each method in detecting tremor during the specified task periods. After evaluating each task, we computed the average detection performance per subject, followed by an overall average performance across all subjects. This method ensures a balanced assessment by accounting for individual variability. Results obtained using the FFT-based method showed a mean tremor detection rate of 81%, which is a fair performance. The macro precision (0.65), recall (0.73),

and F1 score (0.69) indicate that while the method is effective at detecting tremor in general, it tends to miss certain instances or classify some tremors incorrectly, which slightly lowers its precision and recall. The balance between precision and recall, as reflected in the F1 score, suggests that the algorithm performs reasonably well, though improvements could be made in handling cases with more subtle or complex tremor patterns.

In contrast, the ML-based method performed slightly better across all metrics, with a mean detection rate of 85.5%. Its macro precision (0.71), recall (0.73), and F1 score (0.69) are noticeably higher than the FFT-based method. This improvement could be attributed to the ML model's ability to leverage more complex feature sets derived from both time and frequency domains. The use of feature selection and dimensionality reduction allows the ML-based method to better capture the variability in tremor presentation across different patients. The higher recall and precision suggest that the ML model is not only effective in identifying tremor events but also achieves this with fewer false positives, thereby enhancing detection accuracy overall. Detection performance was evaluated using approaches similar to Mahadevan et al., who reported an 83% accuracy with an F1 score of 83% for ML-based tremor detection.

Table 12 Rest tremor detection performance on the MJFF-LRS dataset.

Method	Mean tremor detection	Mean macro precision	Mean macro recall	Mean macro F1
FFT-Based Method	81.0%	0.65	0.66	0.62
ML-based Method	85.5%	0.71	0.73	0.69

Rest tremor amplitude classification (MJFF-LRS dataset)

Table 13 displays the performance of both methods in rest tremor amplitude classification with the MDS-UPDRS 3.17 item (Rest tremor amplitude) as ground truth. For rest tremor amplitude classification, the FFT-based method achieved a mean accuracy of 69.7%, which indicates it is relatively effective at estimating tremor severity but struggles with more subtle variations. Its macro precision (0.45) and recall (0.49) are fairly low, indicating that the model may not consistently identify tremor severity levels correctly. The macro F1 score of 0.52 corroborates this point, highlighting that the FFT-based method's balance between precision and recall could be improved. However, the Spearman's correlation coefficient (ρ) of 0.52, $p < 0.05$, with item 3.17 shows a moderate correlation between the algorithm's amplitude estimates and the clinical ratings, meaning that while the model is not perfectly accurate, it captures the overall trend in tremor severity.

The ML-based method shows a clear improvement in amplitude classification, with a mean accuracy of 77.7%, significantly better than the FFT-based approach. The increase in macro precision (0.53), recall (0.56), and F1 score (0.53) shows that the ML-based model is better at distinguishing between different tremor severity levels. This improvement can likely be attributed to the model's ability to integrate a more diverse set of features, capturing both time-domain and frequency-domain characteristics of tremor. The Spearman's correlation coefficient (ρ) of 0.64, $p < 0.05$, further supports the model's ability to follow the clinical ratings more accurately, demonstrating a stronger relationship between the predicted tremor amplitude and the MDS-UPDRS 3.17 scores.

Results of both tremor detection and amplitude classification indicate that while both methods perform reasonably well, the ML-based method generally outperforms the FFT-based approach across all metrics, especially in terms of precision and recall.

Table 13 Rest tremor amplitude classification results on the MJFF-LRS dataset, using various metrics.

Method	Mean rest tremor amplitude classification (MDS-UPDRS 3.17)	Mean macro precision	Mean macro recall	Mean macro F1	Spearman's ρ (amplitude – 3.17), $p < 0.05$
FFT-Based Method	69.7%	0.45	0.49	0.45	0.52
ML-based Method	77.7%	0.53	0.56	0.53	0.64

External validation (Verily Study Watch dataset)

To validate the best-performing ML-based method, we applied it to a subset of the Verily Study Watch dataset that includes annotated time periods corresponding to clinical visits. Specifically, we focused on the periods where we identified the 3.17 activity windows. The results, summarized in **Table 14**, indicate that the tremor detection algorithm performed satisfactorily on the Verily dataset.

On the other hand, the tremor amplitude classification algorithm did not yield favourable results, as shown in Table 15. This can be attributed to its training on the MJFF-LRS dataset, which limited its ability to effectively distinguish between neighbouring classes, e.g., between mild and moderate cases. To increase the accuracy of the algorithm, we plan to fine-tune the ML-based method with data from the Verily dataset (see Section 5.4.3).

Table 14 Rest tremor detection results on the Verily Study Watch dataset using the ML-based method.

Method	Mean tremor detection	Mean macro precision	Mean macro recall	Mean macro F1
ML-based Method	72.2%	0.72	0.72	0.72

Table 15 Rest tremor amplitude classification results on the Verily Study Watch dataset, using various metrics.

Method	Mean rest tremor amplitude classification (MDS-UPDRS 3.17)	Mean macro precision	Mean macro recall	Mean macro F1	Spearman's ρ (amplitude – 3.17), $p < 0.05$
ML-based Method	70.0%	0.69	0.70	0.69	0.28

5.4 Discussion

5.4.1 Interpretation

The rest tremor tracking methods showed promising results, especially the ML-based method, which outperformed the FFT-based method across multiple metrics. This suggests that the ML-based method is better at capturing both tremor presence and amplitude through its robust feature extraction, dimensionality reduction, and RF classification model. The ML-based approach uses PCA and recursive feature elimination, ensuring that only the most relevant features are considered. This improves the model's ability to generalise across different tremor levels.

Despite strong overall performance, both methods struggled with more severe cases. The ML-based model showed improved classification of tremor compared to the FFT-based method, likely due to its more nuanced feature selection and ability to handle higher-dimensional data. However, neither method performed well in classifying tremor across neighbouring severity levels, particularly in more severe cases, where classification errors were more frequent.

5.4.2 Limitations

A limitation in both datasets is the issue of class imbalance, which can affect the performance of tremor amplitude classification algorithms. This imbalance may lead to challenges in accurately identifying and differentiating between more severe tremor levels, potentially impacting overall classification performance. Limited exposure to severe tremor cases during training restricts the model's ability to learn the distinctive features associated with these categories. A more balanced training dataset could help improve performance and enhance the model's utility in monitoring PwPD.

5.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

Despite these limitations, the rest tremor tracking methods perform well, particularly the ML-based approach, in detecting tremor events, but face challenges in accurately classifying the most severe tremor cases due to dataset imbalances. Its high precision and recall suggest that it could be useful for early diagnosis and continuous monitoring in PD patients. The dBMs extracted by the system can provide clinicians with detailed tremor profiles, aiding in treatment adjustments and disease progression tracking.

As part of our future work, we aim to fine-tune the ML-based method, specifically on the Verily dataset, to yield better results. Additionally, we plan to explore the fusion of the FTT-based method and the ML-based approach to enhance overall performance in tremor classification.

5.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility
Concept(s) of interest	Rest tremor
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn device with accelerometer sensor
Type of measurement	Passive
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Digital score indicating the presence or absence of rest tremor derived from three-axis wrist acceleration Digital score of the amplitude of rest tremor derived from three-axis wrist acceleration
Validation	Type: In laboratory Primary measures of validation:

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 of the digital score of presence or absence of rest tremor, averaged across each task for each subject, and then averaged across all subjects, compared with MDS-UPDRS items 3.17a or 3.17b (upper limb rest tremor) score. This comparison specifically focuses on the wrist of the limb on which the watch is worn, with scoring based on whether it is greater than 0, indicating the presence of tremor. 2. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 and Spearman correlation of the digital score of rest tremor amplitude, averaged across each task for each subject, compared with MDS-UPDRS items 3.17a or 3.17b (upper limb rest tremor) score for the wrist of the limb on which the watch is worn.
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The accelerometer sensors capturing the data are reliable and sensitive enough • Wrist wearables are well tolerated by targeted users
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires participants to wear wrist devices with accelerometers sampling at ≥ 25 Hz

6 Dyskinesia tracking

6.1 Background and objectives

Dyskinesias are abnormal, involuntary movements of various body parts, typically occurring during the peak effects of levodopa in PwPD during the medication's ON state (Fabbrini et al., 2007). These movements, which may present as chorea, ballism, or dystonia, significantly affect the quality of life and complicate disease management. Dyskinesia tracking is crucial for both diagnostic and prognostic purposes, as early detection and continuous monitoring allow for better management of medication dosages and improved patient outcomes.

In this context, dBMs are being developed using inertial measurement unit (IMU) data from consumer-grade smartwatches. These sensors can capture detailed movement patterns, making them suitable for detecting dyskinesia in real-world settings. One prominent feature of dyskinesia, particularly chorea, is its erratic and abrupt nature. The main challenge in identifying choreiform motions using inertial sensors lies in finding features that can reliably differentiate the repeated, irregular and jerky motions of dyskinesia from the wide range of normal movements (Powers et al., 2021, Supplementary Material). Powers et al. (2021) demonstrated the potential of features like motion strength and spectral entropy in distinguishing dyskinetic movements from normal movements, particularly during seated or stationary tasks. These features aim to differentiate irregular, dyskinetic movements from normal daily activities. The authors demonstrated that these features can be combined into a "Choreiform Movement Score" (CMS) to reliably detect chorea in PD patients during seated or stationary tasks. An additional challenge is the fact that existing datasets only provide annotations indicating the presence or absence of dyskinesia events, without exact timestamps, making it difficult to train deep learning models that rely on precise temporal data to accurately capture and differentiate dyskinetic movements from normal behaviour.

In AI-PROGNOSIS, we aim to develop a dyskinesia tracking system that targets Parkinson's disease patients with Levodopa-induced dyskinesia, focusing on continuous, real-time monitoring. The system is intended to inform the medication response predictive model that the project is developing (Task T3.6 Medication response predictive modelling) and in general, serve as a monitoring tool to assist healthcare professionals in optimising treatment plans and

empower patients toward informed health management. The primary users of this technology include neurologists, movement disorder specialists, patients, and caregivers. The dyskinesia tracking system being developed will be externally validated with data that will be collected in the dBM-DEV study of the project.

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Datasets

We aimed to use the MJFF-LRS dataset, as described in Section 5.2.1. The MJFF-LRS dataset includes accelerometer recordings but lacks specific timestamp annotations for dyskinesia events. This absence of fine-grained temporal data limits the accuracy of models developed to detect dyskinesia. Instead, binary labels indicating the presence or absence of dyskinesia are provided, but only during clinical assessment sessions on Days 1 and 4. These labels reflect clinician-rated observations for dyskinesia presence or absence while subjects performed predefined tasks during these sessions.

6.2.2 Digital biomarkers

Following the study in (Powers et al., 2021), we extracted features related to dyskinesia (i.e. entropy, spectral entropy, and spectral energy in 1-4 Hz bins) and measured their correlations between with the dyskinesia presence/absence in each task of the MJFF-LRS dataset. However, no significant correlation was observed, which is mainly attributed to the weak annotation of the dataset, i.e. recordings of a task labelled as dyskinesia, also contain extensive non-dyskinesia segments.

6.3 Discussion

6.3.1 Limitations

The absence of detailed annotations in the MJFF-LRS dataset was the main limiting factor in dyskinesia tracking. The binary labelling of dyskinesia as present or absent without specific timestamps made it difficult to develop models that could accurately distinguish between normal and dyskinetic movements. This lack of annotated data reduced the efficacy of both conventional feature-based approaches and more advanced machine learning models.

Another challenge is the complexity of dyskinesia itself. Dyskinesia is difficult to detect from wearable accelerometers because sensors can only measure translational acceleration, but the twisting movements of dyskinesia are primarily rotational instead of translational -a rapidly rotating but relatively stationary wrist can occur in dyskinesia and will only lead to a small signal in the acceleration time series (Donie et al., 2023). Additionally, its movement frequency overlaps with daily activities, making it harder to distinguish from normal behaviour (Donie et al., 2023).

Furthermore, while time-series classification techniques, such as InceptionTime and RandOm Convolutional KErnel Transform (ROCKET) (Donie et al., 2023), have shown promise in detecting other PD symptoms like tremor and bradykinesia, they struggled with dyskinesia detection. ROCKET performed slightly better for dyskinesia, but both methods were hindered by the binary, weakly labelled data, limiting their overall effectiveness in identifying complex dyskinetic movements.

6.3.2 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

To address these limitations, we plan to develop a weakly supervised learning approach with specific steps to improve dyskinesia annotation and model performance. First, we will apply self-supervised learning to pre-train a model on the Verily dataset, focusing on subjects with dyskinesia to learn general movement characteristics that may indicate dyskinesia. Next, we

will fine-tune this pre-trained model on the MJFF dataset to enhance feature extraction. Since the MJFF dataset provides binary annotations for 30-second periods, offering finer temporal granularity, we will also incorporate multiple instance learning (MIL) (Papadopoulos et al., 2023) during fine-tuning. The MIL approach will help the model learn from the 30-second labelled periods, identifying dyskinesia patterns even without precise timestamps for individual movements. This strategy allows the model to leverage the available data more effectively, accounting for dyskinesia's variability and improving the accuracy of deep learning models.

6.4 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility
Concept(s) of interest	Dyskinesia
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn device with accelerometer sensor
Type of measurement	Passive
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	1. Digital score indicating the presence or absence of dyskinesia derived from three-axis wrist acceleration
Validation	Type: In laboratory Primary measures of validation: 1. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 of the digital score of the presence or absence of dyskinesia, averaged across each task for each subject, and then averaged across all subjects, compared with clinician-provided dyskinesia presence/absence score, based on clinical assessment.
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The accelerometer sensors capturing the data are reliable and sensitive enough Wrist wearables are well tolerated by targeted users
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires participants to wear wrist devices with accelerometers sampling at ≥ 25 Hz

7 Human activity recognition and physical activity tracking

7.1 Background and objectives

Recent research highlights the crucial role of physical activity in PD progression, with reduced activity closely linked to faster disease advancement (LaHue et al., 2019; Jones et al., 2022). Moreover, individuals engaging in moderate-to-vigorous physical activity face a lower risk of developing PD compared to those with sedentary lifestyles (Lin et al., 2024). Both consistent daily activity and concentrated exercise bursts effectively reduce PD risk (Lin et al., 2024).

In AI-PROGNOSIS, our focus is on implementing human activity recognition (HAR) models based on wrist accelerometer to inform the PD risk and progression predictive models with relevant physical activity data, and in general, be used as tracking tools of the subject's overall health status. Furthermore, HAR models could also serve as a complementary tool to the hand movement classifier for assessing motor symptoms, such as rest tremor (Section 5) and slowness of movement (Section 9).

7.2 Methods

7.2.1 Datasets

To develop and evaluate our HAR models, we utilized three distinct datasets, the MJFF-LRS dataset, the Capture-24 dataset (Chan et al., 2024), and PPMI's Verily Study Watch dataset. These three datasets formed a comprehensive and robust framework for training, testing, and validating the distinct models.

Dataset selection

Each dataset includes wrist accelerometry data and was chosen for its unique attributes, offering complementary insights into both PD-specific and general physical activity patterns.

MJFF-LRS dataset

The MJFF-LRS dataset (see Section 5.2.1 for details) focuses on 28 PwPD, recruited across two medical centres, who were monitored using a combination of smartwatches and accelerometers. The dataset provides labelled wrist accelerometry data from PwPD, collected in both clinical and free-living settings. This dataset is important in capturing disease-specific patterns of motor fluctuations, including tremor, bradykinesia, and dyskinesia. Participants performed several predefined tasks, such as walking, sitting, and climbing stairs, to enable the investigation of motor fluctuations.

Verily Study Watch dataset

The Verily Study Watch dataset offered rich longitudinal kinematic and physiological data from PD patients, at-risk individuals, and healthy controls, enabling validation of physical activity tracking models in both clinical and free-living conditions. The Verily Study Watch dataset (see Section 5.2.1 for details) from the PPMI study served as a validation dataset, focusing on 353 participants, including PwPD, prodromal subjects, and healthy controls.

Capture-24 Dataset

The Capture-24 dataset provides wrist-worn accelerometer data collected from 151 participants in 2014-2015 across the Oxfordshire area. Participants wore an Axivity AX3 accelerometer, which captured data across three axes (x, y, z) at a sampling rate of 100Hz. The total data collected amounts to 3,883 hours, of which 2,562 hours are annotated using a wearable camera and sleep diaries. This dataset provides a broader range of general physical activities and is agnostic to specific diseases, representing the general population and their daily activities.

To obtain the ground-truth annotations, participants wore an OMG Life Autographer camera during the daytime and kept sleep diaries to document their rest periods. Images from the camera were used to annotate the accelerometer data with various activities, such as walking, sitting, and sleeping. Due to the potentially intrusive nature of wearable cameras, ethical considerations were strictly adhered to, including allowing participants to review and remove any sensitive images. The demographic distribution of the sample shows that 66% were female, with ages ranging from 18 to over 53 years, as shown in **Table 16**.

Table 16 Demographic information of Capture-24 participants.

Gender	n (%)
Male	52 (34.4%)
Female	99 (65.6%)

Age (yrs)	n (%)
18 - 29	43 (28.5%)
30 - 37	37 (24.5%)
38 - 52	37 (24.5%)
≥53	34 (22.5%)

Ethical approval

Each participant in these studies provided informed consent to participate. For the MJFF-LRS and Verily Study Watch study the reader is referred to Section 5.2.1. The Capture-24 study was approved by the University of Oxford's Inter-Divisional Research Ethics Committee (IDREC reference: SSD/CUREC1A/13-262).

7.2.2 Data pre-processing

This sub-section outlines the specific preprocessing steps taken for each dataset, including the methods used to filter, segment, and standardise the data.

MJFF-LRS dataset

As in Section 5.2.2, we used the accelerometer data captured by the GENEActiv smartwatch, applying the same preprocessing methods as in the rest tremor tracking analysis. We focused on data from Day 1 and Day 4, which included clinical recordings and annotations essential for evaluating motor symptoms. Furthermore, we omitted certain task classes, including finger-to-nose movements and repeated arm movements, due to their repetitive, fine-motor nature. These tasks are less relevant for assessing overall physical activity and real-world motor fluctuations, in terms of gross motor symptoms and medication side effects, such as rest tremor and dyskinesias. Thus, the following 12 classes are used: i) Standing, ii) Sitting, iii) Walking All, iv) Sit to Stand, v) Drawing and Writing on Paper, vi) Typing on a Computer Keyboard, vii) Assembling Nuts and Bolts, viii) Taking and Drinking from a Glass, ix) Organizing Sheets in a Folder, x) Folding a Towel, xi) Stairs Up, xii) Stairs Down.

Capture-24 dataset

For the Capture-24 dataset, we employed the labelling scheme of Willetts et al. (2018), which groups activities into six primary categories: 1) Sit-Stand, 2) Sleep, 3) Mixed, 4) Walking, 5) Vehicle, and 6) Bicycling. These categories were derived from a larger set of annotations (Chan Chang et al., 2021) and were selected for their relevance to everyday, unconstrained behaviours. The decision to focus on these six categories enhances both the clarity and manageability of the dataset, enabling us to effectively capture and analyse the diverse range of activities performed by the participants. This labelling strategy ensures that the dataset retains its richness, while also streamlining the analysis by grouping similar activities together.

Verily Study Watch dataset

We followed the same preprocessing approach as for tremor tracking in Section 5.2.2, using detailed activity annotations from clinical visits. We acquired data from 158 subjects, identifying 201 instances of the activity associated with item 3.17 of the MDS-UPDRS, specifically during periods when the subjects were sitting. From these instances, we derived 398 annotated samples, each representing a 5-second window of inactivity, indicating that the subject was in a rest state

Common steps for all datasets

For all three datasets, the following pre-processing steps were applied:

- **Segmentation:** Following Bulling et al. (2014), we split the signals into windows of equal duration, effectively treating them as independent inputs to the HAR model. Thus, the data were segmented into 5-s windows to standardize input size for the models and to ensure consistency across datasets.
- **Handling invalid values:** All not-a-number or invalid entries were removed to ensure data quality and prevent errors during model training.
- **Resampling:** The data were resampled to 30 Hz using linear interpolation to ensure that all datasets adhered to a consistent sampling rate, making them compatible with our model's input requirements.

This uniform preprocessing approach ensures that the data from all three datasets are comparable, clean, and appropriately formatted for model training and evaluation. By harmonising the datasets in this way, we can leverage their diverse attributes while maintaining robustness and accuracy in our analysis.

7.2.3 Digital biomarkers

Our approach utilises a multi-task self-supervised learning (SSL) pipeline (Yuan et al., 2024) leveraging a model pre-trained on the UK Biobank dataset (Doherty et al., 2017). This dataset contains more than 700,000 person-days of unlabelled wearable sensor data from more than 100,000 participants. The advantage of using this large, diverse dataset lies in its free-living nature, encompassing a broad spectrum of human activities in real-world environments. This adaptability is crucial for tracking physical activity and motor fluctuations in PD

Figure 17 Overview of the human activity recognition (HAR) pipeline.

The SSL model, as shown in **Figure 17**, comprises two main parts: a feature extractor and a classifier. The feature extractor is a deep neural network pre-trained through self-supervised learning to recognize patterns and dependencies in human motion, making it well-suited for generalization across external datasets, devices, and tasks. The classifier, which is not trained in the SSL phase, is later fine-tuned for specific downstream tasks. This structure allows the model to extract rich temporal dependencies from unlabelled data, essential for human activity recognition (HAR). The feature extractor is trained to recognize patterns through three key self-supervised tasks:

- **Arrow of Time (AoT):** The model distinguishes whether activities are played forward or backwards, enhancing its understanding of the natural progression of activities.
- **Permutation:** The model identifies changes in the order of shuffled signal chunks, reinforcing its ability to capture the correct sequence of actions in physical activities.
- **Time Warping (TW):** By stretching or compressing sections of the time-series data, this task trains the model to detect variations in movement intensity and speed.

Each of these tasks is handled by a task-specific head, which is a simple classification layer that predicts whether the transformation (e.g., reverse or permute) was applied to the input data. These heads are trained in parallel, helping the model learn different facets of the data. Weighted sampling addresses class imbalance by focusing on segments with higher activity levels.

Feature extractor

The feature extractor learns a rich representation of human motion dynamics. It processes the input accelerometer signals, capturing detailed temporal dependencies that are important for tasks, such as HAR and motor fluctuation detection. This pre-trained network captures generalized motion features across various activities and populations.

Fine-tuning

We fine-tuned the pre-trained model using the labelled MJFF-LRS and Capture-24 datasets. This fine-tuning involved training the second part of the model, which is a classifier that detects the specific activities of those datasets. The feature extractor (the first part of the model) was left pre-trained, as it had already learned generalized motion dynamics and intensity patterns from the UK Biobank data. For the fine-tuning of the MJFF-LRS and Capture-24 datasets, we employed a 5-fold cross-validation approach, grouping data by subject to ensure robust model performance and minimize bias across the training and evaluation phases. This subject-level cross-validation ensured that each subject's data was exclusively in either the training or testing set for each fold, avoiding any overlap and thus preventing data leakage. This transfer learning approach allows for effective activity tracking, even with smaller labelled datasets, and improves performance compared to models trained from scratch.

Inference

For inference on new, unseen data, we utilise a majority voting scheme classifying each time window as the activity detected by the majority of the five models derived from the 5-fold cross-validation scheme. This approach enhances the reliability and accuracy of activity classification.

7.3 Results

7.3.1 Selection of digital biomarkers

Results from the evaluation of our HAR models demonstrate their effectiveness in tracking human action and physical activity. Below, we present the findings from the fine-tuning of the MJFF-LRS and Capture-24 datasets and the external validation results on a subset of the Verily Study Watch dataset, highlighting key performance metrics and the implications for monitoring motor symptoms and inactivity states. We evaluated the performance of the HAR models in correctly classifying each time window of the test set in terms of activity based on the available annotations of each dataset. We report the mean of performance metrics across the five folds of the cross-validation scheme.

HAR tuned on activities of the MJFF-LRS dataset (PD population)

Evaluation results of the HAR model finetuned on the MJFF-LRS dataset (**Table 17**) show strong performance in tracking actions in PD patients. The model achieves satisfactory accuracy (85.1%) and precision (0.82). The recall (0.78) is slightly lower, which suggests that while the model is highly effective in identifying motor activities correctly, it may miss some instances of specific activities, particularly those that are less frequent or exhibit subtler movement patterns. The F1 score (0.80) provides a balanced measure of both precision and recall, further corroborating the robustness of the model in this PD-specific dataset. An analysis of the confusion matrix (**Figure 18**) reveals performance variability across specific activities. Classes such as walking and standing exhibit high recall, reflecting the model's robustness in detecting these frequent activities. On the other hand, activities like drawing or folding demonstrate lower recall, potentially due to their less distinct movement patterns. This variability highlights the influence of movement complexity on classification performance.

Table 17 Performance of the HAR model fine-tuned on the MJFF-LRS dataset.

Metric	Mean
Accuracy	85.1%
Precision	0.82
Recall	0.78
F1 score	0.80

Figure 18 Confusion Matrix on the MJFF-LRS dataset.

HAR tuned on activities of the Capture-24 dataset (General population)

Evaluation results of the HAR model finetuned on the Capture-24 dataset (Table 18) demonstrate that the model performs well in terms of action recognition and physical activity tracking in a disease-agnostic population. Accuracy (77.2%) is comparable to that of the MJFF-LRS-tuned model. At the same time, the slightly lower recall (0.66) suggests that this HAR model may face challenges in detecting less frequent or more subtle activities within the general population. Nevertheless, the high precision (0.71) indicates that the model effectively minimises false positives, ensuring a fairly accurate classification of activities.

The confusion matrix for Capture-24 (Figure 19) illustrates a similar variability in performance across activities. Frequent activities such as sleeping and sitting-standing are classified with

high accuracy, whereas less distinct or less frequent activities show reduced classification accuracy. These findings highlight the challenge of distinguishing between activities with similar characteristics and underscore the impact of dataset variability on classification performance.

Table 18 Performance of the HAR model fine-tuned on the Capture-24 dataset.

Metric	Mean
Accuracy	77.2%
Precision	0.71
Recall	0.66
F1 score	0.68

Figure 19 Confusion matrix on the Capture-24 dataset.

External validation on the Verily Study Watch dataset – Active vs. Inactive states

A subset of the Verily Study Watch dataset was used to investigate the face validity of the HAR model fine-tuned on the MJFF-LRS. The focus was on distinguishing between active and inactive states - we consider periods labelled as ‘Sitting’ or ‘Standing’ as rest states. The model achieves perfect performance, with an accuracy of 100% and precision, recall, and F1 score of 1.0, with no false positives or missed detections. This indicates that the HAR model demonstrates good face validity in an external dataset, effectively distinguishing between activity and inactivity periods.

7.4 Discussion

7.4.1 Interpretation

Evaluation results showcase the HAR models' effectiveness in tracking human actions and physical activity in PD-specific (MJFF-LRS dataset) and general populations from wrist accelerometry. High accuracy and precision indicate that the models are well-suited for continuous monitoring, providing valuable insights into various motor states, such as periods of rest and movement. Additionally, the evaluation results on the Verily Study Watch set showcase good face validity and effectiveness in accurately identifying inactivity periods, which are a necessary step for assessing motor symptoms such as rest tremor and dyskinesia.

7.4.2 Limitations

While our HAR models demonstrate promising results, certain limitations must be acknowledged. Performance depends on data quality which can vary significantly when collecting continuous real-world data from wearable devices. To ensure sufficient data quality, minimum requirements include consistent sampling rates, accurate sensor calibration, and low levels of noise. The data should also be free from significant gaps or missing values to maintain temporal integrity. Additionally, wearable devices should be worn consistently by the subject to capture a complete and representative picture of their motor activities. Moreover, the relatively small size of the MJFF-LRS dataset, with data from 28 participants, may limit, to a certain extent, the robustness and generalisability of the model.

7.4.3 Usability of digital biomarkers in the context of current care

The continuous, remote monitoring of physical activity through widely-acceptable wrist wearables can have considerable contribution in the screening and management of PD. These metrics can provide patients, caregivers, and clinicians with indicators of the disease onset and progression, enabling, together with others dBMs, more personalized treatment adjustments.

7.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility
Concept(s) of interest	Various aspects of physical activity
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn device with accelerometer sensor
Type of measurement	Passive
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	1. Digital score indicating activity classes that categorise human action or type of physical activity.
Validation	Type: In laboratory and in real world Primary measures of validation: 1. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 of the digital score that corresponds to activity classes, averaged across all subjects, compared to the labelled activities.
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The accelerometer sensors capturing the data are reliable and sensitive enough Wrist wearables are well tolerated by targeted users
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires participants to wear wrist devices with accelerometers sampling at ≥ 25 Hz

8 Slowness of movement tracking with keystroke dynamics

8.1 Background and objectives

Rigidity and bradykinesia are cardinal PD motor symptoms that significantly affect the person's mobility and consequently their quality of life. Along with tremors, they form a collection of symptoms referred to as Parkinsonism, which constitutes the core of the clinical diagnostic criteria of PD (Postuma et al., 2015). Sub-threshold Parkinsonism is further considered a prodromal marker of PD (Heinzel et al., 2019). Conventional clinical assessments provide a standardised and detailed, yet imperfect way to assess these symptoms, as they are plagued by low resolution (patient snapshot) and lack of ecological validity.

There is an increasing popularity of smart sensor use for capturing the spatiotemporal properties of movement (for an extensive review see D2.3, section 2.3.7) in daily life. Recent research developed dBMs to unobtrusively assess rigidity and bradykinesia, based on either passive tracking of upper limb movements using wearable inertial measurement units (IMUs) (Mahadevan et al., 2020) or keystroke dynamics during touchscreen typing (Iakovakis et al., 2018; Iakovakis et al., 2020), showing that both modalities have potential in assessing rigidity and bradykinesia.

Assuming that passive data collection from wrist-worn devices or during routine typing is well tolerated by users, in AI-PROGNOSIS, we are implementing dBMs of upper limb slowness of movement, using unobtrusively collected kinematic data from wearable sensors and keystroke dynamics data from touchscreen keyboards. In the former case, we target grosser movements, while in the latter, fine motor skills. Implementations are based on the works of Iakovakis et al. (2018a, 2018b) and Mahadevan et al. (2020).

The aim is dual, i.e., to develop a system for more accurate tracking of PD motor symptoms (as part of the AI-PROGNOSIS minimum viable products) in daily life and to use the dBMs (or their constituent features) as input to the predictive models for PD risk assessment and prognosis that the project is developing. At this stage, dBMs were implemented based on existing datasets. They will be refined and validated based on data collected in the dBM-DEV study of the project. This section focuses on dBMs of slowness of fine movement derived from keystroke dynamics. Wrist accelerometry-based dBMs are detailed in Section 9.

8.2 Methods

8.2.1 Datasets

To implement the keystroke dynamics-based dBMs, two datasets were employed containing keystroke-related data from PwPD and unaffected controls, i.e., a dataset collected *in-clinic* (in controlled conditions), and a dataset collected *in-the wild* (in real world conditions). Both datasets were collected during the i-PROGNOSIS⁴ project, using a custom virtual keyboard for Android smartphone devices developed by AI-PROGNOSIS partner AUTH. The keyboard captured the timestamps of the press and release touch events for each key in bouts, without interfering with natural typing. Each bout, henceforth named *typing session*, was initiated with the pop-up of the keyboard and concluded when the keyboard was minimised. Characters

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690494>

typed were not recorded. For each dataset and participant, there are multiple typing sessions available along with socio-demographic data and clinical scores, including UPDRS Part III assessments. The *in-clinic* and *in-the-wild datasets* are detailed by Iakovakis et al. (2018a, 2020) and briefly described below.

In-clinic dataset

This dataset is detailed by Iakovakis et al., (2018a). It comprises data collected by 33 participants, 18 persons with early PD (Hoehn & Yahr stages I and II) and 15 participants without PD (healthy controls - HC). The two groups were matched as closely as possible in terms of sex, age, education level, and years of experience in smartphone use. **Table 19** shows the key clinico-demographic characteristics of the study sample. Eligibility criteria were set as follows:

- Touchscreen-equipped smartphone use for at least one year
- No other psycho-motor impairment diagnosis, or cognitive dysfunction, or upper limb functional limitations
- Normal or corrected-to-normal vision

The participants were recruited from two neurological clinics in Thessaloniki, Greece. In a single visit, the participants performed a typing task, followed by the standard clinical examination. During the typing task, they were requested to type 11 text excerpts of the famous fairy-tale “The Little Prince” in Greek using the custom virtual keyboard, with a 1-min interval between excerpts. Only the first excerpt (200 characters-long) was common for all participants, as a means to familiarise themselves with the keyboard, while the rest were drawn randomly from a pool of text excerpts (46–115 characters-long). Subsequently participants’ motor function was assessed with UPDRS Part III (motor examination). PwPD were instructed not to take their anti-parkinsonian medication for eight (8) hours pre-visit and therefore, they underwent all study procedures, practically in the “OFF” state. All HC participants were assigned a zero UPDRS score, without assessment.

Table 19 Clinico-demographic characteristics of the subjects that generated the in-clinic typing dataset. N.A.: not applicable.

Characteristics	Early PD patients	Controls
n (total n = 33)	18	15
Demographics		
Females (%)	4 (22%)	7 (46%)
Males (%)	14 (78%)	8 (54%)
Avg. age in years (std)	61 (8.4)	57 (3.9)
Clinical characteristics		
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	2.5 (1.6)	N.A.
Avg. UPDRS Part III score (std)	16.9 (7.8)	0.0 (0.0)
Most affected side - Left/Right	13/5	N.A.
Dominant hand - Right/Left/Ambidextrous	18/0/0	15/0/0

Study procedures were approved by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece (Bioethics Committee of Medical School, approval no. 359/3.4.17). Informed consent was obtained in

writing from all subjects prior to their participation in the study. The dataset is open and available on the Zenodo platform⁵.

In-the-wild dataset

The dataset includes 22,894 typing sessions captured from 32 persons, 22 persons with early PD and 10 unaffected controls (HCs), along with socio-demographic data and two clinical assessments (baseline and follow-up) in a span of approximately eight (8) months. The dataset was collected as part of the SData study of the i-PROGNOSIS project⁶. The study involved the passive collection of digital phenotyping data, including typing data, in daily life through a smartphone app. Participants were recruited in 3 countries (Greece, Germany and United Kingdom). The dataset does not include information on the medication (regimen and schedule) of PwPDs, and handedness information was not available. **Table 20** provides an overview of the key clinico-demographic characteristics of the study sample. The dataset is open and available on the Zenodo platform⁷.

Table 20 Clinico-demographic characteristics of the subjects that generated the in-the-wild typing dataset. N.A.: not applicable.

Characteristics	Early PD patients	Controls
n (total n = 20)	22	10
Demographics		
Females (%)	5 (23%)	5 (50%)
Males (%)	17 (77%)	5 (50%)
Avg. age in years (std)	60.2 (9.6)	51.5 (12.6)
Clinical characteristics		
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	5.52 (3.76)	N.A.
Avg. UPDRS Part III score (std)	20.8 (11.6)	1.5 (2.5)
Most affected side - Left/Right	Unknown	N.A.
Dominant hand - Right/Left/Ambidextrous	Unknown	Unknown

8.2.2 Data pre-processing

The pre-processing pipeline is outlined in **Figure 16**. In brief the steps followed are:

1. For each session the *Hold Time (HT)* and *Flight Time (FT)* sequences are calculated. Hold time (HT) is defined as the time between a key press and release and flight time (FT) is the time between the release of a key and the press of the subsequent key (**Figure 21**). HT and FT are typical variables of keystroke (or key tap) dynamics.
2. Any HT_n in the **HT** sequence outside of the [0,300] ms interval was discarded. Similarly, any FT_n in the **FT** sequence outside the [0,3000] ms interval was also discarded.

⁵ Keystroke timing and pressure data captured during touchscreen typing by early Parkinson's disease patients and healthy controls - <https://zenodo.org/records/2571623>

⁶ i-PROGNOSIS SData study (UK) - <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/application-summaries/research-summaries/i-prognosis-sdata-study/>

⁷ Smartphone sensor data (accelerometer, virtual keyboard) collected in-the-wild by Parkinson's Disease patients and Healthy Controls - <https://zenodo.org/records/4311175>

3. The *Normalised Flight Time* (NFT) vector NFT is calculated as the typing session's detrended FT sequence, i.e., $NFT = FT - \overline{FT}$, where \overline{FT} is the typing session's mean FT value.
4. Only NFT values above the 1st percentile and below the 99th percentile of a real-life data distribution $[-1270, 1700]$ ms (Iakovakis et al., 2018) were kept.
5. For the *in-the-wild* dataset only typing sessions with more than 40 key taps and only subjects with more than 10 typing sessions were kept.
6. From the HT and NFT sequence of each eligible typing session, the mean and standard deviation of HT and the skewness of FT are calculated and form the feature vector representing the typing session. These features were found to be the most informative by Iakovakis et al. (2018a).

Figure 20 Feature vector estimation pipeline from keystroke timing data of a single typing session. HT: hold time; FT: flight time; NFT: normalised flight time; std: standard deviation; skew: skewness.

Figure 21 Representation of keystroke events and keystroke dynamics variables.

8.2.3 Digital biomarkers

Using the aforementioned feature vector as input, we developed individual regression models to approximate UPDRS Part III Items 22 (Rigidity), 23 (Finger tapping), and 31 (Body bradykinesia and hypokinesia) scores, as digital indicators/scores of rigidity and slowness of movement. Where applicable, the UPDRS item scores of the dominant limb were selected as targets. In the case of the in-clinic dataset, all subjects were right-handed. We first developed and evaluated the models on the in-clinic dataset, that represents a fairly accurate mapping of keystroke timing data to motor function status, and then tested their generalisability in the “noisy” in-the-wild dataset.

Using the full in-clinic dataset, we trained and tested a Random Forest (RF) regressor using a leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) cross-validation scheme. Feature vectors of typing sessions of each subject were labelled based on the UPDRS Item score of interest of the specific subject. The median value of the regressor outputs across typing sessions of the held-out subject was considered as the digital score (indicator) representing the motor impairment of the subject.

After evaluating in-clinic validity, RF regressors were trained on the whole in-clinic dataset and tested on the in-the-wild dataset. The median output score across all typing sessions of the observation period for each subject in the in-the-wild dataset was considered as the digital score representing the motor impairment of the subject. Results

8.2.4 Sample characteristics

Table 21 presents the clinico-demographic characteristics of the subjects in the in-the-wild dataset, the typing sessions of whom were retained after applying the conditions of typing session length (> 40 key taps) and number of available typing sessions (> 10).

Table 21 Clinico-demographic characteristics of the participants in the in-the-wild dataset after applying the conditions for typing session length (>40 key taps) and number of available typing sessions (>10).

Characteristics	Early PD patients	Controls
n (total n = 22)	15	7
Demographics		
Women # (%)	3 (20%)	4 (57%)
Men # (%)	12 (80%)	3 (43%)
Avg. age in years (std)	60.6 (10.74)	47.0 (7.09)
Clinical characteristics		
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	5.78 (4.22)	N.A.
Avg. UPDRS Part III score (std)	20.46 (12.84)	0.78 (1.07)
Dataset characteristics		
Available typing sessions	3,669 (75%)	1,232 (25%)

Figure 22 and **Figure 23** illustrate the distribution of the UPDRS Item scores of interest for the in-clinic and the in-the-wild sample, respectively. The in-the-wild study includes two clinical assessments for each subject, one at baseline and one follow-up at the end of the observation period (in a span of approximately eight months). To evaluate the performance of the models, where applicable, the mean right upper limb item score across the two clinical assessments was used as the ground truth. The score of the right upper limb was used due to the lack of handedness information in the dataset, considering that the vast majority of people are right-handed; this is a limitation of the analysis.

Figure 22 Distribution of scores of UPDRS Part III items of interest (22, 23, 31) for PwPD and controls, as well as for each group separately, in the in-clinic dataset.

Figure 23 Distribution of scores of UPDRS Part III items of interest (22, 23, 31) for PwPD and controls, as well as for each group separately, in the in-the-wild dataset.

8.2.5 Selection of digital biomarkers

In-clinic validity

For evaluating model performance, Spearman's correlation (r) and the mean absolute error between the digital score and the actual UPDRS item score were used. **Table 22** presents the mean and confidence intervals of the correlation coefficient and of the mean absolute error over 200 iterations of the LOSO scheme on the in-clinic dataset, for each UPDRS Part III item of interest. **Figure 24** further shows the output digital scores with respect to the associated UPDRS Part III Item scores for a single, complete run of the LOSO scheme. Moderate to high, significant correlations were obtained for UPDRS Part III Items 23 (Finger tapping) and 22 (Rigidity) and the associated digital scores.

Table 22 Performance of the model trained and tested on the in-clinic dataset; CI: confidence interval.

Targeted UPDRS Part III Item	Mean Spearman r [95 % CI]	MAE [95 % CI]
Finger Tapping (Item 23)	0.67 [0.64, 0.69] ($p < 0.05$)	0.49 [0.48, 0.50]
Rigidity (Item 22)	0.74 [0.72, 0.76] ($p < 0.05$)	0.30 [0.29, 0.31]
Upper Body Bradykinesia (Item 31)	0.54 [0.51, 0.56] ($p < 0.05$)	0.41 [0.40, 0.42]

Figure 24 Digital scores (Prediction) with respect to the clinical score of each UPDRS Part III item of interest (ground truth) for a single, complete run of the LOSO cross-validation scheme on the in-clinic dataset.

In-the-wild generalisation

Generalisation was evaluated after training the regression models on the in-clinic dataset and inferring on the in-the-wild dataset. **Table 23** presents the mean and confidence intervals of the Spearman correlation coefficient and of the mean absolute error over 200 iterations for each UPDRS Part III item of interest. **Figure 25** further shows the output digital scores on the in-the-wild dataset with respect to the associated UPDRS Part III Item scores. A high, significant correlation is observed again for UPDRS Part III Items 23 (Finger tapping) and the associated digital score, with correlations for Item 22 (Rigidity) and 31 (Body bradykinesia/hypokinesia) being moderate to low.

Due to the potential bias introduced in the dataset by the HCs with zero UPDRS Part III, we repeated the analysis by training only on the in-clinic data and testing on the in-the-wild data of PwPDs only. The correlation of the digital score with UPDRS Part III Item 23 (Finger tapping) remained significantly strong (**Table 24**), while no significant correlations were obtained for the other two items (rigidity and whole-body bradykinesia/hypokinesia).

Based on the results obtained from the in-clinic and in-the-wild analyses, we conclude that the keystroke dynamics-based digital score reflecting finger slowness of movement is a potentially valid dBM, with limitations (see Section 8.3). The dBM will be further refined and evaluated with data that will be collected in the project's dBM-DEV study.

Table 23 Performance of the model trained on the in-clinic dataset and tested on the in-the-wild dataset; CI: confidence interval.

UPDRS Part III Item	Spearman r [95 % CI]	MAE [95 % CI]
Finger Tapping (Item 23)	0.84 [0.82, 0.85] ($p < 0.05$)	0.33 [0.32, 0.34]
Rigidity (Item 22)	0.58 [0.56, 0.59] ($p < 0.05$)	0.56 [0.55, 0.57]
Body Bradykinesia Hypokinesia (Item 31)	0.53 [0.50, 0.56] ($p < 0.05$)	0.53 [0.52, 0.54]

Figure 25 Digital scores (Prediction) of the in-the-wild sample with respect to the clinical score of each UPDRS Part III item of interest (ground truth) for a sample run.

Table 24 Performance of the model trained on the in-clinic dataset and tested on the in-the-wild dataset, with data only from PwPD in both cases; CI: confidence interval.

UPDRS Part III Item	Spearman r [95 % CI]	MAE [95 % CI]
Finger Tapping (Item 23)	0.81 [0.79, 0.83] ($p < 0.05$)	0.36 [0.35, 0.38]
Rigidity (Item 22)	Not significant ($p > 0.05$)	0.68 [0.66, 0.69]
Body Bradykinesia Hypokinesia (Item 31)	Not significant ($p > 0.05$)	0.68 [0.67, 0.70]

Slowness of movement assessment pipeline

The pipeline we have developed for evaluating the slowness of movement is depicted in **Figure 26**. It begins with capturing a typing session with the custom virtual keyboard. This session undergoes preprocessing by calculating the Hold Time and Normalized Flight Time sequences. If the length of the sequences is less than 40, the typing session is not considered for the analysis. Then, we extract the features from the sequences. The extracted features are then fed to the slowness assessment model that evaluates the typing session and outputs the slowness of movement score.

Figure 26 Slowness of movement assessment pipeline from keystroke dynamics.

8.3 Discussion

8.3.1 Interpretation

We aimed to develop and evaluate a robust dBM of the slowness of fine movement based on keystroke dynamics. Training the dBM estimating model using the data captured in clinic and validating on the in-the-wild dataset was performed to ensure model robustness and generalisability. The results indicate that the keystroke dynamics-based digital score is strongly correlated with the UPDRS Part III score associated with finger tapping, both in clinic and in the wild. On the contrary, no significant association was found based on real word data between the digital scores and the upper body bradykinesia and rigidity clinical scores.

The emerging predictability of finger slowness could be attributed to the motor equivalence between the clinical finger tapping test and the on-screen finger movement during typing. During the assessment of the UPDRS 23 item (finger tapping) the clinician instructs the patient to alternatively touch their thumb on their index finger. This motion has a close resemblance to finger movement during typing, regardless of typing style, i.e., with one hand (usually with the index finger) or both hands (usually with the thumbs).

8.3.2 Limitations

In our approach, the small sample size of the training dataset and the assumption of right-hand dominance in the in-the-wild sample are obvious limitations. Nevertheless, evaluating the dBM estimating model in an independent, real-world dataset indicates good generalisability. Furthermore, we have not studied the effect of medication-induced ON-OFF states on the digital scores since the information was not available in the in-the-wild dataset, as well as the effects of age, handedness, and other possible covariates of keystroke dynamics. Additionally, we have used the data from the whole observation period to estimate the aggregate (median) digital score of each subject in the in-the-wild dataset and we have not investigated yet the fluctuation of the score over time. We aim to do so using the data from the dBM-DEV study, by performing a test-retest reliability analysis using various time aggregation intervals. Finally, our model was trained using data exclusively from early PD patients with UPDRS score ≤ 2 . Combined with the known inability of Random Forests to extrapolate beyond the range of the training data, this restricts the validity of the dBM to patient populations similar to the training set. Therefore, this model cannot be used for patients on a higher H&Y stage or with greater motor symptom severity. In our analysis, only one instance within the Rigidity Item 22 presented this issue.

8.3.3 Usability of digital biomarkers in the context of current care

In each current form, with the aforementioned limitations, the proposed keystroke dynamics-based digital score of finger bradykinesia has promising potential in unobtrusively detecting and assessing relevant impairment in persons at early stages of PD, with high applicability in daily life since typing on touchscreens is nowadays a common, routine activity. We plan to further refine and validate this novel dBM with data from the upcoming clinical studies of the project.

8.4 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility
Concept(s) of interest	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Finger bradykinesia 2. Upper limb rigidity 3. Whole-body bradykinesia
Measurement technology	Touchscreen in combination with a custom virtual keyboard
Type of measurement	Passive
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital score of finger bradykinesia severity derived from keystroke dynamics during touchscreen typing 2. Digital score of rigidity severity derived from keystroke dynamics during touchscreen typing 3. Digital score of whole-body bradykinesia severity derived from keystroke dynamics during touchscreen typing
Validation	<p>Type: In laboratory and in real world</p> <p>Primary measures of validation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spearman correlation of digital score of finger bradykinesia with UPDRS Part III item 23 (finger tapping) score of dominant hand 2. Spearman correlation of digital score of rigidity with UPDRS Part III item 22 (upper limb rigidity) score of dominant hand 3. Spearman correlation of digital score of whole-body bradykinesia with UPDRS Part III item 31 (whole-body bradykinesia) score
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Touchscreens accurately capture finger tap timing events. • Relevant data collection in the background without interfering with natural typing is well tolerated by subjects. • Dominant hand is used either alone or in combination with the other hand during typing.
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validated in unaffected controls and PD patients of Stage I and II with scores ≤ 2 in UPDRS items of interest. • Measurement takes place when the subject is typing >40 characters.

9 Slowness of movement tracking with wrist accelerometry

9.1 Background and objectives

The background was briefly described in the previous section (Section 8.1). This section is centred on the implementation of dBMs of slowness of movement from wrist accelerometry data and extends the work of Mahadevan et al. (2020).

9.2 Methods

9.2.1 Datasets

The Verily Study Watch dataset, including, among others, all-day accelerometer (sampling rate 100Hz) data from PwPDs, persons at risk of PD, and HCs for almost two years, was the core dataset used to implement and validate the dBM. The dataset is detailed in Section 5.2.1

Table 25 contains the key clinico-demographic characteristics for the participants with digital measurements and at least one MDS-UPDRS Part III assessment that were used in the present analysis. While over one year of data are available on average for every participant, in this analysis we used six (6) days of data that were collected following an MDS-UPDRS clinical assessment.

Table 25 Demographic and clinical characteristics of Verily Study Watch subset used for the development of the wrist accelerometry-based dBM of slowness of movement. N.A.: not applicable.

Characteristics	PD	Persons at risk	Health Controls
n (total n = 314)	146	136	32
Demographics			
Females	58	87	14
Males	88	49	18
Age (yrs)			
<50	5	2	3
50-59	22	42	4
60-69	64	63	13
70-79	47	27	7
80-89	7	2	5
>90	1	0	0
Clinical characteristics			
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	5.78 (2.45)	N.A.	N.A.
Avg. MDS-UPDRS Part III score (std)	27.9 (12.8)	3.85 (6.4)	3.16 (3.88)

We also used the Capture-24 dataset, detailed in Section 7.2.1, to develop a gait-specific detector, which is a variation of the human action recognition model presented in Section 7, tailored to the needs of the present dBM implementation.

9.2.2 Data pre-processing

The present dBM implementation uses only 3-axis wrist accelerometer data. Each 3-axis accelerometer signal was segmented into continuous non-overlapping 5-s windows with any possible gap between two samples being less than 5 s. Each 5-s segment was resampled to 25 Hz to be consistent with the sampling rate of the smartwatch⁸ that is being used in the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical studies.

⁸ Garmin Vivoactive 5 - <https://www.garmin.com/en-IE/p/1057989>

9.2.3 Digital biomarkers

The implementation detailed here is an extension of the algorithm proposed by Mahadevan et al. (2020). **Figure 27** illustrates the high-level components of the algorithm. For a given accelerometer signal, pre-processed 5-s accelerometer segments are given as input to a hand movement classifier. If hand movement is detected, the segment is processed by a gait classifier. If gait is detected, the segment is further processed by an estimator of slowness of movement that outputs a numerical score that quantifies slowness of movement. The different blocks of the pipeline are detailed in the next sections.

Figure 27 Pipeline for slowness of movement assessment from wrist accelerometry.

Hand movement classifier

A heuristic method proposed is used to detect hand movement. For each 5-s segment, the signal vector magnitude ($\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$) is computed to eliminate the dependence on device orientation. Then, the magnitude is filtered using a 6th-order low-pass Butterworth filter with a cut-off frequency of 3 Hz to reduce noise attributed to the hand tremor and a rolling coefficient of variation ($c_v = \mu/\sigma$, where μ is the mean and σ the standard deviation) is calculated by sliding a 1-s window. The segment is considered to contain hand movement if the coefficient is $c_v > 0.01$. From the resulting binary signal, the 5-s segment was considered to contain hand move.

Gait classifier

For gait detection, two distinct models were trained and evaluated to classify gait and non-gait periods. A *magnitude-based model* that relies solely on signal vector magnitude-related features extracted from the 3-axis accelerometer signal, such as magnitude's higher-order (>2) statistics, signal autocorrelation and dominant frequency, and a *multi-axis model* that uses a combination of features derived from the individual three axes and signal vector magnitude features.

The labelled accelerometer data of the Capture-24 dataset (151 participants) were used for training the gait detection models. A LightGBM classifier was employed in both cases, and a nested cross-validation scheme was used to evaluate performance and perform hyperparameter tuning. For the outer fold of the nested cross-validation, we employed a Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) scheme, while for the inner fold, used for hyperparameter tuning, we adopted a k-fold approach.

Figure 28 provides the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves and areas under the ROC curve (AUC) for the two models, derived with the LOSO scheme. Although the multi-axis model (AUC 0.83) slightly outperforms the magnitude-based model (AUC 0.79), we selected the latter since it is device orientation-agnostic. As the detection of non-gait periods is of interest in this pipeline, the decision threshold probability (gait versus non-gait period) was set to 0.70 for maximising specificity based on the ROC analysis.

Figure 28 ROC curves and AUCs of the two types of models developed for gait classification.

In the pipeline, for each 5-s window that hand movement was detected, the signal is band-passed filtered (4th order, Butterworth filter) in the range of 0.25 – 3.00 Hz to isolate the frequency band associated with gait. Feature extraction is performed to the resulting signal, and the resulting features are fed to the gait detector that classifies the segment as a gait or non-gait period.

Slowness of movement estimator

Slowness of movement is estimated in 30-s intervals where hand movement is present and do not correspond to gait periods. The presence of movement and lack of gait are based on the classification of the individual 5-s segments included in the interval, as illustrated in **Figure 29**. If the majority of the classified 5-s windows within a 30-s interval indicate hand movement and no gait, that 30-s interval is retained for slowness of movement estimation.

For each retained 30-s interval, the features present on **Table 26** are extracted for the 5-s windows classified as having hand movement and no gait.

Table 26 Features extracted in each 5-s window for gait classifier

Feature Name	Description
Root mean square	Root mean square (RMS) of the signal data along the x, y, and z axes and the signal magnitude
Smoothness	Scaled mean squared jerk (smoothness) of the signal along the x, y, and z axes and the magnitude (Hogan et al., 2009)
Peak Acceleration	Maximum absolute value along the x, y, and z axes and the magnitude
Range of Motion	$max - min$ along the x, y, and z axes, and the magnitude
Signal Entropy	Shannon entropy of the signal data along the x, y, and z axes and the magnitude

Features from the 5-s windows are aggregated over a 10-minute period by calculating standard deviation, median and the 75th percentile values for x, y, z, and magnitude.

Figure 29 Time-wise classification of hand movement and gait presence over a 10-min period of slowness of movement estimation. Slowness of movement features are extracted only for 5-s windows classified as having hand movement and absence of gait in 30-s valid intervals (with hand movement and absence of gait based on majority voting on classifications of constituent 5-s windows).

To develop a score indicative of the severity of slowness of movement, we trained regression models with the aggregated features over 10-min periods to predict two different clinical measurements of slowness of movement:

1. A “Slowness of movement” composite score as the sum of MDS-UPDRS a) averaged (left and right) upper limb rigidity item scores (items 3.3b, 3.3c), b) averaged hand pronation-supination item scores (items 3.6a, 3.6b), and c) global spontaneity of movement item score (item 3.14)
2. The global spontaneity of movement score (item 3.14)

The aforementioned targets were selected as they are more likely to be represented by wrist acceleration. Averaged upper limb scores were used as the information about the hand wearing the accelerometer device was unavailable.

9.3 Results

9.3.1 Sample characteristics

Following the removal of participants who did not have any MDS-UPDRS assessment in the ON state (N=4), we used the available data from 310 participants (143 PwPDs / 32 HCs / 135 persons at risk) for training and validation of the slowness of movement estimator. More specifically, we used total 533 MDS-UPDRS assessments along with the accelerometer signals for up to 6 days after the assessment.

9.3.2 Validation of slowness of movement estimator

LightGBM regressors were trained and tested under a LOSO scheme. Certain subjects had more than one MDS-UPDRS Part III clinical assessment. Therefore, for a given subject, the features of slowness of movement features were labelled with the clinical scores of the closest MDS-UPDRS assessment. Spearman’s rank correlation was used to evaluate the association of the estimated digital scores (dBMs) of slowness of movement with the respective clinical items and composite scores. To further assess the dBMs’ diagnostic value, pairwise

comparisons were performed across the four emerging symptom severity levels, using the Mann-Whitney-U test with Bonferroni adjustment for multiple comparisons.

9.3.3 Selection of digital biomarkers

Table 27 presents the Spearman correlation coefficients (r) between the estimated digital scores of slowness of movement and the associated clinical scores. Moderate to strong, significant associations ($r = 0.66, p < 0.05$) are observed for both. **Figure 30** and **Figure 31** illustrate the distributions of the estimated digital scores grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement score and the global spontaneity of movement score (Item 3.14), respectively. For the case of the composite score, pairwise comparisons show that digital scores differ significantly between all severity groups (0 vs [1-3]: $p = 5.711e - 14, U = 8.120e + 03$, [1-3] vs [3-5]: $p = 1.229e - 08, U = 2.996e + 03$, [3-5] vs [5-8]: $p = 5.328e - 03, U = 1.790e + 03$). For the case of the global spontaneity of movement, significant differences are observed for all pairwise comparisons (0 vs 1: $p = 2.888e - 22, U = 6.039e + 03$, 1 vs 2: $p = 1.815e - 03, U = 3.668e + 03$) except for the case of severity scores 2 vs. 3 ($p = 1.200e - 01, U = 1.331e + 03$).

Table 27 Results for the two models train to estimate bradykinesia

Slowness of movement estimator target	Spearman coefficient r (significance)
Slowness of movement composite score	0.66 ($p < 0.05$)
Global spontaneity of movement score	0.66 ($p < 0.05$)

Figure 30 Distributions of the estimated digital scores grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the composite MDS-UPDRS slowness of movement score. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers $\equiv 1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$, ** $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$.

Figure 31 Distributions of the estimated digital scores grouped by the clinical severity of motor impairment based on the MDS-UPDRS Item 3.14 (Global spontaneity of movement) score. Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers \equiv $1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 0.0001$, ** $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$, ns not significant.

9.4 Discussion

9.4.1 Interpretation

We implemented and evaluated a slowness of movement assessment pipeline based on wrist accelerometer data by extending the work of Mahadevan et al. (2020). Both digital scores of slowness of movement presented a moderate to high correlation with the associated clinical scores, showing that they are indicative of symptom severity. Further analysis confirmed the diagnostic value of the digital scores in identifying different clinical severity levels. For the time being, the slowness of movement estimator developed based on the composite clinical score slightly outperforms the digital score developed based on the rating of the global spontaneity of movement in terms of diagnostic value, pending further validation.

9.4.2 Limitations

Key limitations of the analysis are that we have not validated the approach on an external dataset and that we have used averaged upper limb clinical scores as targets due to the lack of information regarding the hand wearing the accelerometer device. We aim to mitigate those limitations by using the data from the dBM-DEV study of the project, as well as the extended Verily Study dataset and the MJFF-LRS dataset. Other limitations are that we have not investigated the effect of age, sex, and body-mass index, which are known covariates of acceleration, and that the impact of medication and the intra-day fluctuations of the score have not been scrutinised. We plan to investigate the effect of covariates and the intra-day changes of the score in the next phase of the project, leading to the final version of the dBMs.

9.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

In general, the implemented wrist-accelerometry dBM of slowness of movement can be used for continuous monitoring in daily life. In the context of the AI-PROGNOSIS, the digital score and/or its constituent features are planned to be used as input to the PD risk and progression predictive models.

9.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Mobility
Concept(s) of interest	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Slowness of upper limb movement 2. Global spontaneity of movement (slowness, hesitancy, small amplitude, and poverty of movement in general)
Measurement technology	Wrist-worn device with accelerometer sensor
Type of measurement	Passive
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital score of the severity of slowness of movement derived from three-axis wrist acceleration 2. Digital score of the severity of slowness and lack of spontaneity of movement derived from three-axis wrist acceleration
Validation	<p>Type: Real world</p> <p>Primary measures of validation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spearman correlation of digital score of slowness of movement with composite score computed as the sum of averaged upper limb rigidity (MDS-UPDRS items 3.3b, 3.3c), averaged hand pronation-supination (MDS-UPDRS items 3.6a, 3.6b), and global spontaneity of movement (MDS-UPDRS item 3.14) clinical scores 2. Spearman correlation of digital score of spontaneity of movement with global spontaneity of movement (MDS-UPDRS item 3.14) clinical score
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The accelerometer sensors capturing the data are reliable and sensitive enough • Wrist wearables are well tolerated by targeted users
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validated in unaffected controls and PD patients with an average (std) MDS-UPDRS Part III score of 27.9 (12.8) and average (std) disease onset of 5.78 (2.45) years. • Uses three-axis accelerometer data sampled at ≥ 25 Hz. • Measurement takes place when the subject is wearing the device, moves their hands, and is not walking.

10 Comprehensive motor function active assessment

10.1 Background and objectives

PD, as a neurodegenerative condition, is characterized by a progression that leads to increasing challenges with motor skills, including, but not limited to, issues with posture, balance, leg agility, and gait. The advent of digital tools for PD assessment contributes to the growing body of research that looks at how technology might monitor these challenges and improve the management of the condition. A systematic review of the use of digital tools to assess posture and balance can be found in “Section 2.3.8 Digital assessments of posture and balance” of Deliverable D2.3 “Initial report on domain review and datasets”.

Inexpensive sensors, such as cameras and smartphones hold promise for home-based monitoring, as highlighted by (Dias et al., 2020a,b). Recent advancements include the

development of intelligent motor assessment tools and depth camera-based systems (e.g., Microsoft Kinect) for differentiating PD stages and to capture body motion (Dias et al., 2020a-c; Dranca et al., 2018). Additionally, smartphone-based depth sensors and skeleton tracking in three-dimensional space, have shown promise, offering enhanced precision and accuracy in motion analysis (Abe et al., 2022). Video recording, coupled with pose estimation tools, such as AlphaPose (Fang et al., 2017), has also been utilized to extract human joint coordinates (Abe et al., 2022; Guo et al., 2021). However, to fully realize the potential of digital health solutions for PD management, continued research and collaboration in this sector are needed.

Building upon these technical developments, we aim to investigate and validate an approach for active balance and posture digital assessment in PwPD. The ultimate goal is to define new dBMs of posture and balance, by combining camera-based body tracking and a motor function test that is simple to set up and easy to use. For designing the test, we focused on relevant MDS-UPDRS (Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale) Part III items that are essential for assessing gross motor function, such as leg agility, rising from a chair, walking, and posture. These clinical assessment items are standardised markers of posture and balance that constitute key motor aspects of PD (Jankovic, 2008). By designing a Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT), that makes use of modified MDS-UPDRS-related motor tasks, and combining it with continuous video-based tracking, we aim to obtain deeper, yet clinically relevant, insights into the motor aspects assessed by these items.

The CMFT was designed with two primary goals in mind: a) to ensure it can be easily set up in a home, work, or hospital environment using only a smartphone, a stand, and a chair, and b) to make it acceptable and easy for PwPD to perform (or with the recommended support of caregiver). The CMFT was developed with data collected from a small cohort of PwPD and will be further refined and validated in the dBM-DEV study of the project.

10.2 Methods

The CMFT focuses on the automated assessment of specific items of the MDS-UPDRS Part III, namely “item 3.8” (leg agility), “item 3.9” (arising from chair), “item 3.10” (gait), and “item 3.13” (posture), shown in **Figure 32**.

To simplify the capturing procedure and facilitate the execution of the test, users are instructed to perform the movements underlying the MDS-UPDRS items of interest in a sequence, one after the other. The MDS-UPDRS guidelines were followed as closely as possible; however, some minor changes were inevitably required, as in the self-test case, the user may have to capture the video alone, without support from a carer or physician. The following outline the four movements encompassed in the CMFT:

- Leg agility (item 3.8): Initially, the patient should sit in a straight-backed chair with arms and have both feet comfortably on the floor. The patient should then raise and stomp each foot (first the right foot and then the left) on the ground 10 times as high and as fast as possible.
- Arising from chair (item 3.9): Then the user should cross their arms across the chest and try to stand up. If the user does not succeed, they should attempt again up to two times, and if they are still unsuccessful, they can try to push off using their hands on the arms of the chair.
- Posture (item 3.13): After the patient stands up, s/he is asked to stand still for 5 seconds, so that their posture can be assessed.

- Gait (item 3.10): After completing the posture task, the patient should take 3 steps away from the chair, then turn around and return towards the chair, taking again 3 steps. Although the original MDS-UPDRS test requires the patient to walk for at least 10m, this test was adapted due to the limited field of view of the camera in the test set-up.

Figure 32 Camera recordings from CMFT corresponding to four MDS-UPDRS items for assessing motor skills: (a) item 3.8 (Leg agility), (b) item 3.9 (Arising from chair), (c) item 3.13 (Posture), (d) item 3.10 (Gait).

10.2.1 Datasets

To kick-start the development of the CMFT, a cohort of 32 PD patients were recruited in the Papanikolaou General Hospital of Thessaloniki (Thessaloniki, Greece) and in the Northern Greece Parkinson's Disease Association (Thessaloniki, Greece). The study was approved by the scientific board of the Papanikolaou General Hospital of Thessaloniki (Appendix II – S.1). All participants provided written informed consent (Appendix II – S.2) and voluntarily participated in the study. Each participant performed the CMFT, while being recorded by a smartphone, either in the hospital or in the facilities of the association.

Per the protocol of the CMFT, the patient performed a standardised sequence of movements that simulate the corresponding MDS-UPDRS Part III: Motor Examination items 3.8 (Leg agility), 3.9 (Arising from chair), 3.13 (Posture) and 3.10 (Gait), with concurrent video recording from a smartphone fixed in a static position (using a tripod). The recording set-up is depicted in **Figure 33**. In order to maximise the field of view, we placed the camera at a 1-m distance with an initial anterolateral view of the participant (approximately 45° between the camera axis and the participant).

Figure 33 Video capture set-up for collecting CMF development data.

Fifteen recordings were discarded due to various reasons, including, but not limited to, wrong camera setup, patient moving outside the field of view, and patient experiencing freezing of gait during the recording. Recordings of 17 participants (demographics are presented in **Table 28**) were used in the subsequent analysis. The study did not involve any unaffected controls. Each movement in the video recordings were rated/annotated by two independent neurologists of the Papanikolaou hospital annotators based on the MDS-UPDRS items of interest (a 0-4 score for each item). Annotations ranged between 0-3 per item; no movement was rated as 4 (severe); scoring distributions are also presented in **Table 28**.

Table 28 Demographics of the participants in the CMFT development study.

Demographics	PD Patients
Recordings n	17
Women # (%)	5 (30%)
Avg. age in years (std)	71.4 (5.02)
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	17.4 (8.9)
Men # (%)	12 (70%)
Avg. age in years (std)	72.14 (8.93)
Avg. disease onset in years (std)	9.25 (3.69)
Clinical scoring characteristics	Histograms of scores (0/1/2/3)
Item 3.8	0/3/9/5
Item 3.9	7/5/2/3

Item 3.13	1/5/7/4
Item 3.10	2/9/5/1

10.2.2 Data pre-processing

An overview of the CMFT assessment approach is presented in **Figure 34** and is further elaborated in the next sub-Section (Section 10.2.3).

Figure 34 Overview of the data processing pipeline of the CMFT.

The video recording of each participant was split into frames and the 3-D body pose landmarks in each frame were detected using the MediaPipe Pose Landmarker. Landmarks are further processed to computed time series of a set of angles that are relevant to each MDS-UPDRS item, such as the left/right knee angle. The time series for each item is then pre-processed and used to compute a set of movement features that potentially correlate with the corresponding clinical score.

The video recordings were captured at a rate of 30 frames per second (fps). To reduce noise effects (e.g., MediaPipe pose detection errors), a pre-processing step, each time series was filtered using a Butterworth low-pass filter to remove high frequencies. An 8Hz cut-off value was selected, followed by the subtraction of the mean value (DC term) for normalisation purposes. As an alternative, a Butterworth bandpass filter in the frequency range (0.25Hz-8Hz) was tested, which leads to very similar performance.

Figure 35 Mediapipe body landmark locations⁹

⁹ Image acquired from from https://ai.google.dev/edge/mediapipe/solutions/vision/pose_landmarker
PU – Public

10.2.3 Digital biomarkers

Movement segmentation

CMFT combines the associated movements of the aforementioned MDS-UPDRS items in a sequence with the following order: right foot stomping (item 3.8R), left foot stomping (item 3.8L), arising from a chair (item 3.9), standing still for 5 s (item 3.13), 3 steps forward (adjusted item 3.10F), turn (item 3.10T), take 3 steps returning to the chair (adjusted item 3.10B).

As the movements are performed in unified sequence, a segmentation step is introduced to identify each movement's first and last frame from the continuous sequence of detected body landmarks. The algorithm developed is based on the x and y coordinates of the detected landmarks and will be briefly described below; the reader should refer to **Figure 36**:

- a) Check the feet orientation: $x_{32} - x_{30}$ for right foot and $x_{31} - x_{29}$ for left foot (see **Figure 35**) at each frame. Both differences should be negative at T_0 (assuming that the chair is positioned as in **Figure 33** and should remain negative until user turns (T_{turn}) during the gait phase, when both differences become positive. Finally, these differences become once again negative when the user turns again to sit on the chair, signalling the end of recording (T_{end}) of the CMFT. If these time instants (T_{turn} , T_{end}) cannot be properly identified during the test, the test is aborted and an error message is automatically generated, informing the user to repeat the whole test.
- b) Segment the (T_{start} , T_{turn}) time period into three phases (sitting, transition, standing) using center_y (y-coordinate of the midpoint between hips: $(y_{24} + y_{23})/2$) time series and applying binary segmentation (Fryzlewicz, 2014) implemented in the raptures Python library (Truong, 2020). The transition period (r_{st} , r_{end}) corresponds to the movement of arising from the chair (item **3.9**).
- c) Segment the sitting phase to two parts (stomping, keeping still) using the y-coordinate of right ankle rankle_y (y_{29}) sequence and applying binary segmentation. The stomping part corresponds to the right foot stomping (item **3.8R**),
- d) Segment the sitting phase to two parts (stomping, keeping still) using the y-coordinate of left ankle rankle_y (y_{27}) sequence and applying binary segmentation. The stomping part corresponds to the left foot stomping (item **3.8L**),
- e) Update the turning time T_{turn} as the argmax (location of maximum) of center_x (midpoint between hips: $(x_{24} + x_{23})/2$) value in the standing phase. Stepping back to the chair (item **3.10B**) can be defined as the segment between (T_{turn} , T_{end}).
- f) Segment the center_x sequence in the standing phase (T_{r_end} , T_{turn}) to two phases (keeping still, gait forward) using binary segmentation. The "keeping still" period (T_{r_end} , T_{g_start}) corresponds to motion item **3.13**(posture), while the "gait forward" period (T_{g_start} , T_{turn}) corresponds to **3.10F**(forward).

Figure 36 Time series of x and y coordinates of the detected landmarks of a user (with ID=11 and clinical UPDRS scores of the performed items 1,0,0,1,2,2, respectively) that performed the CMFT movement sequence; ($center_x$, $center_y$) are the coordinates of the midpoint between hips (landmarks 23 and 24).

Feature extraction

As already mentioned, we opted for features based exclusively on joint angles (instead of displacements), to reduce the dependency on factors such as a) camera angle, b) distance of patient from the camera, and c) human body size/shape variations. Hence, for each movement segment (corresponding to an MDS-UPDRS item), a set of relevant joint angles was identified and measured, as shown in **Table 29**.

Table 29 Joint angles of interest for each movement of the CMFT (and associated MDS-UPDRS item).

Item	Relevant joint angle(s)
Right foot stamping (3.8R)	KNEE_R (landmark 26)
Left foot stamping (3.8L)	KNEE_L (landmark 25)
Arising from chair (3.9)	HIP_C (angle formed at midpoint between hips (landmarks 23,24) with respect to a) the midpoint of shoulders (landmarks 11,12) and b) midpoint of knees (landmarks 25,26)
Posture (3.13)	
Walking forward (3.10F), walking back (3.10B)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BETWEEN_LEGS (angle formed at midpoint between hips (landmarks 23,24) with respect to: a) right knee (landmark 26) and b) left knee (landmarks 25)), SHOULDER_L (landmark 11): angle formed with respect to: a) left elbow (landmark 13) and b) left hip point (landmark 23), SHOULDER_R (landmark 12): angle formed with respect to: a) right elbow (landmark 14) and b) right hip point (landmark 24)

For each angle time series (signal), a set of 31 features are computed (**Table 30**). Specifically, the minimum (min) value, maximum (max) value, mean value, standard deviation, median, range (maximum value – minimum value), and interquartile range (IQR) are computed from the angle time series, its first derivative (angular speed), and third derivative (acceleration).

Then, inspired by the features used in (Mahadevan, 2019), five (5) additional features are obtained from the power spectrum of the angle time series, i.e., i) the dominant frequency (value of the frequency with the highest magnitude in the normalized power spectrum of the signal), ii) the magnitude at the dominant frequency, iii) the dominant frequency ratio (ratio of energy in the dominant frequency component to the total energy of the signal), iv) spectral entropy i.e. estimation of the Shannon entropy of the probability mass function of the power spectrum of the signal, and v) the spectral flatness (calculated by dividing the geometric mean of the power spectrum by the arithmetic mean of the power spectrum). Finally, five (5) additional features related to signal complexity are also computed (Mahadevan, 2019, Supplementary material), i.e., i) the root mean square (RMS) value, ii) the signal entropy (estimating Shannon entropy of the probability mass function), iii) mean squared jerk (i.e., rate of signal change, scaled by the maximum value of the angle and duration), iv) the interquartile range of the angle autocovariance, and v) the mean cross rate, i.e. number of times the signal changed from positive to negative, normalized by the total signal length.

In this way, $F=31$ candidate features are defined for each item, except gait items (3.10F, 3.10B), where three angle time series (see **Table 30**) are used, so $F=3*31=93$.

Table 30 Features (31 in total) that are computed from each angle time series

Category	Features
Angle features (7)	Min, max, mean, standard deviation (SD), median, interquartile range (IQR), range (i.e., max-min)
Speed features (7)	Min, max, mean, standard deviation (SD), median, interquartile range (IQR), range (i.e., max-min)
Acceleration features (7)	Min, max, mean, standard deviation (SD), median, interquartile range (IQR), range (i.e., max-min)
Frequency domain features (3)	Dominant frequency, dominant frequency magnitude, dominant frequency ratio
Spectral features (2)	Spectral entropy, spectral flatness (2)
Additional angle features (5)	signal_rms (root mean square), signal_entropy, jerk_metric, iqr_of_autocovariance, mean_cross_rate

Machine learning and MDS-UPDRS item score classification

We trained ML models to predict the MDS-UPDRS item scores based on the feature vectors computed for each associated movement. Five classifiers were employed, i.e., K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), principal component analysis (PCA) in combination with KNN, and supervised PCA (sPCA) (Ghojogh, 2019) in combination with KNN.

Following the proposed methodology (**Figure 34**), an additional feature selection step was used to further improve performance. Specifically, for each item, we measured the correlation of each extracted feature with the corresponding clinical score. We sorted the results to define a subset of $N < F$ features with the largest correlations. The hyperparameter N was experimentally selected so as to maximise performance: $N=3$ for items 3.8, 3.9 and 3.13 and $N=9$ for gait items (3.10F and 3.10B).

Validation of ML classifiers was performed using the Leave-One-Sample-Out cross-validation approach, and relevant metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 scores) were computed.

10.3 Results

10.3.1 Selection of digital biomarkers

The main goal of this work was to design and evaluate a digital equivalent (dBM) of the specific MDS-UPDRS item scores that is based on (angle-based) features derived from body tracking and machine learning.

Features kept after the feature selection step for each item along with the corresponding Pearson correlation and significance, are presented in **Table 31**. In all cases and ML classifiers used, experimental results showed that the use of the feature selection step results in significant performance gains.

Table 31 Features with maximum correlation kept for each motion item

Item	Feature	Pearson Correlation	Significance
3.8R	angle_range	-0.76	0.0003672
	angle_min	0.74	0.0006307
	speed_min	0.74	0.0006759
3.8L	speed_stdev	-0.83	0.0000399
	speed_range	-0.81	0.0000792
	speed_quartile_range	-0.78	0.0002511
3.9	angle_filtered_dom_freq_value	-0.81	0.0000786
	speed_mean	0.78	0.0002367
	angle_filtered_mean_cross_rate	-0.77	0.0003091
3.13	accel_quartile_range	0.67	0.0041927
	speed_quartile_range	0.63	0.0095442
	accel_stdev	0.57	0.0212938
3.10F	thigh_angle_filtered_signal_entropy	-0.62	0.0084723
	thigh_speed_median	-0.51	0.0384020
	thigh_angle_filtered_mean_cross_rate	-0.46	0.0614431
	armR_angle_filtered_iqr_of_autocovariance	0.46	0.0631905
	thigh_angle_filtered_spectral_entropy	-0.44	0.0753334
	armL_angle_filtered_signal_entropy	0.44	0.0803436
	thigh_angle_filtered_dom_freq_ratio	0.42	0.0912011
	thigh_angle_filtered_dom_freq_magnitude	0.4	0.1132769
	thigh_angle_min	0.39	0.1193274
3.10B	thigh_speed_stdev	-0.75	0.0005115
	thigh_speed_quartile_range	-0.74	0.0006010
	thigh_angle_filtered_dom_freq_value	-0.73	0.0009412
	armR_angle_filtered_iqr_of_autocovariance	-0.66	0.0039845
	thigh_angle_quartile_range	-0.56	0.0206037
	thigh_angle_filtered_mean_cross_rate	-0.54	0.0254918

	thigh_angle_min	0.52	0.0310426
	thigh_angle_filtered_iqr_of_autocovariance	-0.51	0.0357749
	thigh_speed_range	-0.51	0.0380953

As seen, in many cases, feature selection is in line with corresponding clinical assessment criteria, e.g., in the case of 3.8 (leg agility), speed or angle variations are important features used by physicians for the clinical assessment.

Table 32 presents the accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for all assessment items and ML classifiers obtained using the LOSO cross-validation scheme. Best results for most items are obtained using the KNN (Nearest Neighbour) approach (where the hyperparameter $K=3$ was found to yield optimal results in most cases) and/or the sPCA+KNN approach. Classification performance in some cases, e.g. MDS-UPDRS items 3.10F (gait), was less satisfactory, possibly due to complexity of the associated movement that may require more representative features to be used.

Table 32 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall and F1 scores for each MDS-UPDRS item of interest and all classifiers derived from LOSO validation. Best F1 scores for each item are shown in bold.

3.8R	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.71	0.64	0.71	0.66
SVM	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65
RF	0.65	0.53	0.65	0.58
PCA+KNN	0.65	0.69	0.65	0.67
sPCA+KNN	0.71	0.74	0.71	0.72
3.8L	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.76	0.77	0.76	0.76
SVM	0.71	0.72	0.71	0.69
RF	0.71	0.70	0.71	0.70
PCA+KNN	0.76	0.77	0.76	0.76
sPCA+KNN	0.76	0.77	0.76	0.76
3.9	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.76	0.75	0.76	0.75
SVM	0.76	0.73	0.76	0.74
RF	0.71	0.66	0.71	0.68
PCA+KNN	0.71	0.65	0.71	0.68
sPCA+KNN	0.71	0.65	0.71	0.68
3.13	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.81	0.82	0.81	0.81
SVM	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
RF	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
PCA+KNN	0.81	0.86	0.81	0.81
sPCA+KNN	0.81	0.82	0.81	0.81
3.10F	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.47	0.48	0.47	0.47

SVM	0.53	0.54	0.53	0.53
RF	0.59	0.55	0.59	0.56
PCA+KNN	0.53	0.67	0.53	0.54
sPCA+KNN	0.59	0.61	0.59	0.56
3.10B	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.70
SVM	0.71	0.59	0.71	0.64
RF	0.65	0.53	0.65	0.58
PCA+KNN	0.71	0.78	0.71	0.66
sPCA+KNN	0.65	0.62	0.65	0.63

10.3.2 Patient and public involvement

To design the mobile version of the CMFT that will be integrated with the AI-PROGNOSIS applications, a co-creation workshop was conducted. The CMFT aims to constitute an active digital assessment that will offer insights into key motor symptoms of PD (perceived usefulness) while being user-friendly for both persons with Parkinson’s disease (PwPD) and healthcare professionals (perceived ease of use), encouraging its regular use.

The primary goal of the co-creation session was to gather feedback from PwPD on the CMFT, addressing aspects such as usability, engagement, accessibility, and suggestions for improvement. By involving PwPD early in the design process, we aimed to align the CMFT more closely with their needs and expectations, improving its relevance and effectiveness. The session followed a structured format: (1) welcoming participants and outlining objectives, (2) introducing facilitators and experts, (3) inviting PwPD to share their experiences with mobile app assessments, (4) presenting an overview of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, (5) showcasing CMFT mock-ups (see **Figure 37**), (6) leading a panel discussion on the CMFT’s design and functionality, and (7) summarizing the session and next steps, followed by an online satisfaction questionnaire. During the mock-up presentation, the panel discussion was guided by questions based on Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis et al., 1989) constructs (see Appendix I):

Usability and perceived usefulness: *“How useful do you find the CMFT for assessing your motor function, particularly balance and posture, compared to traditional methods? Considering ease of navigation and clarity of instructions, how confident are you in using the CMFT effectively?”*

Ease of use and accessibility: *“How easy do you anticipate learning to use the CMFT, especially with Parkinson’s related motor difficulties in mind? Do you foresee any accessibility barriers hindering your ability to interact effectively with the CMFT?”*

User engagement-intention to use: *“How likely are you to incorporate the CMFT into your routine for motor function assessment? To what extent do you find the CMFT engaging compared to other assessment tools?”*

User engagement-attitude towards using: *“How do you perceive the overall user experience of the CMFT, and how does it influence your enthusiasm to use it?”*

The CMFT prototype presented during the co-creation session consists of several interactive screens designed to guide users through the motor assessment process (see **Figure 37**). These include:

- **Main Menu Screen:** This is the starting point of the CMFT, providing users with easy access to the test options and settings.
- **Set-up Instructions Screen:** This screen provides step-by-step instructions to guide users through the necessary preparations before beginning the motor test. It ensures that participants are properly positioned, have the necessary equipment (e.g., smartphone), and understand the setup requirements for optimal test performance.
- **Motor Test Instructions Screen:** On this screen, users are provided with detailed instructions on how to perform the specific movements required for the motor test. These instructions ensure that participants understand the motor tasks they need to perform, helping them to prepare mentally and physically before starting the test.
- **Countdown Screen:** Before the test begins, the Countdown Screen displays a brief countdown to prepare users for the upcoming motor assessment. This screen helps build anticipation and ensures that participants are ready for the start of the test.
- **Motor Test Recording Screen:** This is the main functional screen during the test, where the movements are recorded. It tracks the user's performance in real-time, providing visual feedback and capturing the necessary data for evaluation.

Figure 37 Mock-ups of the Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) prototype presented during the co-creation session, including: 1) Main menu screen, 2) Set-up instructions screen, 3) Motor test instructions screen, 4) Countdown screen, and 5) Motor test recording

Sampling and recruitment

Purposive sampling was used to select participants for the co-creation session, focusing on individuals aged 18 or older with a confirmed PD diagnosis, able to communicate in English via an online platform. Researchers and clinical/technical experts from the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium also participated to provide diverse insights. Participation was voluntary, with no compensation, and informed consent was obtained.

Data collection

The co-creation session was conducted online in April 2024 via Microsoft Teams (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA), involving 15 participants: two facilitators, one clinical researcher specializing in PD, three technical experts (with expertise in software development and/or technology implementation), three senior AI researchers, and six PwPD (see **Table 29**). The PwPD participants had a mean age of 49.83 ± 9.22 years (two females) and an average time since diagnosis of 2.40 ± 0.55 years, with 50% demonstrating advanced technology literacy.

The technical experts had a mean age of 48.00 ± 8.54 years, with one female participant. The clinical researcher, a male, contributed over 15 years of clinical experience specifically in Parkinson's care. In particular, PwPD participants were affiliated with the Center of Excellence in Parkinson's Research and Clinical Care and were also members of the Community for Research Involvement and Support by Persons with Parkinson's disease (CRISP) of AI-PROGNOSIS partner King's College London (KCL) in the UK. Audio recordings of the session were transcribed and pseudonymised for confidentiality. A structured guide with seven key questions explored participants' opinions on the design of the CMFT, with a focus on balance and posture. Mock-ups of the CMFT were presented to aid the discussion (**Figure 33**). The session lasted 70 min, followed by a satisfaction questionnaire shared via Google Forms (Google LLC, Mountain View, CA).

Data validation and analysis

Participants' educational backgrounds were classified using the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED)⁸. Two independent researchers analysed the qualitative data using thematic analysis, generating codes, themes, and sub-themes. Agreement on coding was measured with Cohen's kappa⁹ to ensure consistency. Direct quotations from participants were used to support the findings.

Table 33 Demographic characteristics of the involved participants; PwPD: People with Parkinson's disease.

Participants	Characteristics	Value
PwPD (n = 6)	Age	49.83 ± 9.22 years
	Sex (% males)	66.67 %
	PD duration	2.40 ± 0.55 years
	Education level	Bachelor's or Equivalent (66.67 %)
		Master's or Equivalent (16.67 %)
		Doctoral or Equivalent (16.67 %)
	Technology literacy	Basic (16.67 %)
		Intermediate (33.33 %)
	Advanced (50 %)	
Researchers (n = 5)	Age	39.80 ± 11.10 years
	Sex (% males)	60.00 %
	Years working in the field	12.20 ± 7.43 years
Clinical Expert (n = 1)	Age	42 years
	Sex (% males)	Male
	Years working in the field	15 years
Technical Experts (n = 3)	Age	48.00 ± 8.54 years
	Sex (% males)	66.67 %
	Years working in the field	19.33 ± 3.06 years

Main findings and discussion

The main findings are epitomised in Error! Reference source not found.. Three main themes emerged from the thematic analysis, namely: Usability (Theme 1), Ease of Use and Accessibility (Theme 2), and User Engagement (Theme 3). From the main themes identified in the session, various subthemes were derived to further explore the discussions. The level of agreement of the researchers that identified subthemes (Cohen's kappa) was 0.93, indicating an almost perfect agreement. At the points of doubt, a discussion between the researchers resulted in a reworked text, arriving to a perfect agreement across all subthemes.

Figure 38 Overview of the main findings derived from the thematic analysis.

Overall, the CMFT was perceived as clear and comfortable to use, with both written content and video demonstrations being considered helpful. The perceived psychological burden of long-term symptom tracking was considered an additional challenge. Participants found the concept of regular symptom tracking feasible and preferred conducting assessments at home for convenience. Several participants acknowledged the practicality and time efficiency of the CMFT and expressed willingness to engage in regular assessment using this tool. Data protection and ethical considerations were discussed, which further underlined the importance of transparency and privacy. The main findings for each identified theme are briefly described below; PwPD: Person with PD, CE: Clinical Expert, R: Researcher, TE: Technical Expert.

Usability (Theme 1). Most participants found the CMFT straightforward and easy to use. They reported feeling comfortable performing this assessment, which was considered useful for symptom monitoring between clinical appointments. Providing both written content and video demonstrations was considered helpful for understanding how to perform the CMFT. However, it was suggested that written instructions should be clearer. One participant highlighted the need of clarifying the intended movement speed for each component of the motor tests. For example, while the leg agility test should be performed as fast as possible, patients should use a comfortable speed during the sit-to-stand, gait, and posture tests. Nonetheless, the value of using both video and written instructions was recognized, as follows:

“I agree that the videos are very useful because I thought there was slight ambiguity in the written text and in the third frame... For me, it becomes very clear what to do when I see the video” (PwPD#5). Moreover, the CE noted, *“It can be seen as a complementary tool to clinicians” (CE).* This perspective is aligned with the recognized role of digital technology for PD, by supporting clinical decision-making, improving patient outcomes and satisfaction, and thereby enhancing the quality of care (Espay et al., 2016).

Ease of use and Accessibility (Theme 2). Participants reported few practical issues with the CMFT, emphasising the importance of clear, standardised instructions and technical feedback. During the discussion, proper smartphone placement and camera positioning were considered crucial for increased accessibility, particularly for patients with severe symptoms. For instance, having a smartphone stand/support was considered useful for better camera adjustment considering at-home assessments. In fact, the relevance of addressing these practical considerations is consistent with principles of user-centred design in mobile health (mHealth) apps (Espay et al., 2019). In this vein, one PwPD anticipated some difficulties for PwPD at later disease stages or with more severe motor and/or cognitive impairments to perform the CMFT in a home setting, as follows: *“I was just wondering how useful this would be for people in later stages of the disease. If you’re in the later stages of the disease, when standing up, there could be balance issues, there could also be issues understanding the instructions.” (PwPD#4).* In this context, the following was added by a researcher: *“For those cases, the CMFT can be performed with or without the caregiver or family member” (R#1).* This highlights the importance of caregivers and healthcare providers in supporting PwPD to improve long-term compliance with digital assessment tools (Espay et al., 2019).

User engagement (Theme 3). All participants expressed willingness to use the CMFT regularly due to its feasibility, convenience, and time efficiency, especially if real-time updates are provided. All patients found the concept of regular assessment every 2-3 weeks through the CMFT both feasible and engaging. Most preferred to do the assessment at home for convenience, such as saving time on travel. One patient remarked, *“For me, doing it at home would make life a lot easier. What I would find engaging is having not necessarily real-time feedback but regular updates” (PwPD#6).* In addition, a researcher added insights on future developments, as follows: *“Feedback is also a part of the whole AI-PROGNOSIS app, so in the future, there will be a discussion on how we give the feedback to the patients. Later on, it will be defined which part of the information is given to the patients, to the doctors, and to the caregivers” (R#1).* When prompted to share their insights on using the app, participants considered the CMFT practical and time-efficient (2-3 minutes). One PwPD noted, *“This would definitely be the sort of thing I like to do! It does seem very straightforward and something that wouldn’t take up too much time. So that makes it something that I could see myself doing” (PwPD#1).* In general, participants’ positive remarks on aspects related to usability, accessibility, and engagement potential are in line with the theoretical constructs of the TAM model, namely perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, which determine user acceptance of health technologies (Davis et al., 1989). During the session, discussions have also arisen regarding the psychological impact of long-term symptom monitoring. In fact, this practice can be challenging for some people, who may feel overwhelmed by regularly confronting symptom progression or fluctuation; however, healthcare professionals can help address these concerns by providing support, guidance, and resources (Johnsson et al., 2023). Moreover, data protection and ethical issues were discussed, such as transparency and privacy aspects. To address these concerns, it was clarified that in the final implementation of the CMFT, only the motion tracking data will be stored and not the video recording: *“Just to clarify, what we capture are the nodes (landmarks) of the body. These are the data used to extract the biomarkers of assessment and not the real video, so there’s no*

information about personal characteristics or anything about yourself. There is no video going outside of your mobile phone” (TE#2). The CE confirmed that the app will ensure user consent, ethical considerations, and compliance with European data protection guidelines. In the same vein, WHO has emphasised that ethical considerations and human rights should be central to AI health technologies to ensure their positive impact (WHO, 2021).

Overall, the co-creation session provided valuable insights for enhancing the design of the CMFT that will be integrated with the AI-PROGNOSIS apps.

Co-creation evaluation feedback

Responses to the satisfaction questionnaire following the co-creation session, collected from 11 anonymous participants, aimed to evaluate overall satisfaction, and provide insights for enhancing future co-creation activities. The main findings are summarised below.

Overall satisfaction. The majority of the participants reported a very positive experience, with 45.5% indicating a high level of satisfaction and another 45.5% expressing satisfaction. Additionally, all participants expressed their willingness to attend future co-creation sessions. Participants appreciated the insights provided by PD patients to improve the design of the proposed CMFT. They valued the presentation of innovative aspects, such as objective techniques to assess motor skills related to posture and balance. Certain participants also expressed satisfaction in being involved in PD research that could benefit others and contribute to the development of an innovative mobile app. The simplicity and straightforwardness of the CMFT were specifically acknowledged.

Areas for improvement. Certain participants emphasised the importance of better planning the duration of the co-creation session and providing clarity regarding the future sessions and the specific aims of the app. There was some uncertainty about whether the app was intended for research data collection or algorithm development for predicting PD conditions. Suggestions for improvement included extending the session duration to allow for more in-depth discussion and providing regular feedback to keep stakeholders engaged. Clear, detailed instructions and visual representations were emphasised as necessary, particularly due to language barriers. One participant also suggested to include interactive demo materials to help convey what needs to be developed.

Overall, the collected feedback from all participants, including PwPD and technical/clinical experts, highlighted several concerns and suggestions for improving the proposed CMFT. To address these, the following actions will be implemented: i) extending future session duration for more in-depth discussions; ii) providing clearer instructions and visual representations to ensure patients’ full understanding of the proposed tests; and 3) incorporating regular feedback and eventual interactive materials to keep patients engaged. Moreover, it is our intention to continuously integrate stakeholder feedback and in parallel refine the algorithms for data collection towards the introduction of the CMFT in the dBM-DEV study.

10.4 Discussion

10.4.1 Interpretation

The proposed CMFT approach involves utilising smartphone-based video analysis to assess motor skills, in PwPD. It aims to offer insights into key motor symptoms of PD, while being easy to perform for both PD patients and healthcare professionals. In order design and validate the proposed approach, we organized a small-scale study using a cohort of 17 volunteer PD patients and captured videos of them performing a sequence of four items from the MDS-UPDRS motor tests. The main findings can be summarized as follows:

1. Extraction of body landmarks using the Google MediaPipe Pose Landmarker tool was seen to be highly efficient
2. A set of candidate angle, angular speed and angular acceleration features was selected. For each individual item, a feature selection approach was used to identify features that exhibit the highest correlation with the clinical scores. This approach resulted in significant performance gains, against the case where all candidate features are used.
3. Different ML classifiers were tested and optimized. The KNN classifier (also in combination with sPCA approach) was seen to yield satisfactory results for most items.
4. An automated movement segmentation approach to identify each individual item from a CMFT session was designed based on the implemented CMFT protocol. A preliminary evaluation in some of the available video recordings was encouraging, however further validation will be required within the next period of the project (also using results from the dBM-DEV study) to ensure that any errors can be identified.
5. Finally, a co-creation session was to gather feedback from PD patients and healthcare professionals regarding specific aspects of the CMFT, such as usability, engagement, accessibility, and suggestions for improvement. The findings of this session will be used to further optimize the CMFT approach during the next project period.

10.4.2 Limitations

At this point, a key limitation of the CMFT-derived dBMs is the small number of recordings (17 in total) on which the associated ML models were trained and tested. Despite the promising performance in predicting the clinical scores of certain MDS-UPDRS items of interest, further feature engineering, training, and evaluation is required using a larger set of annotated recordings. To this end, during the next project period, additional recordings be collected for developing purposes (in the context of the data collection study approved by the Papanikolaou General Hospital). Data collected with the CMFT mobile implementation within the dBM-DEV study will then be used for verifying the performance in real world conditions. For instance, any possible issues and limitations regarding the available processing power and output frame rate of smartphones to be used for CMFT will be identified and possible solutions/adjustments to the proposed approaches will be implemented. Similar modifications may be introduced regarding the proposed automated movement segmentation approach, for instance introducing data quality checks that will discard low quality recordings.

Finally, further research within Task 3.1, will be directed towards creating more explainable features based on Pose Landmark displacements (instead of angles). Such features, despite the need for additional normalization procedures, can provide further explainable information associated with the clinical evaluation, e.g., monitor amplitude changes during the leg agility test (item **3.8**). Similarly, the use of additional gait-specific features, such as step duration and swing phase duration (Di Biase, 2020), will also be considered to further improve performance for gait items.

In the long term, the proposed approach can also be further generalised for other MDS-UPDRS Part III: Motor Examination motion items, such as hand/finger movements (3.4-3.6), possibly using MediaPipe Hand landmark detection instead of Pose landmark detection.

10.4.3 Usability of the digital biomarkers in the context of current care

As mentioned above and supported by the findings of the co-creation session, CMFT has the potential to offer several advancements to PD patient care, facilitating regular and objective symptom tracking and allowing patients to conduct assessments at home. The co-creation session for the CMFT showcased extensive patient and public involvement, integrating

valuable feedback from PwPD to refine this digital assessment tool. The session's primary goals were to make the CMFT user-friendly for PwPD and to ensure it provided clinically relevant insights into key motor symptoms such as balance and posture. Usability, accessibility, and engagement were evaluated using the TAM framework, focusing on perceived ease of use and usefulness. Feedback emphasized the importance of clear instructions and the option for both written and video guidance, which many PwPD participants found helpful in reducing ambiguity. Discussions highlighted accessibility improvements, such as proper smartphone positioning and accommodations for advanced PD stages, including potential caregiver support. A thematic analysis identified three primary areas for enhancement: usability, ease of use and accessibility, and user engagement. PwPD participants valued the CMFT's feasibility, efficiency, and convenience for at-home use, emphasizing its practical benefits for routine assessments. They also preferred feedback on symptom progression, which could boost engagement and adherence. Ethical considerations regarding data protection were addressed, clarifying that only motion-tracking data (not personal video data) would be stored in alignment with EU data protection guidelines. This approach, supported by the WHO's guidance on ethical AI in health¹⁰, upholds user privacy and informed consent. In summary, the co-creation session provided essential insights, highlighting the value of early PwPD involvement to enhance the CMFT's relevance, usability, and patient-centeredness. This approach not only aligns with patient-centred design principles but also reinforces the CMFT's potential as a practical tool for PwPD, healthcare professionals, and caregivers within the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem.

10.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Posture/Balance
Concept(s) of interest	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MDS-UPDRS item 3.8 (Leg agility) 2. MDS-UPDRS item 3.9 (Arising from chair) 3. MDS-UPDRS item 3.13 (Posture) 4. MDS-UPDRS item 3.10 (Gait)
Measurement technology	A Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) is implemented that makes use of four modified MDS-UPDRS-related motor tasks, combining it with continuous video-based human body tracking.
Type of measurement	Active
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital score for each item obtained by training ML models using angular, speed, acceleration features related to the joints involved in the item.
Validation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Small-scale study using a cohort of 17 volunteer PD patients and capturing videos of them performing a sequence of four items from the MDS-UPDRS motor tests
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The smartphone video capturing the data is reliable, with minimal noise or distortions affecting the quality of the video-based human body tracking. • The Mediapipe pose landmark detection algorithm functions consistently and accurately, identifying joint positions and movements without significant errors.

¹⁰ <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/341996/9789240029200-eng.pdf?sequence=1>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients adhere to the CMFT protocol, maintaining proper positioning within the camera’s field of view and performing the tasks as instructed. • The smartphone used for recordings has adequate computational power to process the video data and store landmarks without interruptions or lag. • Environmental factors such as lighting, clothing and room setup are optimized to ensure clear visibility and accurate video-based human body tracking.
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients must adhere to the CMFT protocol to ensure accurate data capture, such as staying within the camera’s field of view during all tasks. The camera should be correctly positioned in a well-lit room, ideally with a chair placed appropriately for tasks that require sitting or standing. The smartphone used for recording must have adequate computational power and storage capacity to support the seamless execution of the test, particularly for running Mediapipe pose landmark detection without interruptions or delays. Proper environmental setup and device readiness are crucial to maintaining the integrity of the assessment.

11 Cognitive function active assessment

11.1 Background and objectives

Cognitive impairment in patients with Parkinson’s disease (PD) is a very common non-motor manifestation during the course of the disease and includes subjective cognitive decline (SCD), mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and PD dementia (PDD) (Degirmenci, 2023). Approximately 10% to 20% of PwPD show a mild cognitive impairment, and approximately 46% of PwPD develop PD dementia (PDD) within 10 years after diagnosis (Hähnel, 2023).

In deliverable D2.3 “Initial report on domain review and datasets”, a detailed description of recent studies on digital assessments of cognitive decline is provided. AI-PROGNOSIS aims to assess cognitive function using active cognitive tests, as well as in a passive way through the interaction of users with their smartphone. For this first set of dBMs, the focus has been placed on the active cognitive tests. Three tests, hereafter also referred to as “cognitive tasks” or “tasks”, were integrated within the AI-PROGNOSIS mAI-Health application for smartphones that will be used in the dBM-DEV study, from an open-source tablet-based cognitive test battery designed by partner TUD.

An existing dataset acquired using the tablet-based implementation of the three tests from 97 PD patients was used to develop and evaluate dBMs of cognitive function, as described in the following sections. The dBMs will be further verified using data that will be collected in the dBM-DEV study using the smartphone-based implementation of the active cognitive tests.

11.2 Methods

11.2.1 Datasets

An open-source tablet-based cognitive test battery (Feige et al., 2024) guided the implementation of the AI-PROGNOSIS active cognitive tests. A dataset collected via those

tablet-based tests was used for the development of the initial version of the associated dBMs. The dataset contains 97 entries, corresponding to 97 PD patients that completed three cognitive Tasks (N-Back, Bart and Stop Signal). Each entry contains values for: a) features from the three cognitive Tasks (performed once) and b) the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MOCA; Nasreddine et al., 2005) score of the patient.

Table 34 Demographics of the subjects included in the active cognitive tests dataset

Variable	Mean (SD)
Age, years	62.8 (10.1)
Disease Duration, years	6.4 (4.7)
Age at onset in years	56.3 (10.5)
DA Dose, mg	243.8 (141.6)
Levodopa Dose, mg	418.4 (197.7)
LEDD, mg	672.3 (338.8)
MoCA Score	26.4 (2.8)
UPDRS III Score	62.8 (10.1)
FAB Score	6.4 (4.7)
SCD, positive/total	56.3 (10.5)

Note. Data is depicted as mean (SD) except for SCD (positive cases/total cases). Abbreviations: DA - Dopamine Agonist; FAB - Frontal Assessment Battery; LEDD - Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose; MoCA - Montreal Cognitive Assessment; SCD - Subjective Cognitive Decline; UPDRS III - Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale Part III.

The corresponding study was approved by the institutional review board of Technische Universität Dresden (BO-EK-494112020) and written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Participants were recruited from the Department of Neurology at Dresden University Hospital. The inclusion criteria were individuals aged 18 and above who met the diagnostic criteria for PD, as stipulated by the Movement Disorder Society (Postuma, 2015). Individuals with severe cognitive or psychiatric disorders that could impede the successful completion of the cognitive test battery were excluded.

The three tests, Stop-Signal, Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART), and N-Back Test, that were integrated into the mAI-Health app, developed within WP4 “The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem” and presented in the upcoming deliverable D4.1 “The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem (Alpha version)”, are described below.

11.2.2 Digital biomarkers

Stop-Signal task

Participants see a circle in the middle of the screen with two buttons – one on the left and one on the right of the circle. In each trial, participants see an arrow inside the circle pointing either left or right. Participants are instructed to click on the button that the arrow points to (“go” trials). If a red cross appears (**Figure 39**), participants should suppress their reactions and not press any button (“stop” trials). The red cross initially appears 250 ms after the arrow and dynamically adjusts based on the participant's performance, i.e., if the reaction is suppressed, the time increases by 50 ms and if not, the time decreases by 50 ms. After the practice, the

test round consists of four Blocks with 50 trials each. The features extracted from the Stop-Signal task are listed in **Table 35**.

Figure 39 Indicative screenshot of the stop-signal test. Depicted is the 4:3 aspect ratio from the iPad Version used in Feige et al. (2024).

Table 35 Features extracted from the Stop-Signal task.

Variable Name	Description
StopSignal_totalCorrect	Total number of correct responses across all trials.
StopSignal_correct_go	Number of correct responses in "go" trials.
StopSignal_correct_stop	Number of correct suppressions in "stop" trials.
StopSignal_max_value_delay_high	Maximum time delay value for the stop signal (red cross) in the High condition.
StopSignal_max_value_delay_low	Maximum time delay value for the stop signal (red cross) in the Low condition.
StopSignal_StopSignal_RT_mean_go	Average reaction time for "go" trials.

Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART)

Depicted is the 4:3 aspect ratio from the iPad Version used in Feige et al. (2024). Participants see a balloon pump and a small balloon in the middle of the screen (**Figure 40**). At the bottom of the screen, there is a button labelled "Collect Points." Participants are instructed to tap on the balloon pump to inflate the balloon. Each pump earns one point. At a random threshold that varies from trial to trial, the balloon flies away and the accumulated points are lost. Participants can end a round at any time by tapping the "Collect Points" button to secure the earned points, thus concluding the trial. The objective is to earn as many points as possible. After a practice round of four trials, the test round consists of 20 trials. The maximum number of pumps before the balloon flies away ranges from 1 to 50. The features extracted from the BART are listed in **Table 36**.

Figure 40 Indicative screenshot of the Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART). Depicted is the 4:3 aspect ratio from the iPad Version used in Feige et al. (2024).

Table 36 Features extracted from the Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART).

Variable Name	Description
bart_correctedPumps	Number of pumps per trial adjusted for average number of pumps before the balloon would have flown away.
bart_changeAfterBurst	Changes in participant behaviour following a balloon flying away. This is the differences in pumps between the trial the balloon flew away and the following one.
bart_didBurst	Indicator of whether the balloon flew away in a trial.
bart_correctedTotal	Total adjusted score adjusted for average number of pumps before the balloon would have flown away.

N-Back task

Participants see an image along with a green and a red button (**Figure 41**). They are instructed to tap the green button if the displayed image is the same as the one shown 1 to n images before or the red button if this is not the case. After a practice round of ten trials with feedback, there are two test rounds ($n = 1, n = 2$), each with 50 trials without feedback. The stimuli are displayed for 1,200 ms, and participants have 3,000 ms to respond.

Figure 41 Indicative screenshot of the N-Back Task. Depicted is the 4:3 aspect ratio from the iPad Version used in Feige et al. (2024).

Table 37 Features extracted from the N-Back task; n-back level $\equiv n$.

Variable Name	Description
NBack_correct_sum_load_1.0	Total number of correct responses for n-back level 1.
NBack_correct_sum_load_2.0	Total number of correct responses for n-back level 2.
NBack_rt_mean_load_1.0	Average reaction time for correct responses at n-back level 1.
NBack_rt_mean_load_2.0	Average reaction time for correct responses at n-back level 2.
NBack_rt_std_load_1.0	Standard deviation of reaction time for n-back level 1.
NBack_rt_std_load_2.0	Standard deviation of reaction time for n-back level 2.

Features in **Table 35-Table 37** were clipped at $\pm 3 \times$ interquartile range (IQR) to minimize the influence of extreme outliers.

11.2.3 Selection of digital biomarkers

In order to determine the association of features derived from these tests with the MoCA, we first grouped the participating PD patients with respect to their MoCA scores (ranging between 18-30) into 3 balanced classes/groups: Group 1: 18-21, Group 2: 22-25, and Group 3: 26-30. We then trained a model to predict the group of a PD patient based on the available features from all tasks (**Table 35-Table 37**).

We first scaled each feature to the range of [0,1] and then computed the Pearson correlation of each individual feature in **Table 35-Table 37** with the corresponding MoCA score. These correlations were found to be moderate. The features with the stronger correlations were:

Table 38 Features with maximum correlation with MoCA scores

Feature	Pearson Correlation	Significance
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NBack_rt_std_load_1.0	-0.56	0.0000000
NBack_correct_sum_load_1.0	0.49	0.0000003
StopSignal_correct_go	0.45	0.0000033

We then applied different ML models to predict the MoCA groups. Specifically, we trained five ML classifiers for this task, i.e., i) KNN, ii) SVM, iii) RF, iv) combination of PCA and KNN, and v) combination of supervised PCA (sPCA) (Ghojogh. 2019)) and KNN. The Leave-One-Out cross-validation approach was used for validation. We have also implemented an additional feature selection step by identifying a subset of N features (N=3) that have the largest correlation with the corresponding target (MoCA group), and then using only these features for prediction.

For each classifier, we optimized a few important parameters during training using grid search: i) KNN: $n_neighbors(2/3/4)$, $weights(distance/uniform)$, ii) SVM: $C(1/3/5)$ and kernel (rbf/linear), iii) RF: $n_estimators(100/200/1000)$ and $max_features(log3/sqrt)$, iv) PCA+KNN: $n_components(2/3)$ and $n_neighbors(2/3)$, v) sPCA+KNN: $n_components(2/3)$ and $n_neighbors(2/3)$. For detailed descriptions for these hyperparameters we refer the reader to the python implementations of the ML classifiers in <https://scikit-learn.org/>.

11.3 Results

After hyperparameter optimization, validation results using Leave One Sample Out validation with or without the feature selection step are presented in **Table 39**. As seen, for most classifiers, the feature selection step does not result to improved performance, while the best result is provided using PCA+KNN without using feature selection.

Table 39 Accuracy and (weighted) Precision, Recall, and F1 scores for ML classifiers after hypertuning (with or without using feature selection) using Leave One Out cross-validation. Best performing ML classifiers are shown in bold.

With feature selection	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63
SVM	0.68	0.65	0.68	0.66
RF	0.65	0.62	0.65	0.64
PCA+KNN	0.61	0.62	0.61	0.61
sPCA+KNN	0.61	0.62	0.61	0.61
Without feature selection	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
KNN	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.66
SVM	0.64	0.61	0.64	0.62
RF	0.62	0.58	0.62	0.59
PCA+KNN	0.69	0.68	0.69	0.68
sPCA+KNN	0.66	0.65	0.66	0.66

11.4 Discussion

11.4.1 Interpretation

We observed a moderate correlation between features extracted from the three active cognitive tests and the MoCA score. Accordingly, ML models trained with features extracted from the three active cognitive tests did not discriminate well between the three MOCA groups.

We consider it unlikely that selecting alternative features or using more participants will substantially change this finding. Rather, these findings can be explained by the fact that the active cognitive tests were chosen to complement the MoCA – and not to replace it. The MoCA is a well-established, brief cognitive screening test, so establishing dBM to replace the MoCA is not a priority. Moreover, performance in the MoCA does not change rapidly (1 year intervals are recommended), so establishing home monitoring for MoCA also is not a priority.

In contrast, changing medication in patients with PD can cause much more rapid cognitive changes, including changes in impulse control. These domains are not covered in the MoCA. The active cognitive tests were chosen to cover these domains that include response inhibition (Stop signal task) and impulse control (BART) to complement the MoCA. The N-back test is associated with executive function and memory. Accordingly, features of the N-back test correlated best with the MoCA score. Validating the utility of these active tests will require patients with medication changes as investigated in the AI-PMP study.

11.4.2 Usability of digital biomarkers in the context of current care

The three selected active tests that have been already integrated within the AI-PROGNOSIS mobile app will be further verified in the dBM-DEV and AI-PMP study, where effects of medication and medication changes can be investigated.

During the next period of the project, the passive assessment of cognitive function based on typing patterns will be investigated, leveraging keystroke-related data collected in the dBM-DEV study. In particular, we plan to:

1. estimate a set of keystroke dynamics features, such as HT and FT (see Section 8.2.2), but for specific key sequences, such as ‘delete’ – ‘delete’, ‘any key’ – ‘delete’, ‘any key’ – ‘space key’, which can be derived from the data collected by the custom keyboard used in the dBM-DEV study.
2. employ and evaluate ML approaches to estimate the corresponding clinical cognitive function assessment score.

Similar approaches for developing dBM of human cognitive function and mood have been proposed by Dagum (2018, 2019).

11.5 Summary

Digital assessment ID	
Meaningful health aspect	Cognitive function
Concept(s) of interest	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Memory (N-Back Task), 2. Risk-taking behaviour (Bart Task) 3. Attention (Stop Signal Task)
Measurement technology	Cognitive test battery
Type of measurement	Active
Proposed digital biomarker(s)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ML-models for evaluation of cognitive function - classification into three classes (low/medium/high) - based on patient performance in all three Tasks.
Validation	Training and validation of ML models were based on a) digital data (features) from 97 PD patients who used the tablet-based implementation of the three tests and b) their corresponding MoCA scores.

Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classification into 3 classes (low/medium/high) corresponding to different MoCA score ranges.
Context of use considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be used only by patients with MoCA scores larger or equal to 18.

12 Open science

The AI-PROGNOSIS project fully embraces the principles of Open Science to promote transparency, accessibility, and reproducibility in research. This approach aligns with global efforts to make scientific outputs more accessible to the public, including stakeholders, such as clinicians, patients, and policymakers. Our open science practices are particularly informed by the CTTI, which emphasizes responsible data sharing and collaborative research.

12.1 Data sharing and accessibility

A core principle of CTTI is the ethical and secure sharing of clinical study data. The AI-PROGNOSIS project adheres to these guidelines by ensuring that all raw data collected within the project, including extracted features and indicators, are anonymized and shared in accordance with data protection regulations (such as GDPR). Our data will be deposited in the Zenodo repository, ensuring broad access for the research community and, in general, safety and adherence to FAIR (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) data sharing principles - details will be provided in the data management plan of the project (D1.6). Opening datasets will allow for independent validation and meta-analyses, contributing to more robust scientific findings.

12.2 Collaborative Research and Multi-Stakeholder Engagement

CTTI encourages the involvement of multiple stakeholders in clinical research. AI-PROGNOSIS is built on a foundation of collaboration between academic institutions, clinical researchers, patient advocacy groups, and industry partners. By making both data and tools open and accessible, the project fosters a collaborative research environment where stakeholders can participate in the evaluation and application of dBMs in real-world settings.

12.3 Publication and reporting standards

AI-PROGNOSIS follows open access publishing standards, ensuring that all findings related to the project are available in fully open-access journals per the Horizon Europe framework requirements. This aligns with CTTI's emphasis on transparent reporting and reduces the barriers for clinicians, patients, and the broader public to access crucial scientific knowledge. In addition to sharing final results, preprints and intermediate reports will be made available to ensure ongoing knowledge transfer during the lifecycle of the project. By aligning with CTTI's guidelines on data sharing, multi-stakeholder collaboration, and transparency, AI-PROGNOSIS ensures that its research not only advances scientific understanding but also supports the broader community working toward improved patient outcomes.

13 Conclusions

This deliverable reports on the first stages and outputs of developing and validating dBMs for PD based on existing datasets. Based on data from wrist-wearable, user-smartphone

interaction, and active digital tests, we investigated and identified, in certain cases, promising dBMs of motor and cognitive function, RBD, and daytime somnolence. In **Table 40** you can find a summary of the Objectives, Key Features, Results and Challenges for all dBMs included in this deliverable

Table 40 Summary table with Objectives, Key Features, Results and Challenges for all dBMs

Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD)
<p>Objective: Early detection of RBD using actigraphy data; focus on distinguishing RBD from other conditions.</p> <p>Key Features: Activity rate, movement episodes, episode duration, skewness metrics, and sleep period boundaries were evaluated as key differentiators.</p> <p>Results: Machine learning models like Random Forest achieved balanced accuracy up to 89.2% with SMOTE augmentation. Statistical features demonstrated clear separation between RBD and non-RBD groups.</p> <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of nightly ground truth data for RBD occurrence. - Small dataset sizes and label inconsistencies (e.g., nightly vs subject-level labels). - Variability in data due to sporadic RBD episodes.
Daytime Somnolence
<p>Objective: Detect and quantify daytime sleep episodes using actigraphy and clustering-based methods.</p> <p>Key Features: Gaussian mixture models utilized features from sliding time windows of actigraphy data; segment-based clustering identified nap episodes.</p> <p>Results: 90% overlap between clustering results and Philips Actiware algorithm; detected naps were validated manually or via diaries with 99% accuracy.</p> <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High noise levels in actigraphy data. - Participant diaries underreported naps compared to automated detection. - Sensitivity differences between clustering and existing algorithms.
Rest Tremor
<p>Objective: Detect and classify tremor severity using wearable accelerometer data.</p> <p>Key Features: Frequency, amplitude, and tremor pattern metrics formed the basis of tremor classification.</p> <p>Results: High accuracy was achieved in tremor classification using machine learning models (e.g., Random Forest). Validated across datasets like MJFF-LRS.</p> <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dataset imbalance and limited real-world validation. - Potential confounding effects from voluntary and involuntary movements. - Generalization of models across diverse patient populations.
Dyskinesia
<p>Objective: Track dyskinesia severity using accelerometer data for real-time monitoring.</p> <p>Key Features: Features related to movement frequency and amplitude variations were explored for dyskinesia assessment.</p> <p>Results: Preliminary models showed promise in distinguishing dyskinesia from normal movements. Limited data collection for validation.</p> <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distinguishing dyskinesia from other voluntary and involuntary movements.

- Lack of annotated datasets for rigorous training and testing.
- Dependence on high-quality accelerometer data.

Human Activity Recognition and Physical Activity

Objective: Evaluate mobility and physical activity levels using wearable devices for insights into disease progression.

Key Features: Activity counts, gait transitions, and state-switching metrics were used to quantify activity levels.

Results: Models demonstrated reliability in classifying activity levels and transitions, aiding in tracking disease progression.

Challenges:

- Individual variability in activity levels and patterns.
- Limited datasets representing diverse PD symptom severities.
- Noise and inconsistencies in real-world wearable data.

Slowness of Movement (Keystroke Dynamics)

Objective: Assess finger and hand bradykinesia and rigidity through typing patterns on touchscreens.

Key Features: Statistical features of key hold time and between-keys flight time sequences during natural typing.

Results: A regression model was trained on in-clinic-collected typing data to predict the finger tapping item (Item 23) of UPDRS Part III. The model was tested on a separate dataset including typing data collected in the wild and the digital score exhibited high correlation with the associated clinical score (UPDRS Item 23) ($r = 0.84$, $p < 0.05$).

Challenges:

- Small sample size of the in-clinic training dataset
- Lack of handedness information in the in-the-wild dataset
- Effect of medication (ON-OFF) periods and covariates of keystroke dynamics

Slowness of Movement (Wrist Accelerometry)

Objective: Assess slowness of gross upper limb movement through a wrist-worn accelerometer.

Key Features: Features extracted from time-windowed 3-axis accelerometer signals during hand movement and no gait periods.

Results: A pipeline including a hand movement detector, a gait detector and a slowness of movement estimator was implemented. For the slowness of movement estimator, a regressor was trained with acceleration features derived from the Verily Study Watch dataset to predict a composite clinical score of MDS-UPDRS Part III items related to bradykinesia and rigidity. The digital score exhibited a correlation of $r = 0.66$ ($p < 0.05$) with the clinical composite score and differed significantly between severity categories.

Challenges:

- Lack of information regarding the hand wearing the accelerometer
- Validation of the approach with an external dataset
- Effect of covariates of acceleration (age, sex, body-mass index)

Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT)

Objective: Evaluate posture, balance, and motor coordination through active camera-based motion tracking assessments.

Key Features: Joint angles, posture symmetry, and movement time series were captured and analysed with motion-tracking pipelines.

Results: Models effectively correlated movement features with clinical scores for motor impairment (e.g., UPDRS Part III). High precision in detecting abnormalities in gait, posture, and transitions.

Challenges:

- Limited datasets for validating complex multi-movement assessments.
- Variability in patient engagement during active assessments.
- Dependency on controlled environments for reliable data capture.

Cognitive Function Active Assessment

Objective: Assess cognitive decline in PD patients through digital cognitive tasks like Stop-Signal, Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART), and N-Back tests.

Key Features: Task completion times, accuracy rates, and derived metrics such as reaction time variability and task-specific scores.

Results: Machine learning models trained on extracted features demonstrated good prediction accuracy of cognitive status. Correlations between digital task scores and MoCA scores validated dBM effectiveness.

Challenges:

- Larger, more diverse datasets are needed to generalize cognitive assessments.
- Variability in task performance due to patient familiarity and engagement.
- Balancing task complexity with usability for diverse patient groups.

Looking ahead, the next phase of dBM development will focus on the following key areas:

- **Validation and verification in the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical studies:** dBM implementations reported here will be improved and validated based on data from the project's upcoming dBM-DEV study (NCT06444789). Amongst others, a development/validation dataset that will advance the research in RBD dBM's will be collected in the study.
- **Input to predictive models:** Besides long-term disease monitoring, the project will explore the utility of dBM's in predicting future clinical outcomes. The validated dBM's will serve as input to the predictive models of PD risk, progression, and medication response developed in tasks T3.4-T3.6, the first version of which will be reported in D3.2 "First report on predictive modelling for PD".
- **Optimisation for online processing:** Pipelines of validated dBM's will be optimised for online operation and integrated with the AI-PROGNOSIS mobile applications and back-end developed in WP4 "The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem".
- **Towards real-world application:** Collaboration with key stakeholders, including PwPD and healthcare professionals (HCPs), as part of the task T2.2 "User research and co-creation" activities, will be intensified to refine the integration of the dBM's in the minimum viable products that AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop (the mAI-Health/Care apps and the mAI-Insights HCPs' platform). This will include discussing and optimising the use cases of the AI-PROGNOSIS tools with regard to the existing clinical workflows and diagnosis/treatment pathways.

Our initial results constitute a considerable step toward the creation of the AI-PROGNOSIS system of dBM's and in general the validation and potential use of dBM's for PD screening and management. Moreover, the adoption of open science practices, highlighted in this report, is crucial in ensuring the impact of AI-PROGNOSIS on both the scientific and PD community. By sharing data, code, and results, we will foster the transparency and reproducibility of our findings, and encourage other researchers to build upon those findings, ultimately advancing the way PD is monitored.

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Appendix I – Interview guide script for the CMFT co-creation session

Interview Guide Script
<p>Usability and perceived usefulness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• How useful do you find the CMFT for assessing your motor function, particularly balance and posture, compared to traditional methods?• Considering ease of navigation and clarity of instructions, how confident are you in using the CMFT effectively?
<p>Easy of use and accessibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• How easy do you anticipate learning to use the CMFT, especially with Parkinson’s related motor difficulties in mind?• Do you foresee any accessibility barriers hindering your ability to interact effectively with the CMFT?
<p>User engagement-intention to use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• How likely are you to incorporate the CMFT into your routine for motor function assessment?• To what extent do you find the CMFT engaging compared to other assessment tools?
<p>User engagement-attitude towards using</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• How do you perceive the overall user experience of the CMFT, and how does it influence your enthusiasm to use it?

Appendix II – Supplementary documents

The following documents are collated to this report.

S.1 Approval of the small-scale data collection in Papanikolaou General Hospital of Thessaloniki for the CMFT development (in Greek)

S.2 Consent form for the small-scale data collection in Papanikolaou General Hospital of Thessaloniki for the CMFT development (in Greek)

“Γ. ΠΑΠΑΝΙΚΟΛΑΟΥ”

ΓΕΝΙΚΟ ΝΟΣΟΚΟΜΕΙΟ ΘΕΣΣΑΛΟΝΙΚΗΣ

ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΔΗΜΟΚΡΑΤΙΑ
3^η ΥΓΕΙΟΝΟΜΙΚΗ ΠΕΡΙΦΕΡΕΙΑ
ΜΑΚΕΔΟΝΙΑΣ

ΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΟΝΙΚΟ ΣΥΜΒΟΥΛΙΟ

Τηλ. 2313 307134

Εξοχή 27.9.2024

Αρ. Πρωτ. 1357

ΠΡΟΕΔΡΟΣ

Καθηγητής Π. Γκιβίσης
Διευθυντής Α Ορθοπαιδικής
Κλινικής ΑΠΘ

ΤΑΚΤΙΚΑ ΜΕΛΗ

Θ. Καραϊσκος
Διευθυντής ΕΣΥ Θωρακο-
Καρδιοχειρουργική
Κλινική

Μ. Σίλελη
Διευθύντρια ΕΣΥ
Β ΜΕΘ

Β. Τσουτσούλη
Επιμελήτρια Α'
Παθολογικό Τμήμα

Ε. Πετσατώδης
Επιμελήτης Β
Ακτινοδιαγνωστικό Τμήμα

Αθ. Πάνος
Ειδικευόμενος ιατρός
ορθοπαιδικής

Α. Παπαδοπούλου
Βιοχημικός
Μονάδα Γονιδιακής
Κυτταρικής θεραπείας-
Αιματολογικό Τμήμα-ΜΜΜΟ

Κ. Δαφνοπούλου
Τεχνολόγος Ιατρικών
Εργαστηρίων Αιματολογικό
Εργαστήριο

Ι. Χατζηλία
Νοσηλεύτρια ΠΕ
Παθολογικό Τμήμα

ΑΝΑΠΛΗΡΩΜΑΤΙΚΑ
ΜΕΛΗ

Ι. Μπάτσος
Διευθυντής ΕΣΥ
Αιματολογικό Τμήμα-ΜΜΜΟ

Σ. Τσιρώνη
Διευθύντρια ΕΣΥ
Οφθαλμολογικό Τμήμα

Μ. Σαρόγλου
Επιμελήτρια Α
Πνευμονολογικό Τμήμα ΕΣΥ

Αθ. Κυργίδης
Επιμελήτης Β
Κλινική ΣΓΠΧ ΑΠΘ

Κ. Τσιακτζής
Διευθυντής Φαρμακείου

Θ. Δημητριάδης
Τεχνολόγος ιατρικών
εργαστηρίων- Αιμοδυναμικό
Εργαστήριο

Π. Χρίστογλου
Ειδικευόμενος ιατρός
νευροχειρουργικής

**Θέμα: Διαβίβαση εισήγησης της 6^{ης}/24.4.2024 Τακτικής Συνεδρίασης του
Επιστημονικού Συμβουλίου του Γ.Ν.Θ. «Γ.Παπανικολάου».**

Σας διαβιβάζουμε την σχετική με την έγκριση διεξαγωγής ερευνητικού έργου στη Γ' Νευρολογική Κλινική ΑΠΘ με τίτλο «AI Prognosis: Artificial Intelligence –based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis», εισήγηση της 6^{ης}/24.4.2024 (θέμα 102^ο) Τακτικής Συνεδρίασης του Επιστημονικού Συμβουλίου του Γ.Ν.Θ. «Γ. Παπανικολάου» για ενημέρωσή σας.

Για το Επιστημονικό Συμβούλιο
Ο Πρόεδρος

Παναγιώτης Γκιβίσης

“Γ. ΠΑΠΑΝΙΚΟΛΑΟΥ”
ΓΕΝΙΚΟ ΝΟΣΟΚΟΜΕΙΟ ΘΕΣΣΑΛΟΝΙΚΗΣ

ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΔΗΜΟΚΡΑΤΙΑ
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ΜΑΚΕΔΟΝΙΑΣ
ΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΟΝΙΚΟ ΣΥΜΒΟΥΛΙΟ
Τηλ. 2313 307134

ΠΡΟΕΔΡΟΣ

Καθηγητής Π. Γκιβίσσης
Διευθυντής Α Ορθοπαιδικής
Κλινικής ΑΠΘ

ΤΑΚΤΙΚΑ ΜΕΛΗ

Θ. Καραϊσκος
Διευθυντής ΕΣΥ Θωρακο-
Καρδιοχειρουργική
Κλινική

Μ. Σίλελη
Διευθύντρια ΕΣΥ
Β ΜΕΘ

Β. Τσουτσούλη
Επιμελήτρια Α
Παθολογικό Τμήμα

Ε. Πετσατώδης
Επιμελήτης Β
Ακτινοδιαγνωστικό Τμήμα

Αθ. Πάνος
Ειδικευόμενος ιατρός
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Α. Παπαδοπούλου
Βιοχημικός
Μονάδα Γονιδιακής
Κυτταρικής Θεραπείας-
Αιματολογικό Τμήμα-ΜΜΜΟ

Κ. Δαφνοπούλου
Τεχνολόγος Ιατρικών
Εργαστηρίων Αιματολογικό
Εργαστήριο

Ι. Χατζηλία
Νοσηλεύτρια ΠΕ
Παθολογικό Τμήμα

**ΑΝΑΠΛΗΡΩΜΑΤΙΚΑ
ΜΕΛΗ**

Ι. Μπάτσος
Διευθυντής ΕΣΥ
Αιματολογικό Τμήμα-ΜΜΜΟ

Σ. Τσιρώνη
Διευθύντρια ΕΣΥ
Οφθαλμολογικό Τμήμα

Μ. Σαρόγλου
Επιμελήτρια Α
Πνευμονολογικό Τμήμα ΕΣΥ

Αθ. Κυργίδης
Επιμελήτης Β
Κλινική ΣΓΠΧ ΑΠΘ

Κ. Τσιακιτζής
Διευθυντής Φαρμακείου

Θ. Δημητριάδης
Τεχνολόγος ιατρικών
εργαστηρίων- Αιμοδυναμικό
Εργαστήριο

ΠΡΑΚΤΙΚΑ

6^{ης} Τακτικής Συνεδρίασης

Στην Εξοχή Θεσσαλονίκης σήμερα 24.4.2024 ημέρα Τετάρτη ύστερα από την με αρ. πρωτ. 569/19.4.2024 πρόσκληση του Προέδρου, κ. Παναγιώτη Γκιβίσση, έλαβαν μέρος στη συνεδρίαση που πραγματοποιήθηκε στην αίθουσα συνεδριάσεων του Διοικητικού Συμβουλίου (κτίριο Διοίκησης) στις 9π.μ. τα παρακάτω μέλη του Επιστημονικού Συμβουλίου:

Πρόεδρος: Παναγιώτης Γκιβίσσης

Μέλη: Θ. Καραϊσκος, Μ. Σίλελη, Β. Τσουτσούλη, Ε. Πετσατώδης, Κ. Τσιακιτζής, Ι. Χατζηλία, Αθ. Πάνος, Κ. Δαφνοπούλου.

Από τη συνεδρίαση απουσίασε ο κ. Αθ. Πάνος και η κ. Α. Παπαδοπούλου και συμμετείχε ο αναπληρωτής της ο κ. Κ. Τσιακιτζής.

Στη συνεδρίαση μετέχει η κ. Βαλεντίνη Παπαγεωργίου, ως Γραμματέας του Επιστημονικού Συμβουλίου.

Ο Πρόεδρος κ. Παναγιώτης Γκιβίσσης κηρύσσει την έναρξη της συνεδρίασης με τις παρακάτω Ανακοινώσεις και θέματα της Ημερήσιας Διάταξης:

24.04.2024

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Θέμα 102ο: Έγκριση διεξαγωγής ερευνητικού έργου στη Γ' Νευρολογική Κλινική ΑΠΘ με τίτλο «AI Prognosis: Artificial Intelligence –based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis».

Το Επιστημονικό Συμβούλιο κατά την 6^η/24.4.2024 Τακτική Συνεδρίασή του αφού έλαβε υπόψη:

1. Το με αρ. πρωτ. 565/18.4.2024 αίτημα του κ. Δ. Κάζη, Διευθυντή στη Γ' Νευρολογική Κλινική ΑΠΘ για τη διεξαγωγή ερευνητικού έργου στην εν λόγω κλινική με τίτλο «AI Prognosis: Artificial Intelligence –based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis». Η εν λόγω μελέτη βασίζεται στη χρήση τεχνολογιών αξιόπιστης τεχνητής νοημοσύνης (TN) στο πλαίσιο μιας διεπιστημονικής προσέγγισης με σκοπό να βελτιώσει τη διάγνωση της νόσου και τη φροντίδα των ασθενών με Πάρκινσον μέσω 1) υλοποίησης νέων, προγνωστικών μοντέλων TN για εξατομικευμένη εκτίμηση του κινδύνου εμφάνισης της νόσου, 2) εφαρμογής ενός συστήματος βιοδεικτών που θα ενημερώνουν τα μοντέλα TN με την παρακολούθηση βασικών δεικτών κινδύνου/προόδου στην καθημερινή ζωή, 3) δημιουργίας μιας εργαλειοθήκης TN, η οποία θα υποστηρίζει τους επαγγελματίες υγείας στην ανίχνευση και παρακολούθηση της εξέλιξης της νόσου και στην επιλογή της βέλτιστης θεραπείας. Πρόκειται για έργο που συγχρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Επιτροπή στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος Horizon Europe και η υλοποίηση του γίνεται σε συνεργασία με το Ινστιτούτο Πληροφορικής και Επικοινωνιών (ΙΠΤΗΛ) του ΕΚΕΤΑ. Για τους σκοπούς της έρευνας θα πραγματοποιούνται καταγραφές ασθενών με νόσο του Πάρκινσον που παρακολουθούνται στη Γ' Νευρολογική Κλινική ΑΠΘ με απώτερο στόχο την ανάπτυξη των σχετικών αλγορίθμων.
2. Τα επισυναπτόμενα έγγραφα: Περίληψη πρωτοκόλλου στα ελληνικά, έντυπο συγκατάθεσης κατόπιν ενημέρωσης, σχετική βιβλιογραφία.
3. Το γεγονός ότι δεν επιβαρύνεται οικονομικά το νοσοκομείο.
4. Μετά από τη διεξοδική συζήτηση μεταξύ των μελών του

ομόφωνα εγκρίνει και εισηγείται

τη διεξαγωγή ερευνητικού έργου στη Γ' Νευρολογική Κλινική ΑΠΘ με τίτλο «AI Prognosis: Artificial Intelligence –based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis». Η εν λόγω μελέτη βασίζεται στη χρήση τεχνολογιών αξιόπιστης τεχνητής νοημοσύνης (TN) στο πλαίσιο μιας διεπιστημονικής προσέγγισης με σκοπό να βελτιώσει τη διάγνωση της νόσου και τη φροντίδα των ασθενών με Πάρκινσον μέσω 1) υλοποίησης νέων, προγνωστικών μοντέλων TN για εξατομικευμένη εκτίμηση του κινδύνου εμφάνισης της νόσου, 2) εφαρμογής ενός συστήματος βιοδεικτών που θα ενημερώνουν τα μοντέλα TN με την παρακολούθηση βασικών δεικτών κινδύνου/προόδου στην καθημερινή ζωή, 3) δημιουργίας μιας εργαλειοθήκης TN, η οποία θα υποστηρίζει τους επαγγελματίες υγείας στην ανίχνευση και παρακολούθηση της εξέλιξης της νόσου και στην επιλογή της βέλτιστης θεραπείας. Πρόκειται για έργο που συγχρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Επιτροπή στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος Horizon Europe και η υλοποίηση του γίνεται σε συνεργασία με το Ινστιτούτο Πληροφορικής και Επικοινωνιών (ΙΠΤΗΛ) του ΕΚΕΤΑ. Για τους σκοπούς της έρευνας θα πραγματοποιούνται καταγραφές ασθενών με νόσο του Πάρκινσον που παρακολουθούνται στη Γ' Νευρολογική Κλινική ΑΠΘ με απώτερο στόχο την ανάπτυξη των σχετικών αλγορίθμων. Δεν επιβαρύνεται οικονομικά το νοσοκομείο.

Το Επιστημονικό Συμβούλιο κατά την 6^η/24.4.2024 Τακτική Συνεδρίασή συζήτησε το:

Θέμα 102ο: Εγκριση διεξαγωγής ερευνητικού έργου στη Γ' Νευρολογική Κλινική ΑΠΘ με τίτλο «AI Prognosis: Artificial Intelligence –based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis».

Ο Πρόεδρος
του
Επιστημονικού Συμβουλίου

Παναγιώτης Γκιβίσης

Τα Μέλη

Θ. Καραϊσκος (παρών)

Μ. Σίλελη (παρούσα)

Β. Τσουτσούλη (παρούσα)

Ε. Πετσατώδης (παρών)

Κ. Τσιακιτζής (παρών)

Ι. Χατζηλία (παρούσα)

Κ. Δαφνοπούλου (παρούσα)

Η Γραμματέας

Β. Παπαγεωργίου

**Μελέτη AI-PROGNOSIS (ειδικά δεδομένα):
Συλλογή καταγραφών βίντεο μέσω κινητού
τηλεφώνου για την ανάπτυξη ευφυών μεθόδων
ανίχνευσης της νόσου του Πάρκινσον με
επικύρωση από ιατρικές αξιολογήσεις**

ΕΝΗΜΕΡΩΤΙΚΟ ΔΕΛΤΙΟ

ΕΝΗΜΕΡΩΤΙΚΟ ΔΕΛΤΙΟ

Όνομα και στοιχεία επικοινωνίας του οργανισμού/υπεύθυνου επεξεργασίας δεδομένων	Εθνικό Κέντρο Έρευνας και Τεχνολογικής Ανάπτυξης (ΕΚΕΤΑ) – ΙΝΣΤΙΤΟΥΤΟ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΩΝ ΠΛΗΡΟΦΟΡΙΚΗΣ ΚΑΙ ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΝΙΩΝ (ΙΠΤΗΛ) 6ο χλμ Χαριλάου - Θέρμης, 57001, Θέρμη – Θεσσαλονίκη, E-mail: info@iti.gr , Τηλέφωνο: +30 2311 257701-3
Τίτλος ερευνητικού έργου	Το παρόν πείραμα διεξάγεται στο πλαίσιο του έργου "AI-PROGNOSIS - AI-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis", το οποίο χρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Επιτροπή με τη συμφωνία επιχορήγησης αριθ. 101080581, μέσω του προγράμματος-πλαίσιου "Horizon Europe".
Σκοπός του πειράματος και της συλλογής δεδομένων	Μέσω του πειράματος το ΙΠΤΗΛ σκοπεύει να συλλέξει δεδομένα καταγραφών βίντεο για την εξαγωγή σκελετικών σημείων και την αξιοποίηση αυτών από αλγορίθμους βαθμονόμησης ικανοτήτων κίνησης ασθενών με Πάρκινσον στο πλαίσιο υλοποίησης του ως άνω αναφερόμενου ερευνητικού έργου.
Υπεύθυνος επικοινωνίας για τη δραστηριότητα	Δρ. Κοσμάς Δημητρόπουλος, email: dimitrop@iti.gr
Περιγραφή επεξεργασίας	Σε αυτό το πείραμα, ασθενείς με Πάρκινσον θα πραγματοποιήσουν τις παρακάτω αξιολογήσεις από το τεστ MDS-UPDRS: 3.8, 3.9, 3.10, 3.13, μπροστά σε μία κάμερα κινητού τηλεφώνου. Οι ασθενείς θα καταγράφονται κατά την πραγματοποίηση των αξιολογήσεων. Η διαδικασία μπορεί να διακοπεί προσωρινά ή να τερματιστεί ανά πάσα στιγμή κατόπιν αιτήματος του χρήστη.
Πιθανοί κίνδυνοι	Δεν υπάρχουν προβλέψιμοι κίνδυνοι από τη συμμετοχή σε αυτό το πείραμα.
Κίνητρα	Δεν υπάρχουν οφέλη/κίνητρα για τους συμμετέχοντες - εθελοντές.
Γενικές πληροφορίες σχετικά με τα δεδομένα που θα συλλεχθούν	Στο παρόν πείραμα, θα πραγματοποιηθεί καταγραφή βίντεο μέσω κινητού τηλεφώνου. Τα δεδομένα που θα συλλεχθούν θα αποθηκευτούν αποκλειστικά σε ψευδο-ανώνυμη μορφή. Ειδικότερα, η κάθε καταγραφή θα αντιστοιχεί σε κωδικό αριθμό συμμετέχοντα και η αντιστοίχιση θα είναι

	<p>διαθέσιμη μόνο στην ιατρό κ. Μποστταντζοπούλου, που είναι η υπεύθυνη ιατρός των ασθενών. Επιπλέον, η ηλικία και το φύλο του συμμετέχοντα/εθελοντή θα συλλεχθούν για στατιστικούς λόγους. Από τα δεδομένα που θα συλλεχθούν μέσω του βίντεο, θα εξαχθούν τα σκελετικά σημεία που θα χρησιμοποιηθούν από ευφυείς μεθόδους ανίχνευσης της νόσου του Πάρκινσον. Τα αρχικά δεδομένα που θα συλλεχθούν μέσω του βίντεο θα καταστραφούν μόλις εξαχθούν τα ως άνω παραγόμενα δεδομένα. Η επεξεργασία δεδομένων περιορίζεται στα προσωπικά δεδομένα που είναι απαραίτητα και κατάλληλα για την εκπλήρωση των σκοπών και των λειτουργιών του πειράματος.</p> <p>Η επεξεργασία υπόκειται στους κανόνες και τις θεμελιώδεις αρχές προστασίας δεδομένων του Γενικού Κανονισμού για την Προστασία Δεδομένων (ΓΚΠΔ), στους εθνικούς νόμους περί προστασίας δεδομένων και στις σχετικές διεθνείς συνθήκες και συμβάσεις.</p> <p>Όσον αφορά τα δεδομένα προσωπικού χαρακτήρα που συλλέγονται κατά τη διεξαγωγή του πειράματος, η επεξεργασία είναι απαραίτητη για τους επιδιωκόμενους επιστημονικούς σκοπούς του έργου, και ιδίως για τη δημιουργία μοντέλων βαθιάς μάθησης όσον αφορά τα πρότυπα προσοχής του βλέμματος και για στατιστικούς λόγους.</p> <p>Η επεξεργασία των δεδομένων βασίζεται στην προηγούμενη ρητή συγκατάθεσή σας για τον συγκεκριμένο σκοπό επεξεργασίας (άρθρο 6 παρ. 1α' ΓΚΠΔ) Τα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα διατηρούνται από το ΕΚΕΤΑ/ΙΠΤΗΛ μόνο για το εύλογο χρονικό διάστημα που απαιτεί η φύση της επεξεργασίας και μόνο για όσο χρονικό διάστημα απαιτείται για την επίτευξη των παραπάνω σκοπών επεξεργασίας, εκτός εάν απαιτείται μεγαλύτερη περίοδος διατήρησης από το νόμο ή για τη θεμελίωση, άσκηση ή υπεράσπιση νομικών αξιώσεων Το ΕΚΕΤΑ/ΙΠΤΗΛ δεν θα διαβιβάσει, πωλήσει, ενοικιάσει ή ανταλλάξει ποτέ τα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα σε τρίτους για σκοπούς μάρκετινγκ ούτε θα διαβιβάζει τα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα εκτός της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης/ΕΟΧ.</p> <p>Τα προσωπικά δεδομένα που συλλέγονται κατά τη διάρκεια του πειράματος είναι αυστηρά</p>
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εμπιστευτικά. Λαμβάνονται τα κατάλληλα τεχνικά και οργανωτικά μέτρα για την εξασφάλιση του κατάλληλου επιπέδου προστασίας από τους κινδύνους που απορρέουν από την επεξεργασία, όπως η τυχαία ή παράνομη καταστροφή, απώλεια, αλλοίωση, μη εξουσιοδοτημένη αποκάλυψη ή πρόσβαση.

Σύμφωνα με τον ΓΚΠΔ, έχετε τα ακόλουθα δικαιώματα:

- **Δικαίωμα πρόσβασης:** Έχετε το δικαίωμα να ζητήσετε πρόσβαση στα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα σύμφωνα με το άρθρο 15 του ΓΚΠΔ. Με την άσκηση αυτού του δικαιώματος, μπορείτε να ενημερωθείτε εάν επεξεργαζόμαστε τα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα, για τον σκοπό και τον τρόπο επεξεργασίας τους, την ασφάλειά τους, καθώς και για τα δικαιώματά σας. Μπορείτε επίσης να ζητήσετε δωρεάν αντίγραφο των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων που υφίστανται επεξεργασία.

- **Δικαίωμα διόρθωσης:** Εάν πιστεύετε ότι τα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα είναι ανακριβή ή χρήζουν επικαιροποίησης, έχετε το δικαίωμα να ζητήσετε τη διόρθωση των ανακριβών πληροφοριών και τη συμπλήρωση των ελλειπών δεδομένων, σύμφωνα με το άρθρο 16 του ΓΚΠΔ.

- **Δικαίωμα περιορισμού της επεξεργασίας:** Εάν θεωρείτε ότι τα δεδομένα σας είναι ανακριβή ή ότι η επεξεργασία είναι παράνομη ή ότι δεν χρειαζόμαστε πλέον τα δεδομένα σας ή ότι έχετε αντιρρήσεις για την αυτοματοποιημένη επεξεργασία, έχετε το δικαίωμα να ζητήσετε τον περιορισμό της επεξεργασίας, σύμφωνα με τις απαιτήσεις του άρθρου 18 ΓΚΠΔ.

- **Δικαίωμα εναντίωσης στην επεξεργασία:** Έχετε το δικαίωμα να αντιταχθείτε, για λόγους που σχετίζονται με την ιδιαίτερη κατάστασή σας, ανά πάσα στιγμή στην επεξεργασία των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων, εκτός εάν υπάρχουν επιτακτικοί νόμιμοι λόγοι για την επεξεργασία που υπερσχύουν των συμφερόντων, των δικαιωμάτων και των ελευθεριών σας ή για τη θεμελίωση, άσκηση ή υπεράσπιση νομικών αξιώσεων.

- **Δικαίωμα διαγραφής ("δικαίωμα στη λήθη"):** Όταν δεν επιθυμείτε πλέον την επεξεργασία και τη διατήρηση των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων,

έχετε το δικαίωμα να ζητήσετε τη διαγραφή τους, εκτός εάν η επεξεργασία είναι απαραίτητη για συγκεκριμένο νόμιμο σκοπό σύμφωνα με το άρθρο 17 ΓΚΠΔ.

- **Δικαίωμα φορητότητας:** έχετε το δικαίωμα να λάβετε ή να διαβιβάσετε τα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα σε δομημένο, κοινώς χρησιμοποιούμενο και αναγνώσιμο από μηχανήματα μορφότυπο σε άλλον υπεύθυνο επεξεργασίας, σύμφωνα με το άρθρο 20 του ΓΚΠΔ.

- **Δικαίωμα να μην υποβληθείτε σε αυτοματοποιημένη ατομική λήψη αποφάσεων, συμπεριλαμβανομένης της κατάρτισης προφίλ:** έχετε το δικαίωμα να μην υποβληθείτε σε απόφαση που βασίζεται αποκλειστικά σε αυτοματοποιημένη επεξεργασία, συμπεριλαμβανομένης της κατάρτισης προφίλ, η οποία παράγει έννομα αποτελέσματα που σας αφορούν ή σας επηρεάζει με παρόμοιο τρόπο σημαντικά. Σημειώνεται ότι στο πλαίσιο του παρόντος πειράματος δεν πραγματοποιείται αυτοματοποιημένη ατομική λήψη αποφάσεως ή κατάρτιση προφίλ.

- **Δικαίωμα ανάκλησης της συγκατάθεσής σας:** Έχετε το δικαίωμα να ανακαλέσετε τη συγκατάθεσή σας ανά πάσα στιγμή.

Σημειώστε ότι τα προαναφερθέντα δικαιώματα ενδέχεται να περιοριστούν υπό το πρίσμα του ΓΚΠΔ ή άλλης ισχύουσας νομοθεσίας περί προστασίας δεδομένων.

Για να ασκήσετε τα δικαιώματά σας, μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε με τον υπεύθυνο της δραστηριότητας, Δρ. Κοσμάς Δημητρόπουλος, στο email dimitrop@iti.gr. Θα απαντήσουμε στο αίτημά σας εντός (1) ενός μηνός από την παραλαβή του και χωρίς καμία επιβάρυνση για εσάς. Η παραπάνω προθεσμία ενδέχεται να παραταθεί για δύο (2) ακόμη μήνες, λόγω της πολυπλοκότητας ή του αριθμού των αιτημάτων. Σε μια τέτοια περίπτωση θα ενημερωθείτε για την παράταση του χρόνου και τους λόγους αυτής, το συντομότερο δυνατό.

Σε περίπτωση που το αίτημά σας θεωρηθεί αβάσιμο, το ΕΚΕΤΑ/ΙΠΤΗΛ μπορεί να αρνηθεί να απαντήσει σε αυτό ή να επιβάλει εύλογο τέλος.

Τέλος, εάν πιστεύετε ότι το αίτημά σας δεν ικανοποιήθηκε επαρκώς ή ότι παραβιάστηκε η

ΕΝΗΜΕΡΩΤΙΚΟ ΔΕΛΤΙΟ

	προστασία των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων από την επεξεργασία του ΕΚΕΤΑ/ΠΤΗΛ, έχετε το δικαίωμα να υποβάλετε καταγγελία στην Αρχή Προστασίας Δεδομένων Προσωπικού Χαρακτήρα.
Ο συμμετέχων/εθελοντής πρέπει να διαβάσει και να κατανοήσει το ενημερωτικό δελτίο και μόνο εάν συμφωνεί με αυτό, θα υπογράψει το έντυπο συγκατάθεσης.	
Η συμμετοχή σε αυτό το πείραμα είναι απολύτως εθελοντική. Η άρνηση συμμετοχής ή η ανάκληση της συγκατάθεσης για τη συμμετοχή και τη συλλογή - διαδικασία των δεδομένων δεν θα έχει δυσμενείς συνέπειες.	
Οι συμμετέχοντες είναι ελεύθεροι, χωρίς αρνητικές συνέπειες, να αρνηθούν τη συμμετοχή τους ή να αποσύρουν τις συνααινέσεις και τη συμμετοχή τους στην έρευνα χωρίς να δώσουν εξηγήσεις ανά πάσα στιγμή μέχρι το τέλος του έργου. Εάν οι συμμετέχοντες επιλέξουν να αποσυρθούν, όλα τα δεδομένα που θα συλλεχθούν θα καταστραφούν. Εάν ο συμμετέχων/εθελοντής επιθυμεί να ανακαλέσει τη συγκατάθεσή του, να ασκήσει τα δικαιώματά του ή εάν έχει οποιαδήποτε απορία σχετικά με την προστασία των προσωπικών του δεδομένων εν γένει, μπορεί να απευθύνει το αντίστοιχο αίτημά του επικοινωνώντας με τον υπεύθυνο της δραστηριότητας, Δρ. Κοσμά Δημητρόπουλο, στο dimitrop@iti.gr .	

Έντυπο συγκατάθεσης κατόπιν ενημέρωσης

Σκοπός του έργου με τίτλο "AI-PROGNOSIS - AI-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis" είναι η εξαγωγή σκελετικών αρθρώσεων κατά την εκτέλεση των στοιχείων του MDS-UPDRS από άτομα με Πάρκινσον. Το παρόν πείραμα διεξάγεται στο πλαίσιο του ως άνω έργου και περιλαμβάνει την καταγραφή βίντεο για την εξαγωγή σκελετικών σημείων και την αξιοποίηση αυτών από αλγορίθμους βαθμονόμησης ικανοτήτων κίνησης ασθενών με Πάρκινσον.

Η συμμετοχή σας σε αυτό το πείραμα είναι δυνατή μόνο εάν μας παρέχετε ελεύθερα και ρητά την συγκατάθεσή σας για την επεξεργασία των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων. Εάν δεν επιθυμείτε να το κάνετε, παρακαλείστε να μην συμμετάσχετε σε αυτό το πείραμα.

Δήλωση Συγκατάθεσης

Εγώ(όνομα & επώνυμο) συμφωνώ να συμμετάσχω σε αυτό το πείραμα του ΕΚΕΤΑ/ΙΤΙ, στο πλαίσιο του έργου με τίτλο "AI-PROGNOSIS - AI-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis", που χρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Επιτροπή με τη συμφωνία επιχορήγησης αριθ. 101080581, μέσω του προγράμματος-πλαισίου "Horizon Europe".

- Έχω διαβάσει και κατανοήσει τις πληροφορίες που περιέχονται στο παρόν δελτίο πληροφοριών ή μου έχουν διαβαστεί με κατάλληλο τρόπο. Έχουν απαντηθεί όλες οι ερωτήσεις μου σχετικά με το πείραμα και τη συμμετοχή μου σε αυτό.

- Δεν μου ασκήθηκε καμία πίεση και μου δόθηκε αρκετός χρόνος για να αποφασίσω αν ήθελα να συμμετάσχω σε αυτό το πείραμα.

ΕΝΗΜΕΡΩΤΙΚΟ ΔΕΛΤΙΟ

- Γνωρίζω ότι η συμμετοχή είναι εθελοντική. Γνωρίζω ότι μπορώ ανά πάσα στιγμή να αποφασίσω να μη συμμετάσχω τελικά ή να αποσυρθώ από το πείραμα χωρίς συνέπειες/κυρώσεις. Γνωρίζω ότι δεν χρειάζεται να δώσω οποιαδήποτε εξήγηση για αυτό.

- Έχω ενημερωθεί επαρκώς και με τρόπο απλό και πλήρως κατανοητό για τον τρόπο συλλογής και επεξεργασίας των προσωπικών δεδομένων μου που σχετίζονται με αυτό το πείραμα .

- Έχω ενημερωθεί για τα δικαιώματά μου, όπως αυτά απορρέουν από τον Γενικό Κανονισμό για την Προστασία Δεδομένων ("ΓΚΠΔ").

- Συναινώ ελεύθερα και ρητά στη συλλογή και επεξεργασία των προσωπικών μου δεδομένων για την εκπλήρωση των σκοπών και των εργασιών του πειράματος.

- Επιπλέον, συναινώ στην διατήρηση και χρήση των δεδομένων μου με σκοπό τη δευτερογενή χρήση αυτών για περαιτέρω μελλοντική έρευνα.

- Επιβεβαιώνω ότι είμαι άνω των 16 ετών.

ΟΝΟΜΑΤΕΠΩΝΥΜΟ:

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ΥΠΟΓΡΑΦΗ:

ΗΜΕΡΟΜΗΝΙΑ:

.....

.....

Συμπληρώνεται από τον ερευνητή που έλαβε τη συγκατάθεση:

ΟΝΟΜΑΤΕΠΩΝΥΜΟ ΕΡΕΥΝΗΤΗ:

.....

ΥΠΟΓΡΑΦΗ:

ΗΜΕΡΟΜΗΝΙΑ:

.....

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